

Accelerating circular bio-based solutions integration in European rural areas

D2.3 European Rural Bioeconomy Network creation and stakeholders mapping (2nd update)

Responsible Author: AVEBIOM

Biorural.eu

Grant Agreement No.	101060166
Project Acronym	BioRural
Project Title	Accelerating circular bio-based solutions integration in European rural areas
Type of action	CSA - Coordination and Support Actions
Horizon Europe Call Topic	HORIZON-CL6-2021-CIRCBIO-01-08: Mainstreaming inclusive small-scale bio-based solutions in European rural areas
Start – ending date	1 September 2022 – 31 August 2025
Project Website	https://Biorural.eu/
Work Package	WP2: European Rural Bioeconomy Network and success stories
WP Lead Beneficiary	ASOCIACION ESPANOLA DE LA VALORIZACION ENERGETICA DE LA BIOMASA (AVEBIOM)
Relevant Task(s)	T2.1: Development of European Rural Bioeconomy Network; T2.2: Liaison with related existing networks and projects
Deliverable type Dissemination level	R – Report PU: Public
Due Date of Deliverable	31 August 2025
Actual Submission Date	14 November 2025
Responsible Author	Daniel García, Pablo Rodero, Alicia Mira (AVEBIOM)
Contributors	ALL partners
Reviewer(s)	CERTH

Document History

Date	Version	Changes	Contributor(s)
02/06/2025	V0.0	First Version (Template)	Daniel García (AVEBIOM)
07/07/2025	V1.0	First draft (including partners inputs in stakeholder mapping and liaison)	All partners to sections 2.3 (national plans), and 3.3.2 & 3.3.3 (liaison with projects and networks). CERTH to Section 3.2 AVEBIOM to whole sections
15/07/2025	V2.0	Second draft (complete document; punctual inputs pending for review; Integration of RBP aggregated data)	Individual partners inputs. RBP leaders (DELPHY, CERTH, IUNG, AVEBIOM) additions. AVEBIOM comprehensive review and integration of last inputs
31/07/2025	V2.1	Last updates of data and ERBN subscriptions (sections #2 and #3)	RBP leaders last inputs. AVEBIOM comprehensive review and integration of last inputs.

7/08/2025	V2.3	Update of section #4, executive summary, conclusions and annexes.	AVEBIOM updates section #4 and performs the last aggregation of data for executive summary.
25/08/2025	V3.0	Reviewed second draft, with small upgrades in text.	Bas Paris and Dimitris Michas (CERTH)
25/08/2025	V4.0	Consolidated version, including update of deliverable history of changes	AVEBIOM in Review of last inputs and last addition to Deliverable info tables.
29/08/2025	V5.0	Final version	CERTH Final review
14/11/2025	V6.0	Revised Final Version	AVEBIOM and CERTH

Disclaimer

Funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or European Research Executive Agency. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them

**Funded by
the European Union**

© BioRural Consortium, 2025

BioRural Consortium			
Participant Nr.	Participant organisation name	Short name	Country
1	ETHNIKO KENTRO EREVNAS KAI TECHNOLOGIKIS ANAPTYXIS	CERTH	EL
2	DELPHY BV	DELPHY	NL
3	ASSOCIATION DU POLE DE COMPETIVITE VALORIAL	VALORIAL	FR
4	NATUREPLAST SAS	NATUREPLAST SAS	FR
5	IZES GGMBH	IZES	DE
6	AARHUS UNIVERSITET	AU	DK
7	INSTYTUT UPRAWY NAWOZENIA I GLEBOZNAWSTWA, PANSTWOWY INSTYTUT BADAWCZY	IUNG-PIB	PL
8	VMU DIDZIOJO UNIVERSITETAS	VMU	LT
9	LATVIJAS LAUKSAIMNIECIBAS UNIVERSITATE	LLU	LV
10	ASOCIACION ESPANOLA DE LA VALORIZACION ENERGETICA DE LA BIOMASA	AVEBIOM	ES
11	UNIVERSIDADE DE COIMBRA	UC	PT
12	CENTRO DA BIOMASSA PARA A ENERGIA	CBE	PT
13	AIEL ASSOCIAZIONE ITALIANA ENERGIE AGROFORESTALI	AIEL	IT
14	REFRAME FOOD ASTIKI MI KERDOSKOPIKI ETAIRIA REFRAME.FOOD	RFF	EL
15	INCOMMON NON-PROFIT CIVIL LAW COMPANY	ICO	EL
16	UNIVERZA V LJUBLJANI	UL	SI
17	ALGEN, CENTER ZA ALGNE TEHNOLOGIJE, DOO	ALGEN	SI
18	ASOCIATIA GREEN ENERGY	GEA	RO

19	ZDRUZENIE PLATFORMA ZA ZELEN RAZVOJ SKOPJE	GGP	MK
----	--	-----	----

ACRONYMS and definitions	
Short name	Definition
#Tag	Bioeconomy themes are tagged for the key actors identified in each of the 14 BioRural countries. These tags are defined in section 2.1.
AKIS	Agricultural Knowledge and Innovation System - AKIS refers to the network of organizations and people involved in generating, sharing, and using knowledge and innovation in agriculture. It aims to improve the flow of information between researchers, advisors, farmers, and other stakeholders.
CB	Circular Bioeconomy
DX.Y	Deliverable report for work package X, number Y
eoKPI	Expected Outcome KPI, key performance indicator to measure the reach of project towards the achievement of expected outcomes described in the project Grant Agreement.
Key actor	Actors who are relevant to implement BioRural actions, or to create the ERBN community and network
MX	Month X of BioRural project
OG	Operational groups
PC	Project coordinator
PA	Practice Abstract, a concise, practitioner-oriented summary that presents a project or a solution with practical recommendations in a clear and accessible way. It is used to facilitate knowledge exchange, promote innovations, and connect stakeholders across agriculture, forestry, and rural sectors.
PO	Project Officer for a EU project, person from CINEA who manages EU-funded projects from programs like Horizon Europe, Connecting Europe Facility (CEF), and the LIFE Programme.
RBA	Rural bioeconomy Alliance, cluster of EU-funded projects established on May 31, 2023, to accelerate and support the development of circular bioeconomy initiatives in rural areas of the European Union. The RBA's purpose is to facilitate collaboration, knowledge sharing, and the dissemination of best practices, success stories, and pilot projects among its member projects.
RBP	Internal Nomenclature of BioRural to define the 4 regional clusters, Rural Bioeconomy Platforms being: SW, SE, NW, NE. BioRural countries are distributed there as follows: SW (Spain, Portugal, Italy), SE (Greece, Slovenia, Romania, North Macedonia), NW (Netherlands, Germany, France, Denmark); NE (Poland, Lithuania, Latvia).
SME	Small and Medium Enterprises
Stakeholder	Any potential actor interested in the information or adoption of Circular Bioeconomy Solutions and Practices.
SWOT	SWOT analysis is a strategic planning tool used to identify a project's or organization's Strengths, Weaknesses, Opportunities, and Threats. It helps in understanding internal and external factors to support decision-making and strategy development.
thERBN	EU Funded Project - Thematic European Rural Bioeconomy Network. It aims to create an EU multi-actor thematic network which bridges the gap between innovative circular bioeconomy solutions and small farms & foresters. It will be based on BioRural ERBN community, and evolve towards thematic network with a coordinating structure connected to national AKIS.

Executive Summary

The D2.1 and D2.2 reports on the engagement of key players in the project countries and the status of liaison with other EU projects have been updated in this document. It summarises the key actors' participation status at the conclusion of the BioRural project and correlates to the state at M36.

Similar to D2.2, this document is organised into three sections based on three "areas of action," or domains, wherein key players must be engaged and liaison activities with projects and networks must be conducted. From the standpoint of BioRural strategy, these actions have been essential to growing an ERBN community and supporting the implementation and effect of BioRural actions.

Area of action #1 - National & subnational (section #2)

Promoting the up-scale adoption of small-scale bio-based solutions suitable for rural areas is the ultimate goal of BioRural. The organisations, businesses, government agencies, and other stakeholders deemed essential to either (a) support and carry out BioRural initiatives or (b) assist in the creation of an operational European Rural Bioeconomy Network, or ERBN, are referred to as "key actors" under this document. In addition to operating at the EU level, BioRural is present in 14 EU countries. Since the beginning of the project, BioRural partners have carried out a concerted action of reconciliation in order to achieve the positive participation of important actors. They reported this at M12 in D2.1, at M24 in D2.2, and now at M36 in D2.3. Section 2 of this document presents the outcomes of direct engagement with relevant actors.

As result of the engagement, it has been possible to achieve next indicators:

- The coordination and reporting of involvement status has been grouped by geographic regions known as RBPs (Rural Bioeconomy Platforms), as was previously done in D2.1.
- As of the current reporting period in M36, partners have identified 1,212 key actors who may be relevant to the implementation and support of BioRural or to the successful uptake of project outcomes. This suggests 81 additional important players in relation to the 1,131 actors listed in M24 (under D2.2).
- **943 significant players have been contacted** in total, 659 of them have done so through meetings, e-meetings, and phone calls, with an additional 117 added during the most recent period, M24–M36.
- **441 key actors** (36% of the 1,212 identified) **have already participated** in project actions as a result of this initial rapprochement, which is 85 higher than at M24.
- Of the 1,212 key actors identified, **305 (25%), have gone above and beyond in their collaboration with BioRural**. They have co-organized events, assisted with the preparation of workshops, reported success stories, among other actions. They add 76 collaborators more than at M24.
- There are currently **616 members of the ERBN community**, of whom 376 are key actors or organisations that have been identified, while 240 are stakeholders—individuals, businesses, organisations, and recipients of project outcomes—rather than key actors to execute BioRural or ERBN. This accomplishment surpasses the goal of reaching 400 ERBN members by the project's conclusion. 574 members have been added primarily through subscriptions made using the BioRural toolkit, while 42 individuals and groups have done so by formally expressing interest. In regard of the gender balance, the share male – female of the persons registered through the toolkit remains paired, 50% with an improvement from M24 to M36 of 1 percentile.

Section #2 presents details of these achievements aggregated by each geographical RBP (SW, SE, NW, NE). The individual country updates are presented as an Appendix to this deliverable.

Area of action #2 – Bioeconomy Networks and projects (section #3)

Under this area, three main results are described: (1) the status of RBA - Rural Bioeconomy Alliance and (2) the status of connection and collaboration with EU and national projects, and (3) the status of connection and collaboration with EU and national networks.

Rural Bioeconomy Alliance - RBA (section 3.2)

The creation and launch of this group of EU-funded bioeconomy initiatives took place in May 2023 (Month M9 for BioRural). Through the RBA, individual EU projects focused on small-scale solutions and rural areas can collaborate more effectively and have a greater influence on the bioeconomy. It was established as one of eleven EU-funded projects. To link and strengthen BioRural and the 11 RBA projects, a total of 29 separate collaborations between BioRural and RBA project partners went into force at month M24.

The RBA has grown to include 19 project members in 2024 and 2025. Nevertheless, some of them—like BioRural—have completed or plan to complete it by 2025. The partnerships of BioRural have persisted and **succeeded in leveraging 50 synergies with RBA initiatives**, primarily through national-level activities such as workshop organisation, participation in BioRural activities (challenges, surveys), or effective dissemination promotion.

Liaison with national and EU projects (section 3.3)

The second sub-action line is the individual liaison of BioRural partners with EU and national projects.

A total of three long term EU initiatives has been identified: **EU-Farmbook, modernAKIS and Tools4CAP. 5 synergies have been leveraged.** It should be noted the agreement to link the BioRural toolkit with EU-Farmbook, which began in 2025, and will continue with the project thERBN once BioRural is completed.

Partners have **identified a total of 35 EU project and 8 national projects** to establish synergies with. **About EU projects**, a total of **63 synergies were discussed, leveraging 52 collaborations** by end of BioRural project. In respect the **national 8 funded projects**, **17 potential synergies** were identified, and **gave rise to 15 effective individual collaborations.**

Liaison with national and EU Networks (section 3.4)

Concerning CAP Networks, the **EU CAP network** has already reached out to a short-term collaborator for T1.2 at M24. Additionally, info about BioRural initiatives has been shared via the EU CAP network website. Eleven of the National CAP Networks in the 14 BioRural countries have been approached in this regard. Eight coordination activities and synergies—not merely informational meetings—took place in order to spread BioRural activities, such as workshops, via respective channels. More than only specific synergies, a number of partners also kept in regular touch, which allowed information to be shared both ways.

Liaison with **other EU and national networks** has proceeded with different level of involvement. In respect EU networks, several **referential sectorial or non-specific networks** linked to bioeconomy were identified. **Several synergies (totalling 5)** were leveraged, as follows: Bioenergy Europe as speaker in BioRural online tutorials; the ICA - Association for European Life Science Universities to promote the EU Challenge; or ERIAFF - European Regions for Innovation in Agriculture, Food and Forestry to disseminate BioRural.

In terms of **EU bioeconomy networks**, **8 have been identified.** A total of **6 individual collaborations** have been achieved by BioRural partners before finishing the project. Some examples are the Community of Practice for Bioeconomy Education in Europe (ICA-CoP Bio-Edu), Biorefine Cluster Europe, ERDN - European Rural Development Network and the CIGR Bioeconomy Network. Notwithstanding these collaborations were in general

weaker than with EU and National projects or national Networks, where the mutual interests were found to be stronger and easier to realise.

National networks, either related to bioeconomy, or on specific bioeconomy topics, have revealed to be quite effective and synergistic to trigger collaborations. Over the course of the project, **BioRural partners have identified 24 pertinent national networks** in the 14 BioRural countries. The approach has led to **identify up to 40 potential synergies**. A total of **34 individual collaborations** has been leveraged.

Area of action #3 – ERBN internal structure (section #4)

The third area of action for the ERBN strategy is the **creation of the internal structure of organisations** to assume the **management of the network** following BioRural's completion. At M12 partners agreed to build a management structure with key actors interested to steer and manage the ERBN. As result of the internal discussions, BioRural partners **found by M16 that the best option** to add value through this network was to **keep ERBN specific and thematic**.

In addition to the project, a number of partners and other important players have worked together to develop this thematic network. Initial relationships with **EU-Farmbook and the CIRC-Bio sister projects** (RuralBioUp, Scale-Up, MainstreamBio) **have prepared the groundwork** for resource discovery **and the presentation of a plan to turn the ERBN** asset being developed by BioRural **into a thematic network** spanning the entire EU. The **new project thERBN** was conceived and leaded in a collaboration of University Ghent (leader of EU-Farmbook) with some key partners from BioRural, RuralBioUp, Scale-Up and MainstreamBio. The new project entitled thERBN – Thematic European Rural Bioeconomy Network, started 1st January 2025.

thERBN and BioRural have shared hands-on work on ERBN during 2025. The coordinated actions are additive and complementary. Two periods can be distinguished (1) prior to the thERBN start date (1st January 2025), where BioRural has continued working in the expansion of the ERBN community and BioRural toolkit functionalities; and (2) following thERBN start date (1st January 2025 and beyond), when BioRural has kept working on ERBN community growth, and fine-tuning the BioRural toolkit with a few functionalities. During this period great interactions have taken place, and thERBN has started with the excellent base created by BioRural.

Already at M24 BioRural drafted a series of recommendations to continue growing the ERBN. They are summarised in form of a total of 10 Strategy lines, described in D2.2, and reproduced here in section #4.2. There is already a plan of action for the months of September 2025–December 2027 once BioRural is complete. In order to turn ERBN into a theme network and to activate it as an active network on CB that is specifically important for farmers, foresters, and their advisors, this program adheres to the ten strategy lines.

Table of Contents

1	Introduction	10
1.1	About this document	10
1.2	Structure of the document	11
1.3	About BioRural actions through project and in last period M24-M36	12
2	Area of action #1: key actors and stakeholders at national level	13
2.1	Introduction	13
2.2	SW RBP Results – Status at M36	14
2.2.1	SW RBP Overview	14
2.2.2	Highlights by SW RBP country: Spain, Italy and Portugal	19
2.3	SE RBP Results – Status at M24	21
2.3.1	SE RBP Overview	21
2.3.2	Highlights by SE RBP country: Greece, Slovenia, Romania and North Macedonia	27
2.4	NW RBP Results – Status at M24	28
2.4.1	RBP NW Overview	28
2.4.2	Highlights by NW RBP country: The Netherlands, Denmark, Germany and France	34
2.5	NE RBP Results – Status at M24	36
2.5.1	RBP NE Overview	36
2.5.2	Highlights by NE RBP country: Poland, Latvia and Lithuania	41
2.6	Aggregated indicators for all RBPs and ERBN	42
3	Area of action #2. Bioeconomy networks and projects	49
3.1	Introduction	49
3.2	The Rural Bioeconomy Alliance – RBA	49
3.2.1	About RBA	49
3.2.2	RBA members and coordination	50
3.2.3	Results – Status at M36	50
3.3	Liaison with national and EU projects	51
3.3.1	Liaison with RBA projects	52
3.3.2	Liaison with long term EU initiatives	57
3.3.3	Liaison with EU funded projects	58
3.3.4	Liaison with National funded projects	67
3.4	Liaison with national and EU networks	70
3.4.1	EU CAP Network and National CAP Networks	70
3.4.2	Liaison with EU relevant networks	72
3.4.3	Liaison with National networks	73
4	Area of action #3: establishing a durable ERBN structure	78
4.1	Introduction	78
4.2	Actions and status at M24	78
4.3	ERBN evolution and status by end of BioRural project	81
5	Conclusions	84
	Appendix	86

List of Figures

Figure 1. BioRural and regional organization into geographic RBPs	10
Figure 2. BioRural and ERBN: the three areas of action to set the strategies	11
Figure 3. SW RBP: summary of identified key actors profiles by M36	14
Figure 4. SW RBP: status of activation of key actors at M36 LEFT: Identified VS Approached. RIGHT: distribution of achievements by type of key actor	17
Figure 5. SW RBP: Quadrant diagram and evolution for the period M12 – M36	18
<i>Figure 6. SW RBP: Achievements in the enrolment of key actors and stakeholders into the ERBN by M36. LEFT: achievements vs target; RIGHT: disaggregation by profile</i>	19
Figure 7. SE RBP: summary of identified key actors' profiles by M36	21
Figure 8. SE RBP: status of activation of key actors at M36. LEFT: Identified VS Approached. RIGHT: distribution of achievements by type of key actor	24
Figure 9. SE RBP: Quadrant diagram and evolution for the period M12 – M36	25
Figure 10. SE RBP: Achievements in the enrolment of key actors and stakeholders into the ERBN by M36. LEFT: achievements vs target; RIGHT: disaggregation by profile	27
Figure 11. NW RBP: summary of identified key actors' profiles by M36	29
Figure 12. NW RBP: status of activation of key actors at M36. LEFT: Identified VS Approached. RIGHT: distribution of achievements by type of key actor	31
Figure 13. NW RBP: Quadrant diagram and evolution for the period M12 – M36	32
Figure 14. NW RBP: Achievements in the enrolment of key actors and stakeholders into the ERBN. By M36 LEFT: achievements vs target; RIGHT: disaggregation by profile	34
Figure 15. NE RBP: summary of identified key actors' profiles by M36	36
Figure 16. NE RBP: status of activation of key actors at M36. LEFT: Identified VS Approached. RIGHT: distribution of achievements by type of key actor	38
Figure 17. NE RBP: Quadrant diagram and evolution for the period M12 – M36	39
Figure 18. NE RBP: Achievements in the enrolment of key actors and stakeholders into the ERBN by M36. LEFT: achievements vs target; RIGHT: disaggregation by profile	40
Figure 19. BioRural RBPs: summary of identified key actors profiles by M36.	43
Figure 20. BioRural RBPs: status of activation of key actors at M36. LEFT: Identified VS Approached. RIGHT: distribution of achievements by type of key actor	45
Figure 21. BioRural ERBN: Achievements in the enrolment of key actors and stakeholders into the ERBN by M36 in the 14 BioRural countries. LEFT: achievements vs target; RIGHT: disaggregation by profile	47
Figure 22. Gender distribution in the ERBN in M18 and M36 (registrants through toolkit)	47
Figure 23. Gender distribution according to ERBN members profile. Data in M18 and M36	48
Figure 24. Rural Bioeconomy Alliance – RBA: logo and participating projects at date August 2025	50

List of Tables

Table 1. Tags utilized in BioRural to classify the key actor profile	13
Table 2. Tags utilized in BioRural to classify the key actors themes of bioeconomy	13
Table 3. SW RBP: Bioeconomy themes coverage at M36 of project	15
Table 4. SW RBP: Actions performed to approach key actors by M36	16
Table 5. SE RBP: Bioeconomy themes coverage at M36 of project	22
Table 6. SE RBP: Actions performed to approach key actors by M36	23
Table 7. NW RBP: Bioeconomy themes coverage at M36 of project	29
Table 8. NW RBP: Actions performed to approach key actors by M36	30
Table 9. NE RBP: Bioeconomy themes coverage at M36 of project	37
Table 10. NE RBP: Actions performed to approach key actors by M36	37
Table 11. BioRural RBPs: Bioeconomy themes coverage at M36 of project	43
Table 12. BioRural RBPs: Actions performed to approach key actors by M36	44
Table 13. Distribution of the ERBN community members in the 14 BioRural countries along the project periods	46
Table 14. Series of tables to track synergies with the RBA projects	52
Table 15. Series of tables to track synergies with Long term EU Initiatives	57
Table 16. Series of tables to track synergies with EU funded projects	58
Table 17. Series of tables to track synergies with National funded projects	68
Table 18. Series of tables to track synergies with EU and national CAP Networks	71
Table 19. Series of tables to track synergies with EU sectorial clusters and organisations	72
Table 20. Series of tables to track synergies with EU bioeconomy networks	72
Table 21. Series of tables to track synergies with National networks	73
Table 22. SWOT analysis performed by M24 on the re-scoping of ERBN towards thematic division and post-project continuity	79
Table 23. Strategic actions for ERBN as derived from SWOT analysis performed in M24 by BioRural partners	79
Table 24. Strategic actions performed by BioRural before and after the starting date of thERBN project	81
Table 25. Timeline of ERBN progress after BioRural finishes	82

1 Introduction

1.1 About this document

The aim of BioRural is to establish a European network of rural Bioeconomy stakeholders by:

- developing 4 regional Rural Bioeconomy Platforms (RBP) in a geographic context, to connect neighbouring countries and identify commonalities, stimulate knowledge exchange, cooperation and collaboration and assist on developing future rural Bioeconomy initiatives.
- liaising with Bioeconomy networks and projects, to further support the knowledge transfer and the impact and reach of BioRural, by identifying synergies and agreeing upon formal collaborations

BioRural works parallel in 14 countries and has established an internal structure of organization by dividing the project actions in 4 EU geo-regions, called RBP - Rural bioeconomy Platforms, as depicted below in Figure 1.

Figure 1. BioRural and regional organization into geographic RBPs

By uniting local and regional rural stakeholders, BioRural and its structures—the ERBN and the regional RBPs—are fostering the growth of a local circular economy and promoting long-term, sustainable local economic opportunities that tangentially benefit the larger local economy.

Potential project and ERBN participants are organised into two primary groups under the BioRural strategy's vision.

- **Key actors:** those who (1) Perform transfer to or influence targeted actors, and/or (2) may facilitate project implementation and widen project impacts. Examples: Farmers or foresters organisations, clusters, consultants, universities, researchers, extension services, networks, projects, technology facilitators, etc.
 - ☐ BioRural aims to involve them in project activities and to work together to widen project's impact. They are being tracked in each project's country (section #2)
- **Targeted actors:** those who are potential adopters of new small-scale biobased solutions. Examples: Farmers, foresters, rural SMEs, local industries, investors, local government.
 - ☐ BioRural aims to increase awareness and readiness for adoption of biobased innovations

In Month 12 (end of August 2023), BioRural published D2.1, which outlines the process used to carry out a coordinated effort in the involvement of important actors, in the communication with strategic initiatives and networks, and in the consolidation of a possible management structure for the ERBN. To achieve this, partners previously described a national strategy in each BioRural country by: determining which key actors should be contacted, categorising them based on their project relevance and willingness to work together, and determining the optimal time to do so (either early in the project or later). The present document builds on D2.1 (M12) and D2.2 (update at M24) and focuses to update the current status at M36.

1.2 Structure of the document

The current document follows D2.2's structure and is organised in accordance with the three areas of action that T2.1 and T2.2 address.

- #1: National & subnational (requiring contact with key actors) aiming at incorporating key actors to BioRural actions and set a community of interest of the ERBN
- #2: Bioeconomy networks and projects (specially allowing knowledge transfer) allowing to multiply effects and obtain support for both BioRural actions and ERBN
- #3: Internal structure to manage and maintain active the ERBN community

These areas of action are briefly summarized into Figure 2 (more details in Section 1.2 in previous deliverable D2.1 and D2.2).

Figure 2. BioRural and ERBN: the three areas of action to set the strategies

1.3 About BioRural actions through project and in last period M24-M36

The primary activities carried out during the BioRural project's last year have been:

EU Bioeconomy Challenge

The most relevant in this period in terms of cooperation, efforts and involvement of external actors.

Preparations for the **first EU Bioeconomy Challenge** began prior to M24, with internal structures and methods. The objective of the challenge was to identify and promote promising **bio-based solutions** originating from rural areas, encourage knowledge exchange, and support the scaling up of innovative practices aligned with the EU Bioeconomy Strategy.

The four regional EU Challenges—South-West, South-East, North-West, and North-East—were launched in June 2025. Selection of best ideas took place until M25 (September 2024). Regional finals in SW, SE, NW, NE were celebrated during October and November 2024. Each RBP had three finalists (totaling 12 among the 4 RBPs) who advanced to the EU Challenge final, which was held in Brussels on May 12, 2025. The regional challenges convoked over **100 participants** along Europe.

This activity contributed to the BioRural project's overarching aim of connecting grassroots innovations with wider EU-level networks and policy frameworks. It demonstrated the potential of rural regions to deliver impactful, sustainable bioeconomy solutions.

Policy recommendations and policy workshops

Policy recommendations were drafted according to evidence identified through project actions. WP3 local Workshops, WP1 surveys, were sources of information as open dialogue was established with multiple actors.

These suggestions served as the foundation for the creation of preliminary policy briefs. BioRural prepared individual policy briefs contained into D3.5 Guidelines for future Bioeconomy research and policy. Additionally, a joint policy brief was created and presented at a policy workshop that took place in Brussels on May 13–14, 2025, in conjunction with the Rural Bioeconomy Conference. This has informed the contents of D2.4. Following, a concerted effort was made by a number of Circular Bioeconomy (CB) initiatives to provide feedback to the European Bioeconomy Strategy in June 2025.

Uploading materials and widening ERBN community

Partners have been working to further enhance the value of the ERBN community and BioRural toolbox over the past few years. As a result, partners have been working to create new factsheets, financing possibilities, practice abstracts (PAs), success case studies, and summaries of innovative technologies.

In order to entice stakeholders to join, partners have also issued open communications to visualise ERBN and the toolkit and urged important actors to join the ERBN community.

Final results and exploitation

Several project outcomes have been recorded and improved by partners in order to prepare important BioRural components such as the D2.3.- European Regional Bioeconomy Network creation and stakeholders mapping (2nd update), D2.7 - Regional Bioeconomy Platform Success Stories Identification (1st update), D3.2 - Knowledge exchange material (1st update), D3.4 - Cross-border collaboration results, D4.3 - Toolkit Content and Updates (1st update), D5.3 - Results of the dissemination and exploitation including communication activities, D5.5 - Second batch of Practice Abstracts, D5.6 - Business model blueprints and tools.

D2.3 European Rural Bioeconomy Network creation and stakeholders mapping (2nd update)

2 Area of action #1: key actors and stakeholders at national level

2.1 Introduction

This section #2 updates the status of key actors engagement and ERBN community status previously reported in Deliverable report D2.1 (August 2023, M12) and D2.2 (August 2024, M24).

The materials and methods are described in detail in D2.1, section 2.1. However, it is accurate to reiterate the definition of tags for the benefit of clarity, as they are essential to a clear understanding of the graphs and tables that follow in section 2.2. Table 1 includes the tags describing key actor's main profile, whereas Table 2 describes the bioeconomy themes pertinent to a key actor or the areas in which the key actor develops its professional activity.

Table 1. Tags utilized in BioRural to classify the key actor profile

#TAG	TAGS for Stakeholder <u>profiles</u>
#PP	Primary producers (individual farmers, foresters, fishers)
#PP.Org	Primary producers organisations
#Comp	Company, SME, self-employed (not being primary producer)
#Comp.Org	Sectorial, SMEs, company organisations
#Cons	Consultant (private, in any field. Profile can be specified with the Bioeconomy theme #TAG)
#Cons.Org	Consultants organisations
#RU	Rural actor (relevant for project as a single stakeholder: city council, county board, local leader, etc.)
#RU.Org	Rural organisations (rural development, Local Action Groups, rural territories, etc.)
#Gov	Government department, service, etc.
#R/Ed	Research and/or education (universities, research centres, tech. centres, schools, vocational schools, etc.)
#Net	Network (type can be specified with Bioeconomy #TAGs and in comments)
#Proj	Project (type can be specified with Bioeconomy theme #TAGs and in comments)
#Oth	Any other not falling in previous (civil organisations, etc.)

Table 2. Tags utilized in BioRural to classify the key actors themes of bioeconomy

#TAG	TAGs for bioeconomy <u>theme</u>
#Agr/F	Agri/Food: Related to agriculture and food (inland resources)
#For	Forest: Related to forest (inland resources)
#Aq	Aquatic: Related to fisheries and aquaculture (aquatic resources)
#BE	Bioenergy: Transforming bio-resource into energy, or providing services or good to this value chain
#BM	Biomaterials: Transforming bio-resource into intermediate or final bio-based products and goods, or providing services or good to this value chain
#Hor	Horizontal: Any actor like rural organisations, large R&D centres, which are not theme-specific and cover all 5 bioeconomy classes
#Nspec	Non-specific. As could be an innovation booster. May cover some areas, not being specific of any of them.

2.2 SW RBP Results – Status at M36

2.2.1 SW RBP Overview

The BioRural South-West Rural Bioeconomy Platform (SW RBP) is built by 3 countries: Spain, Italy and Portugal. Among them, Spain is head of the RBP, adopting the role of RBP leader. Each country developed a specific strategy for key actors’ engagement at M12, which can be consulted as an Annex to D2.1. An update of the strategy and status was reported in M24 through D2.2.

The combined SW RBP numbers for month M36 are shown in this summary. Individual insights for each country are included at the end of this sub-section. Country report updates are included into the Appendix to the present deliverable.

SW RBP: Key actors’ profile in the strategy

In order to determine which important players would be pertinent to bolstering BioRural initiatives in their own countries, BioRural partners conducted individual country-by-country analysis by M12 and to encourage participation, cooperation, and integration into the European Rural Bioeconomy Network (ERBN) community.

Following the analysis, M12 developed a list of important players for each BioRural country, including the organization's profile, important bioeconomy subjects, and project importance. According to the intermediate report D2.2 in M24, partners discovered more important players as the project progressed after M12 that had not been initially taken into account.

At M36, the profiles of the key actors identified is presented next in Figure 3. Additionally, Table 3 indicates the numeric and percent distribution of topics relevant for those key actors.

Figure 3. SW RBP: summary of identified key actors profiles by M36

In regard M12, at M36 a total of new additional **41 key actors have been added** to the identified key actors considered as potentially relevant to support BioRural actions and widen project impacts. As observed in Figure 3 **at M36 the total key actors identified add 249 organisations in the 3 RBP countries.**

As observed the predominant profile is research and education organisations (70) as well as companies, clusters and sectorial organisations (47). Government bodies (35) and primary producers (31) are also a noticeable part of the share. Rural organisations and consultants, who may take a role of facilitators for dissemination (complementing primary producers organisations), add 14 and 13 organisations respectively. A total of 20

Networks and 11 Projects have been identified as relevant for the project in the SW RBP. In respect the distribution of key actors identified at M12, the share is similar, with an increase of R&D and companies and companies organisations.

In respect the bioeconomy topics covered by these key actors, they are presented in Table 3. The distribution is quite similar as that reported at M12. The new actors added to the list of key actors targeted have been distributed evenly among topics, resulting in a similar percentual distribution, with changes of just 1 percentile. The prevailing classes are the inland resources, Agri-Food (#Agr/F) and Forest (#For) with percentages of 19 and 17%. Rest of bioeconomy themes like Aquatic resources (#Aq), Bioenergy (#BE) and Biomaterials (#BM) all get good shares ranging 12% to 14%. The distribution is therefore well balanced, specially taking into account the fact that horizontal (#Hor) and non specific (#Nspec) key actors add in total 77 organisations (24%). In this later #Hor group multiple research centres and rural organisations are included, therefore being connected to all or most of 5 bioeconomy areas.

Table 3. SW RBP: Bioeconomy themes coverage at M36 of project

Period: M1-M36 Bioeconomy theme	TOTAL		Nr. By profile								
	Nr	%	#PP or #PPOrg	#Comp or #Comp.Org	#Cons or #Cons.Org	#RU or #RU.Org	#Gov	#R/Ed	#Net	#Proj	#Oth
[Agr/F] Agri/F	62	19%	15	13	5	0	9	14	4	2	0
[For] Forest	56	17%	11	3	4	0	11	18	4	3	2
[Aq] Aquatic	39	12%	10	8	1	0	8	6	5	1	0
[BE] Bioenergy	46	14%	0	15	3	1	6	10	1	3	7
[BM] Biomaterials	42	13%	0	14	2	0	3	14	3	3	3
[Hor] Horizontal	62	19%	0	4	3	12	12	21	5	4	1
[Nspec] Non specific	15	5%	0	3	5	0	2	5	0	0	0
TOTAL (Nr)	322	100%	36	60	23	13	51	88	22	16	13
TOTAL (%)	100%	100%	11%	19%	7%	4%	16%	27%	7%	5%	4%

IMPORTANT NOTE: this table summarises the tags, to identify if all bioeconomy themes are being covered in the strategy to approach key actors. Since several key actors have been tagged with more than one tag, the total accounting of tags (322) is larger than the total number of key actors (249).

RBP SW: Status at M36 (August 2025)

Conducting meetings and communications was the first step in activating the relevant players. During this first stage, **by end of August 2023** (Month 12 of project) the **SW RBP partners considered more relevant initially 119 out of the 208 key actors identified**. By **M24 a total of 182 have been contacted or approached**, and the list of total key actors **considered relevant grew from 209 to 233**, and **by M36 grew to 249**.

At M36, as observed in Table 4, a total of **204 actors have been object of communication** leading to a total of **163 meetings**. These communications have triggered **the effect of 97 key actors having already either participated** (as audience by attending events, meetings, workshops) **or collaborated** (by supporting project, as by providing data, vision, connecting with other actors, or co-organising workshops or events), **or both of them, adding 74 participations and 137 collaborations**.

From the **249 key actors identified, 45 remained finally inactive**, as being prioritised by partners the engagement towards other key actors.

Table 4. SW RBP: Actions performed to approach key actors by M36

ACTIONS	Nr. KEY ACTORS			TOTAL NR of actions			Interpretation (figures at M36)
	M12	M24	M36	M12	M24	M36	
Communi-cations	100	182	204	100	182	204	Informative or "ice-breaking" interactions are used to raise awareness of BioRural's existence and objectives. They are not engagement actions, though. <i>A total of 204 key actors have been contacted via phone, calls or emails.</i>
Meetings	44	78	108	55	107	163	<u>Meetings are direct actions of engagement</u> (visits, in-person talk, phone or e-meetings) where partners explain value and try to activate interest, so that key actors will take part into BioRural actions. <i>A total of 108 key actors were met, few of them with more than one meeting, totalling 163 meetings.</i>
Participa-tions	12	46	56	13	60	74	<u>Participation refers to</u> take part in a project action, meaning key actors are active, though not necessarily engaged and supporting project. Examples: participate as audience in a seminar or workshop, respond a survey, etc. <i>A total of 56 key actors have participated in BioRural actions by M36. Several of them participated in more than one action (adding a total of 74 participations). Among these 56 key actors, 37 of them have also collaborated, thus considered status of "engaged", whereas the rest 19 simply participated, thus considered their status as "active" (see Figure 4).</i>
Collabora-tions	24	54	78	30	88	137	<u>Collaboration means</u> that engagement has been successful to trigger key actors to support BioRural actions: by collaborating in organising a workshop, by engaging other stakeholders to participate in project surveys, etc. <i>A total of 78 key actors have collaborated with BioRural. Several of them collaborated not just once, and therefore 137 collaborations took place.</i>

As observed in Table 4 (period M12 to M36) the increase of meetings proceeded as new 30 key actors were met, and new collaborations occurred. The growth is similar to the rate between M12 and M24. In regard the participations, the rate between M24-36 (10 new actors participating, totalling new 14 participations) decreased in respect the previous period M12-M24 (new 34 key actors participated, adding 47 participations). This fact reflects the path of the project. Whereas during M12-M24 multiple workshops were organised, and the SW EU Challenge was launched, in the last period M24-M36 the actions concentrated in the celebration of SW EU-Challenge, and the incorporation of more materials to the BioRural toolkit. As such, Nr of participations grew, but not in such large rate as it did in the previous period.

In respect collaborations they have continued growing in a similar rate: M12-M24 new 30 actors collaborated, whereas M24-M36 new additional 34 actors did it. The total collaborations, from all actors collaborating in period M24-M36 rose from 88 in M24 to 137 in M36, adding a total of new 49 collaborations. This rate is slightly lower than previous period (plus 58). Still, it shows that even having M24-M36 less activity of open events than in the previous periods, the collaborations kept growing, thus showing a good consolidation of BioRural engagement with multiple key actors. This is a sound indicator of the fact that project does not evolve alone in SW RBP, but in connection with key actors who can multiply project effects.

These figures are also displayed visually and disaggregated in Figure 4 by key actor profile.

Figure 4. SW RBP: status of activation of key actors at M36 LEFT: Identified VS Approached. RIGHT: distribution of achievements by type of key actor

As observed in Figure 4 (left) during the project the SW RBP partners faced to potentially contact and/or engage the whole set of identified key actors (totalling 249). Partners have finally approached 205 of them by M36: 107 becoming aware, 19 active (participated but not collaborated) and 78 engaged (collaborated but may also have participated). A number of key actors who were initially believed to be pertinent for the project have resulted to be not interested, reactive or simple not relevant for it. As result, BioRural partners have adjusted the strategy and focused efforts on other key actors, either previously or recently identified.

Several important actors have been drawn to join and/or work together as partners in their countries have executed pertinent project initiatives. Among the 108 key actors object of contact for awareness, a total of 60 have already participated and/or collaborated, meaning:

- 19 key actors have participated, but not collaborated; thus, they reach the status of “active”
- 78 actors have collaborated, meaning they reached the status of “engaged” with BioRural. It must be noted that several of these actors, 37 in total have done both, participate and collaborate. Notwithstanding in terms of degree of engagement they are classified with the superior stage, “engaged”.

RBP SW key actors’ analysis and next steps

By cross-checking in a graph the degree of activation (X-Axis) and the relevance (Y-Axis) that the key actors may have for project implementation and growth of ERBN in their countries, each country partner has conducted an analysis of the key actors in order to further determine the status of advancement in their engagement. The representation of these variables has been arranged by means of a “quadrant diagram” (methodology and explanation provided in D2.1, section 2.2.2).

Figure 5 shows by RBP country the evolution of the key actors from M12 (August 2023) until M36 (August 2025).

KEY ACTORS ENGAGEMENT STATUS AND EVOLUTION ALONG PROJECT LIFETIME

Status at M12

Status at M24

Status at M36

SPAIN

ITALY

PORTUGAL

Figure 5. SW RBP: Quadrant diagram and evolution for the period M12 – M36

As observed in all countries, the effect of partners by interacting with key actors has caused them, especially those considered relevant, to move to the right-side quadrants of the graph, in the transition from M12 till M36. Specific details and highlights by each SW RBP country is presented below in section 2.2.2 and Appendix to D2.3.

RBP SW: ERBN and adhesion of key actors and another stakeholders

As stated in the BioRural project proposal by the KPI Nr #1.3 (eoKPI 1.3), each BioRural RBP had to achieve 100 Stakeholders to be registered on BioRural Toolkit (for a total of 400 when the four BioRural RBPs by M36 are added). These stakeholders may include either key actors (relevant at national level because of their influence, position or ability as multipliers), or any other actor being targeted by the project (final potential adopters, technology facilitators, etc.).

This enrolment and commitment have taken place by two paths:

- persons registering into the toolkit (key actors or stakeholders organisations)

- alternatively, for key actors, not willing to register in the IT platform, by reception of a formal statement (email or letter) of their intend to collaborate and interact with ERBN community, or become part of its structure.

The achievements by M36 are summarised into Figure 6. As observed on the left side at M36 the **SW RBP countries contribute to the ERBN community with a total of 157 members**. All of them subscribed to the ERBN by registering through the BioRural toolkit. This total of 157 members of the ERBN complies with the minimum target set of 100 to be reached by M36 in the SW RBP. This shows an outstanding contribution from the SW to the growth of the ERBN community.

Among these 157 members, 66 are persons of key actors organisations (having an influencing or multiplying role in the country) **and 95 are persons considered part of BioRural target audience** (farmers, technicians, technology facilitators, consultants, cooperatives, etc.). Whereas key actors have been object of direct approach and interaction, the rest of stakeholders subscribing have not been object of direct engagement and communication. The fact that they have subscribed is an indicator of the project reach and ability to create value for final target audience. These stakeholders became aware of BioRural through communication (social media, posts, news, fairs, etc.) or after participating in any of the multiple BioRural actions (workshops, tutorials, events, etc.). This aggregation of key actors and stakeholders in connection through a platform, interested in innovation, bioeconomy and application of new small-scale solutions, is a principal value which in return is expected to attract more organisations to enrol into the ERBN beyond project lifespan.

As observed below, Figure 6 (right) depicts the distribution of the 157 members from SW RBP at M36. The principal groups are Companies and companies organisations (adding 50) and research organisations (adding 46). This shows a good interest of private sector and of R&D centres. As well the subscription of associations, clusters and NGOs reaches 35 persons, including also from the primary sector. Public administrations and government add only 12 members, which can be understood as these actors are necessary, but usually not actively involved in initiatives and networks. Additionally other 14 actors fall under the classification of other, projects and networks.

Figure 6. SW RBP: Achievements in the enrolment of key actors and stakeholders into the ERBN by M36. LEFT: achievements vs target; RIGHT: disaggregation by profile

2.2.2 Highlights by SW RBP country: Spain, Italy and Portugal

The general planning of the strategies for Spain, Italy and Portugal is available as an Annex to D2.1. The update at M24 as appendix to D2.2, and the details at M36 as an appendix to this deliverable D2.3. Highlights at M36 distilled from D2.3 appendix are presented next.

SPAIN

At M36 the total key actors identified adds a total of 96. A total of 27 key actors has been added to the list from the initial list identified at M12. These are organisations that were not previously thought of but have since been shown to be relevant. Through the cooperation of other players who pointed them out, by carrying out acts and meeting informally, or by organising new activities for which such actors were required, these individuals have been discovered as project proceeds. Examples are Task T3.2 (to organise the regional workshops), T3.3 to organise the SW EU Challenge, or as synergies with other actors of projects took place. A total of 77 key actors has been approached until M36, leading to 41 having already participated in at least one project action, and 33 of them having already collaborated, supporting BioRural implementation (e.g. as co-organiser of T3.2 workshops, or by bridging towards other organisations).

The good evolution of the involvement of key actors into project actions is well observed into Figure 5 with the quadrant graphs. It is there evident how the rightmost quadrants (meaning actors already engaged and collaborating) is more densely populated than the graph at M12.

In respect ERBN subscription, target by 36 was initially set to 34 organisations. This figure was already surpassed at M12, with a total of 35 members adhered to ERBN community. At the current status, a total community of 51 users can be considered as part of ERBN. Several of these organisations have collaborated with AVEBIOM, and are expected to continue being active with the ERBN in future.

ITALY

At M36 AIEL successfully mapped 53 key actors in all the sector of the bioeconomy covering all the bioeconomy sectors and a broad range of profiles. The activity of tracking key actor was mostly performed in the first and second year and in the third year were substantially stable.

The evolution of involvement of key actor is observed into the quadrant graph (Figure 5). The involvement of actors grows easier as long as the most relevant key actors were engaged. Active participation is nevertheless very difficult to achieve, key actors and generally stakeholders have grown weary of networks and platforms which in their experience have not been effective in the past in connecting stakeholders.

Regaining the trust of the stakeholder is a difficult and demanding process in which active support and cooperation (like co-organization and participation in workshops) was playing a crucial role. The quadrant graph offers an explanatory view of the evolution, between the representation taken in month 12 and the one taken in month 24, and the last in the month 36.

Regarding all the stakeholder either key actors or not the country abundantly fulfil the target for the period, achieving the subscription of 51 members in the ERBN (given a target of 25), reaching 60 ERBN members by M36.

PORTUGAL

By Month 36 (M36), Portugal's engagement strategy continued to mature, adding 4 new key actors since M24, totalling 98 identified stakeholders. This group includes a balanced mix of research and education institutions, primary producer organisations, governmental services, SMEs, and networks. The quadrant diagram (Figure 5) clearly reflects an overall eastward movement, with a larger proportion of high-relevance stakeholders now reaching higher activation levels, demonstrating successful engagement efforts.

Out of the total key actors (98), 88 have been approached up to now, there were an increase in meetings (21 to 26), participation (19 to 22), and collaborations (16 to 19). This sustained involvement indicates growing trust and relevance of BioRural in the national bioeconomy landscape.

Regarding the European Rural Bioeconomy Network (ERBN), Portugal exceeded its initial target of 33 subscriptions, reaching 47 ERBN members by M36. Most subscriptions stemmed from research institutions and

companies, aligned with the national strategy’s focus. However, engagement of local authorities and individual stakeholders remains a challenge, calling for more dynamic and inclusive network strategies.

Overall, the period M24–M36 has consolidated Portugal’s contribution to the ERBN by advancing stakeholder relevance, broadening participation, and increasing long-term engagement potential.

2.3 SE RBP Results – Status at M24

2.3.1 SE RBP Overview

The BioRural South-East Rural Bioeconomy Platform (SE RBP) is built by 4 countries: Greece, Slovenia, Romania and North Macedonia. Among them, Greece is head of the RBP, adopting the role of RBP leader. Each country developed a specific strategy for key actors’ engagement at M12, which can be consulted as an Annex to D2.1. An update of the strategy and status was reported in M24 through D2.2.

In the present summary the aggregated figures of SE RBP in M36 are presented. Individual insights for each country are included at the end of this sub-section. Country report update is included into the Appendix to the present deliverable.

SE RBP: Key actors’ profile in the strategy

In order to determine which important players would be pertinent to bolstering BioRural initiatives in their own countries, BioRural partners conducted individual country-by-country analysis by M12 and to encourage participation, cooperation, and integration into the European Rural Bioeconomy Network (ERBN) community.

Following the analysis, M12 developed a list of important players for each BioRural nation, including the organization’s profile, important bioeconomy subjects, and project importance. According to the intermediate report D2.2 in M24, partners discovered more important players as the project progressed after M12 that had not been initially taken into account.

At M36, the profiles of the key actors identified is presented next in Figure 7. Additionally, Table 5 indicates the numeric and percent distribution of topics relevant for those key actors.

Figure 7. SE RBP: summary of identified key actors’ profiles by M36

In regard M12, at M36 a total of new additional 67 key actors have been added to the identified key actors considered as potentially relevant to support BioRural actions and widen project impacts. As observed in Figure 7, **at M36 the total key actors identified add 347 organisations in the 4 RBP countries.**

Most identified actors are research and education institutions (61), along with companies, clusters, and sectoral organizations (102). Primary producers and government bodies also represent a significant portion, with 31 organizations each. Additionally, rural organizations (15) and consultants (19)—who often serve as facilitators in dissemination efforts—complement the presence of primary producer organizations. In total, 12 networks and 44 projects have been recognized as relevant to the project within the SE RBP. By month 12 (M12), the distribution of key actors remained largely consistent, with a noted increase in the number of companies and related organizations.

Regarding the bioeconomy topics addressed by the key actors, these are summarized in Table 5. As outlined in the first report (M12), the bioeconomy themes covered by the identified actors. The most prominent thematic category is “Agriculture,” followed closely by “Horizontal” themes. The latter is particularly prevalent due to the broad focus of research centres and universities, which often span multiple bioeconomy areas. Actors such as rural organizations, consultants, and networks are more likely to benefit from the project’s diverse outputs, as they are not limited to a specific thematic area. Conversely, forest and aquatic bioeconomy topics are notably underrepresented. This reflects the resource base of the bioeconomy in Slovenia, Romania, and North Macedonia, where agriculture and forestry dominate due to their largely inland geographies and economic structures. Nonetheless, all bioeconomy topics, including the underrepresented ones, should continue to be explored and further developed beyond M12.

Table 5. SE RBP: Bioeconomy themes coverage at M36 of project

Period: M1-M36 Bioeconomy theme	TOTAL		Nr. By profile								
	Nr	%	#PP or #PPOrg	#Comp or #Comp.Org	#Cons or #Cons.Org	#RU or #RU.Org	#Gov	#R/Ed	#Net	#Proj	#Oth
[Agr/F] Agri/F	114	28%	25	32	3	8	5	21	3	14	3
[For] Forest	34	8%	3	8	2	4	3	8	0	4	2
[Aq] Aquatic	47	12%	11	11	1	2	4	13	0	3	2
[BE] Bioenergy	44	11%	0	27	1	2	1	5	2	6	0
[BM] Biomaterials	51	13%	0	32	0	0	0	12	1	4	2
[Hor] Horizontal	103	25%	1	13	11	9	16	13	6	16	12
[Nspec] Non specific	15	4%	0	1	0	0	1	6	0	1	6
TOTAL (Nr)	408	100%	40	124	18	25	36	78	12	48	27
TOTAL (%)	100%	100%	10%	30%	4%	6%	9%	19%	3%	12%	7%

IMPORTANT NOTE: this table summarises the tags, to identify if all bioeconomy themes are being covered in the strategy to approach key actors. Since several key actors have been tagged with more than one tag, the total accounting of tags (408) is larger than the total number of key actors (347).

RBP SE: Status at M36 (August 2025)

Conducting meetings and communications was the first step in activating the relevant players. During this first stage, **by end of August 2023 (Month 12 of project) the SE RBP partners considered more relevant initially 146 out of the 280 key actors identified.** By M24 a total of 238 have been contacted or approached, and the list of total key actors considered relevant grew from 280 to 329.

At M36, as observed in Table 6, a total of **281 actors has been object of communication** leading to a total of **238 meetings**. These communications have triggered **the effect of 154 key actors having already either participated** (as audience by attending events, meetings, workshops) **or collaborated** (by supporting project, as by providing data, vision, connecting with other actors, or co-organising workshops or events), **or both of them, adding 200 participations and 157 collaborations.**

From the **347 key actors identified, 82 remained finally inactive**, as being prioritised by partners the engagement towards other key actors.

Table 6. SE RBP: Actions performed to approach key actors by M36

ACTIONS	Nr. KEY ACTORS			TOTAL NR of actions			Interpretation (figures at M36)
	M12	M24	M36	M12	M24	M36	
Communi-cations	132	238	281	132	238	281	Informative or "ice-breaking" interactions are used to raise awareness of BioRural's existence and objectives. They are not engagement actions, though. <i>A total of 281 key actors have been contacted via phone, calls or emails.</i>
Meetings	95	191	238	109	254	356	<u>Meetings are direct actions of engagement</u> (visits, in-person talk, phone or e-meetings) where partners explain value and try to activate interest, so that key actors will take part into BioRural actions. <i>A total of 238 key actors were met, few of them with more than one meeting, totalling 356 meetings.</i>
Participa-tions	55	103	134	58	136	200	<u>Participation refers to</u> take part in a project action, meaning key actors are active, though not necessarily engaged and supporting project. Examples: participate as audience in a seminar or workshop, respond a survey, etc. <i>A total of 134 key actors have participated in BioRural actions by M36. Several of them participated in more than one action (adding a total of 200 participations). Among these 134 key actors, 87 of them have also collaborated, thus considered status of "engaged", whereas the rest 47 simply participated, thus considered their status as "active" (see Figure 8).</i>
Collabora-tions	24	81	107	25	105	157	<u>Collaboration means</u> that engagement has been successful to trigger key actors to support BioRural actions: by collaborating in organising a workshop, by engaging other stakeholders to participate in project surveys, etc. <i>A total of 107 key actors have collaborated with BioRural. Several of them collaborated not just once, and therefore 157 collaborations took place.</i>

As observed in Table 6 (period M12 to M36) a total of 238 actors were contacted, resulting in 356 meetings. These interactions have led to the involvement of 134 key actors in project activities, primarily surveys and workshops at this stage. Of these, 107 have actively collaborated by contributing data, insights, supporting dissemination, or helping reach additional target audiences, particularly through survey efforts. Out of the 347 key actors identified so far, 82 remain inactive or unaware of the project, with no evidence of engagement or interest to date. Figure 8 provides a visual and disaggregated representation of these figures by key actor profile.

These figures are also displayed visually and disaggregated in Figure 8 by key actor profile.

Figure 8. SE RBP: status of activation of key actors at M36. LEFT: Identified VS Approached. RIGHT: distribution of achievements by type of key actor

As observed in Figure 8 (left) during the project the SE RBP partners faced to potentially contact and/or engage the whole set of identified key actors (totalling 347). **Partners have finally approached 265 of them by M36:** 111 becoming just aware of project; 47 becoming active (as participating in project workshops, events); and 107 engaged (having already collaborated with project). A number of key actors who were initially believed to be pertinent for the project have resulted to be not interested, reactive or simple not relevant for it. As result, BioRural partners have adjusted the strategy and focused efforts on other key actors, either previously or recently identified.

Several important actors have been drawn to join and/or work together as partners in their countries have executed pertinent project initiatives. Among the 238 key actors object of contact for awareness, a total of 154 have already participated and/or collaborated, meaning:

- 47 key actors have participated, but not collaborated; thus they reach the status of “active”
- 107 actors have collaborated, meaning they reached the status of “engaged” with BioRural. It must be noted that several of these actors, 87 in total, have done both, participate and collaborate. Notwithstanding in terms of degree of engagement they are classified with the superior stage, “engaged”.

RBP SE key actors’ analysis and next steps

By cross-checking in a graph the degree of activation (X-Axis) and the relevance (Y-Axis) that the key actors may have for project implementation and growth of ERBN in their countries, each country partner has conducted an analysis of the key actors in order to further determine the status of advancement in their engagement. The representation of these variables has been arranged by means of a “quadrant diagram” (methodology and explanation provided in D2.1, section 2.2.2).

Figure 9 shows by RBP country the evolution of the key actors from M12 (August 2023) until M36 (August 2025).

KEY ACTORS ENGAGEMENT STATUS AND EVOLUTION ALONG PROJECT LIFETIME

Status at M12

Status at M24

Status at M36

GREECE

SLOVENIA

ROMANIA

NORTH MACEDONIA

Figure 9. SE RBP: Quadrant diagram and evolution for the period M12 – M36

As observed in all countries, the effect of partners by interacting with key actors has caused them, especially those considered relevant, to move to the right-side quadrants of the graph, in the transition from M12 till M36. Specific details and highlights by each SW RBP country is presented below in section 2.3.2 and Appendix to D2.3.

RBP SE: ERBN and adhesion of key actors and another stakeholders

As stated in the BioRural project proposal by the expected outcome KPI Nr #1.3 (eoKPI 1.3), each BioRural RBP had to achieve 100 Stakeholders to be registered on BioRural Toolkit (for a total of 400 when the four BioRural RBPs by M36 are added). These stakeholders may include either key actors (relevant at national level because of their influence, position or ability as multipliers), or any other actor being targeted by the project (final potential adopters, technology facilitators, etc.).

This enrolment and commitment have taken place by two paths:

- persons registering into the toolkit (key actors or stakeholders organisations)
- alternatively, for key actors, not willing to register in the IT platform, by reception of a formal statement (email or letter) of their intend to collaborate and interact with ERBN community or become part of its structure.

The achievements by M36 are summarised into Figure 10. **As observed on the left side at M36 the SE RBP countries contribute to the ERBN community with a total of 189 members.** A total of 165 have subscribed to the ERBN by registering through the BioRural toolkit, whereas 24 have done it by formally agreeing to support BioRural and participate / sustain the ERBN. This total of 189 members of the ERBN complies with the minimum target set of 100 to be reached by M36. This shows an outstanding contribution from the SE RBP to the growth of the ERBN community.

Among these 189 members, 125 are persons of key actors' organisations (having an influencing or multiplying role in the country) **and 64 are persons considered part of BioRural target audience** farmers, technicians, technology facilitators, consultants, cooperatives, etc.). Whereas key actors have been object of direct approach and interaction, the rest of stakeholders subscribing have not been object of direct communication. The fact that they have subscribed is an indicator of the project reach and ability to create value for final target audience. These stakeholders became aware of BioRural through communication (social media, posts, news, fairs, etc.) or after participating in any of the multiple BioRural actions (workshops, tutorials, events, etc.). This aggregation of key actors and stakeholders in connection through a platform, interested in innovation, bioeconomy and application of new small-scale solutions, is a principal value which in return is expected to attract more organisations to enrol into the ERBN beyond project lifespan.

As observed below, Figure 10 (right) depicts the distribution of the 189 members from SE RBP at M36. More specifically, 61 members are from Research and education institutes, 65 members are private companies or self-employed, 37 members are associations, clusters and NGO'S, 9 members are Government and public administration and finally 17 members are consisted of other types of organizations, companies or institutions, mainly networks and projects.

Figure 10. SE RBP: Achievements in the enrolment of key actors and stakeholders into the ERBN by M36. LEFT: achievements vs target; RIGHT: disaggregation by profile

2.3.2 Highlights by SE RBP country: Greece, Slovenia, Romania and North Macedonia

The general planning of the strategies for Greece, Slovenia, Romania and North Macedonia is available as an Annex to D2.1. The update at M24 as appendix to D2.2, and the details at M36 as an appendix to this deliverable D2.3. Highlights at M36 distilled from D2.3 appendix are presented next.

GREECE

Regarding Month36 (M36), a total of 60 key stakeholder organizations has been identified as strategically relevant for engagement throughout the project. This number has steadily increased since Month 12 (M12), reflecting the evolving scope and refinement of the project’s stakeholder mapping and outreach strategy. By M36, 47 of these key actors had been actively approached, resulting in 20 participating in at least one project activity and 31 establishing collaborative relationships that directly support the implementation of BioRural project. Furthermore, all companies that participated in the Greek Bioeconomy Challenge expressed a clear interest in joining the European Rural Bioeconomy Network (ERBN), demonstrating the growing momentum and stakeholder commitment around the project’s objectives.

SLOVENIA

By Month 36 (M36), a total of 127 key actors were systematically mapped in Slovenia, representing all major sectors of the bioeconomy and encompassing a diverse range of stakeholder profiles. These actors were identified through multiple BioRural project tasks related to bioeconomy advancement and rural development. Between M24 and M36, 15 additional stakeholders either expressed formal interest or actively engaged in project activities—particularly within the framework of the European Bioeconomy Challenge (Task 3.3), the collection of new success stories (Task 2.4), and the preparation of the second batch of Practice Abstracts (Deliverable 5.5). The stakeholder profile distribution reveals a predominance of companies and their representative organizations, followed by research and education institutions, and other collaborative projects. Significant engagement was also noted by primary producers, rural actors, government bodies, and consultancy services. By M36, 90 key actors had been contacted, resulting in 109 bilateral or group meetings. Of these, 72 stakeholders participated in at least one project-related activity, with 53 of them providing direct contributions and supporting the implementation of specific BioRural tasks.

ROMANIA

At project month 36 (M36), the total number of key actors identified and engaged reached 103. Between M24 and M36, 14 new stakeholders were added to support the implementation of Circular Bioeconomy Challenge Workshops under Task 3.3, as well as other dissemination activities, the identification of success stories, and the

development of practice abstracts. These newly engaged stakeholders primarily include representatives from EU-funded bioeconomy projects, research and educational institutions, NGOs, clusters, and farmer organizations. The stakeholder composition is mainly concentrated in three categories: private companies and their associations, research and academic institutions, and primary producer organizations. Of the 103 actors approached, 82 have participated in at least one project activity, and 35 have actively contributed to BioRural implementation—either as co-organizers of dissemination events or by facilitating connections with additional relevant networks and organizations.

NORTH MACEDONIA

By Month 36 (M36), a total of 57 key actors had been identified, marking a steady increase in engagement since Month 24 (M24). Two additional actors were identified during the M24–M36 period, primarily through targeted outreach and the regional workshop participation process. The profile distribution of these actors reflects a strong representation from companies and their associations, government institutions, R&D organizations, and primary producer groups. Notably, the participation of companies and primary producers increased between M24 and M36, indicating growing stakeholder's interest and alignment with project objectives. Of the 57 key actors approached by M36, 15 have actively engaged in at least one project activity, with 9 having contributed directly to project implementation—either as workshop speakers, judges, featured success stories, or by facilitating connections with additional relevant stakeholders.

2.4 NW RBP Results – Status at M24

2.4.1 RBP NW Overview

The BioRural North-West Rural Bioeconomy Platform (NW RBP) is built by 4 countries: The Netherlands, Denmark, Germany and France. Among them, The Netherlands is head of the RBP, adopting the role of RBP leader. Each country developed a specific strategy for key actors' engagement at M12, which can be consulted as an Annex to D2.1. An update of the strategy and status was reported in M24 through D2.2.

In the present summary (M36) the aggregated figures of NW RBP are presented. Individual insights for each country are included at the end of this sub-section. Country report update is included into the Appendix to the present deliverable.

RBP are presented, with specific insights to individual country highlights at the end of this sub-section.

NW RBP: Key actors' profile in the strategy

In order to determine which important players would be pertinent to bolstering BioRural initiatives in their own countries, BioRural partners conducted individual country-by-country analysis by M12 and to encourage participation, cooperation, and integration into the European Rural Bioeconomy Network (ERBN) community.

Following the analysis, M12 developed a list of important players for each BioRural nation, including the organization's profile, important bioeconomy subjects, and project importance. According to the intermediate report D2.2 in M24, partners discovered more important players as the project progressed after M12 that had not been initially taken into account.

At M36, the profiles of the key actors identified is presented next in Figure 11. Additionally, Table 7 indicates the numeric and percent distribution.

Figure 11. NW RBP: summary of identified key actors' profiles by M36

In regard M12, at M36 a total of new additional **22 key actors have been added** to the identified key actors considered as potentially relevant to support BioRural actions and widen project impacts. As observed in Figure 11, at M36 the total key actors identified add **340 organisations in the 4 RBP countries**.

The structure of the NW RBP key actor profile is similar to that of M12 and 24. Where the predominant profiles are mainly those of companies and company organization, which still have increased in number in the list of targeted key actors. Other actors added are under Research and education and Rural Organisations. This is a likely positive side effect of the organisation of actions attracting researchers and companies, as the T3.3 EU Challenge.

As observed in Table 7 in respect of the distribution of bioeconomy themes by key actor profile, the themes are well distributed., though agri-food and biomaterials are prevailing. The distribution is quite similar as in M24. To be remarked the main horizontal profile on government, rural networks and research and education organisations. As such, being usually part of the AKIS system in each country, specially in knowledge transfer, they can be very strategic to convey the BioRural results after project ends.

Table 7. NW RBP: Bioeconomy themes coverage at M36 of project

Period: M1-M36 Bioeconomy theme	TOTAL		Nr. By profile								
	Nr	%	#PP or #PPOrg	#Comp or #Comp.Org	#Cons or #Cons.Org	#RU or #RU.Org	#Gov	#R/Ed	#Net	#Proj	#Oth
[Agr/F] Agri/F	77	23%	17	27	1	4	4	9	15	0	0
[For] Forest	22	6%	3	5	2	2	0	1	9	0	0
[Aq] Aquatic	40	12%	1	20	2	0	0	13	1	2	1
[BE] Bioenergy	26	8%	1	14	6	1	1	1	1	1	0
[BM] Biomaterials	69	20%	1	44	8	1	0	6	8	1	0
[Hor] Horizontal	59	17%	1	6	2	9	15	13	6	7	0
[Nspec] Non specific	48	14%	1	5	6	3	3	17	9	1	3
TOTAL (Nr)	341	100%	25	121	27	20	23	60	49	12	4
TOTAL (%)	100%	100%	7%	35%	8%	6%	7%	18%	14%	4%	1%

IMPORTANT NOTE: this table summarises the tags, to identify if all bioeconomy themes are being covered in the strategy to approach key actors. Since one of the key actors has been tagged with more than one tag, the total accounting of tags (341) is larger than the total number of key actors (340).

RBP NW: Status at M36 (August 2025)

Conducting meetings and communications was the first step in activating the relevant players. During this first stage, **by end of August 2023** (Month 12 of project) the **NW RBP partners considered more relevant initially 130 out of the 246 key actors identified**. By **M24 a total of 238 have been contacted or approached**, and the list of total key actors **considered relevant grew from 246 to 340**.

At M36, as observed in Table 8, a total of **188 actors has been object of communication** leading to a total of **217 meetings**. These communications have triggered **the effect of 135 key actors having already either participated** (as audience by attending events, meetings, workshops) **or collaborated** (by supporting project, as by providing data, vision, connecting with other actors, or co-organising workshops or events), **or both of them, adding 148 participations and 49 collaborations**.

From the **318 key actors identified, 96 remained finally inactive**, as being prioritised by partners the engagement towards other key actors.

Table 8. NW RBP: Actions performed to approach key actors by M36

ACTIONS	Nr. KEY ACTORS			TOTAL NR of actions			Interpretation (figures at M36)
	M12	M24	M36	M12	M24	M36	
Communi-cations	88	161	188	88	161	188	Informative or "ice-breaking" interactions are used to raise awareness of BioRural's existence and objectives. They are not engagement actions, though. <i>A total of 188 key actors have been contacted via phone, calls or emails.</i>
Meetings	69	160	173	76	181	217	<u>Meetings are direct actions of engagement</u> (visits, in-person talk, phone or e-meetings) where partners explain value and try to activate interest, so that key actors will take part into BioRural actions. <i>A total of 173 key actors were met, few of them with more than one meeting, totalling 217 meetings.</i>
Participa-tions	54	110	129	65	123	148	<u>Participation refers to</u> take part in a project action, meaning key actors are active, though not necessarily engaged and supporting project. Examples: participate as audience in a seminar or workshop, respond a survey, etc. <i>A total of 129 key actors has participated in BioRural actions by M36. Several of them participated in more than one action (adding a total of 148 participations). Among these 129 key actors, 32 of them have also collaborated, thus considered status of "engaged", whereas the rest 97 simply participated, thus considered their status as "active" (see Figure 12).</i>
Collabora-tions	5	29	38	5	33	49	<u>Collaboration means</u> that engagement has been successful to trigger key actors to support BioRural actions: by collaborating in organising a workshop, by engaging other stakeholders to participate in project surveys, etc. <i>A total of 38 key actors have collaborated with BioRural. Several of them collaborated not just once, and therefore 49 collaborations took place.</i>

As observed in Table 8 (period M12 to M36) the increase of participations and collaborations kept the growing tendency, thus at a lower rate than during M12-M24. This is reasonable as far as during the second year of the project (M12-M24) multiple workshops, call for EU Challenge and events were organised by BioRural partners. However last year has concentrated in final events for EU Challenge, where only selected candidates participated, to keep growing the BioRural toolkit by uploading further materials, preparing new factsheets, etc. As well last year has been devoted to preparation of last outputs like policy recommendations, or bioeconomy blueprints. These actions require less involvement of key actors.

These figures are also displayed visually and disaggregated in Figure 12 by key actor profile.

Figure 12. NW RBP: status of activation of key actors at M36. LEFT: Identified VS Approached. RIGHT: distribution of achievements by type of key actor

As observed in Figure 12 (left) during the project the NW RBP partners faced to potentially contact and/or engage the whole set of identified key actors (totalling 340). Partners have finally approached 222 of them by M36: 87 becoming aware, 97 active has having participated in any of the project actions, and 38 engaged, as having collaborated. A number of key actors who were initially believed to be pertinent for the project have resulted to be not interested, reactive or simple not relevant for it. As result, BioRural partners have adjusted the strategy and focused efforts on other key actors, either previously or recently identified.

Several important actors have been drawn to join and/or work together as partners in their countries have executed pertinent project initiatives. Among the 160 key actors object of contact for awareness, a total of 135 have already participated and/or collaborated, meaning:

- 97 key actors have participated, but not collaborated; thus they reach the status of “active”
- 38 actors have collaborated, meaning they reached the status of “engaged” with BioRural. It must be noted that several of these actors, 32 in total, have done both, participate and collaborate. Notwithstanding in terms of degree of engagement they are classified with the superior stage, “engaged”.

RBP NW key actors’ analysis and next steps

By cross-checking in a graph the degree of activation (X-Axis) and the relevance (Y-Axis) that the key actors may have for project implementation and growth of ERBN in their countries, each country partner has conducted an analysis of the key actors in order to further determine the status of advancement in their engagement. The representation of these variables has been arranged by means of a “quadrant diagram” (methodology and explanation provided in D2.1, section 2.2.2).

Figure 13 shows by RBP country the evolution of the key actors from M12 (August 2023) until M36 (August 2025).

KEY ACTORS ENGAGEMENT STATUS AND EVOLUTION ALONG PROJECT LIFETIME

Status at M12

Status at M24

Status at M36

The NETHERLANDS

DENMARK

GERMANY

FRANCE

Figure 13. NW RBP: Quadrant diagram and evolution for the period M12 – M36

As observed in all countries, the effect of partners by interacting with key actors has caused them, especially those considered relevant, to move to the right-side quadrants of the graph, in the transition from M12 till M36. Specific details and highlights by each SW RBP country is presented below in section 2.4.2 and Appendix to D2.3.

RBP NW: ERBN and adhesion of key actors and another stakeholders

As stated in the BioRural project proposal by the expected outcome KPI Nr #1.3 (eoKPI 1.3), each BioRural RBP had to achieve 100 Stakeholders to be registered on BioRural (for a total of 400 when the four BioRural RBPs by M36 are added). These stakeholders' may include either key actors (relevant at national level because of their influence, position or ability as multipliers), or any other actor being targeted by the project (final potential adopters, technology facilitators, etc.).

This enrolment and commitment have taken place by two paths:

- persons registering into the toolkit (key actors or stakeholders organisations)
- alternatively, for key actors, not willing to register in the IT platform, by reception of a formal statement (email or letter) of their intend to collaborate and interact with ERBN community, or become part of its structure.

The achievements by M36 are summarised into Figure 14. As observed on the left side at M36 the **NW RBP countries contribute to the ERBN community with a total of 121 members**. A total of 105 have subscribed to the ERBN by registering through the BioRural toolkit, whereas 16 have done it by formally agreeing to support BioRural and participate / sustain the ERBN. This total of 121 members of the ERBN complies with the minimum target set of 100 to be reached by M36.

Among these 121 members, 90 are persons of key actors' organisations (having an influencing or multiplying role in the country) **and 31 are persons considered part of BioRural target audience** (farmers, technicians, technology facilitators, consultants, cooperatives, etc.). Whereas key actors have been object of direct approach and interaction, the rest of stakeholders subscribing have not been object of direct communication. The fact that they have subscribed is an indicator of the project reach and ability to create value for final target audience. These stakeholders became aware of BioRural through communication (social media, posts, news, fairs, etc.) or after participating in any of the multiple BioRural actions (workshops, tutorials, events, etc.). This aggregation of key actors and stakeholders in connection through a platform, interested in innovation, bioeconomy and application of new small-scale solutions, is a principal value which in return is expected to attract more organisations to enrol into the ERBN beyond project lifespan.

As observed below, Figure 14 (right) depicts the distribution of the 121 members from NW RBP at M36. In coherence with the predominant profile of the targeted actors in NW RBP, the principal profile of ERBN members are companies (58). Associations and clusters, related either with private sectors, or with rural organisations is the second group in size, with 22 members into ERBN. Research and Education (22), Government (10) and other profiles (9) complete the share.

Figure 14. NW RBP: Achievements in the enrolment of key actors and stakeholders into the ERBN. By M36 LEFT: achievements vs target; RIGHT: disaggregation by profile

2.4.2 Highlights by NW RBP country: The Netherlands, Denmark, Germany and France

The general planning of the strategies for The Netherlands, Denmark, Germany and France are available as an Annex to D2.1. The update at M24 as appendix to D2.2, and the details at M36 as an appendix to this deliverable D2.3. Highlights at M36 distilled from D2.3 appendix are presented next.

The NETHERLANDS

By the conclusion of the BioRural project at M36, a total of 66 key actors were identified, marking a significant increase of 46 from the initial list at M12. These additional actors, comprising companies, research and education organizations, and primary producers, were recognized as critical during the implementation of project actions or while planning new initiatives requiring their involvement. Of these, 58 key actors were approached across 65 meetings, with 15 actively participating in at least one project action and 7 providing direct collaboration, such as co-organizing the T3.2 national workshops or facilitating connections with other organizations.

Key engagement efforts focused on tasks like T3.2 (regional workshops), T3.3 (NW regional workshop), and fostering synergies with other projects, which expanded outreach to new stakeholders. Events such as the Biobased Gardens Open Day proved particularly effective, generating positive feedback and reinforcing interest in both the BioRural project and the broader ERBN. Despite challenges posed by the crowded biobased economy landscape in the Netherlands, tailored engagement strategies ensured meaningful participation, though some stakeholders prioritized other initiatives over biobased solutions.

Regarding ERBN subscriptions, the initial target of 25 organizations by M36 was surpassed, with 28 expressing interest. Of these, 14 have officially registered through the toolkit, while another 14 have declared their intent to join the ERBN community without finalizing subscription. Many of these organizations have collaborated with Delphy and are expected to remain active within the ERBN, contributing to its future growth and impact.

DENMARK

In Denmark a total of 90 key actors has been identified. Three success stories have been reported and uploaded on BioRural Toolkit. Collaboration in organization of and conduction of the Danish regional workshops under T3.2 was a good opportunity for launching the BioRural project. The workshops did lead to engagement of several stakeholders. 9 key actors have collaborated and supported BioRural implementation.

In Denmark, the principal profiles active and collaborating are dominated by companies or their organizations, but also research and education organizations as well as primary producers' organizations and government institutions are represented.

There has been a good evolution of the involvement of key actors into project actions. This is evident when comparing the quadrant diagrams presented in D2.3 in Figure 13. The graph for M36 shows a higher degree of activation and engagement of the key actors than in the graphs for M12 and M24.

ERBN subscription target by M36 was set to 25. This figure has been reached as a total of 29 users are registered and can be considered as part of ERBN. All 29 have subscribed through the toolkit, and additional other key actors have declared interest into ERBN and will seek information on the toolkit.

Contact and involvement of public authorities and local advisory institutions and individuals is important for the development of local biobased solutions. Good engagement has been obtained with companies, research and advisory organisations and primary producers. Also, government institutions have been involved, but here the involvement could be desired more comprehensively

GERMANY

At M12 the total key actors identified for Germany are 93. Additionally, a total of 2 key actors has been added in the period M12-M36, as they were new collaborators for the regional workshops under T3.2 and in terms of several events as communication activity for WP5. The distribution is as follows: mostly represented are networks, than companies and their organisations as well as research and education. At M24 a total of 29 key actors has been approached, leading to 18 having already participated in at least one project action, and 11 of them having already collaborated, supporting BioRural implementation (e.g. as co-organiser of T3.2 workshops, or by bridging towards other organisations).

The good evolution of the involvement of key actors into project actions has proceeded well, as presented in the quadrant graphs Table 14, since the rightmost quadrants (meaning actors already engaged and collaborating) is more densely populated than the graph at M12. M36 shows less this tendency, which is not evidenced as the work and connections have been kept with organisations previously active or engaged.

At the current status, a total community of 26 ERBN members can be considered as part of ERBN. Among them all have already subscribed through the toolkit, 16 being key actors and 10 stakeholders. Good involvement of companies has taken place specially M12-M24, showing the effect and interest of private sector in new forms of bioeconomy.

FRANCE

At the conclusion of the project (M36), several key observations can be made regarding stakeholder engagement and the development of the ERBN network in France.

Positive elements observed

Strengthened regional engagement: Interactions with regional institutions and agricultural chambers have had a significant impact, particularly with the Pays de la Loire region, which played an active role in disseminating BioRural events and promoting the platform.

Involvement of support organisations: Numerous business support organisations have continued to demonstrate strong interest in BioRural and to other circular bioeconomy initiatives, specially the new thematic network to be activated by the ERBN project. Having actively participated in workshops under Task T3.3, these organisations have expressed their willingness to engage in the upcoming working groups planned under (i) agriculture, (ii) livestock and (iii) forestry residues of the ERBN, and to either join or maintain their involvement in the ERBN network.

Structural difficulties identified

Limited perception of added value: Because the platform is openly accessible, key stakeholders do not always perceive a clear incentive to register or actively engage.

Lessons learned and future outlook

The project period has successfully introduced the platform to a wide variety of actors (private companies, academic institutions, associations, etc.). The ERBN France network is now composed of strategic individuals who are well positioned to contribute to the thematic working groups of the thERBN project. The platform currently serves as a valuable repository of resources, which will be further consolidated and enriched through thERBN. However, it is important to note that user registration was sometimes hindered by the proliferation of similar platforms at regional, national, and European levels, which can lead to stakeholder fatigue. Sustained regular engagement with platform members, along with an active mobilisation strategy, will be essential to keep this digital ecosystem dynamic. Additionally, enabling members to contact each other directly will be a valuable feature to help transform the platform into a true knowledge-sharing hub for circular bioeconomy.

2.5 NE RBP Results – Status at M24

2.5.1 RBP NE Overview

The BioRural North-East Rural Bioeconomy Platform (NE RBP) is built by 3 countries: Poland, Latvia and Lithuania. Among them, Poland is head of the RBP, adopting the role of RBP leader. Each country developed a specific strategy for key actors' engagement at M12, which can be consulted as an Annex to D2.1. An update of the strategy and status was reported in M24 through D2.2.

In the present summary M36 the aggregated figures of NE RBP are presented. Individual insights for each country are included at the end of this sub-section. Country report update is included into the Appendix to the present deliverable.

NE RBP: Key actors' profile in the strategy

In order to determine which important players would be pertinent to bolstering BioRural initiatives in their own countries, BioRural partners conducted individual country-by-country analysis by M12 and to encourage participation, cooperation, and integration into the European Rural Bioeconomy Network (ERBN) community.

Following the analysis, M12 developed a list of important players for each BioRural nation, including the organization's profile, important bioeconomy subjects, and project importance. According to the intermediate report D2.2 in M24, partners discovered more important players as the project progressed after M12 that had not been initially taken into account.

At M36, the profiles of the key actors identified is presented next in Figure 15. Additionally, Table 9 indicates the numeric and percent distribution by type of bioeconomy theme (by theme "tag").

Figure 15. NE RBP: summary of identified key actors' profiles by M36

In regard M24, at M36 a total of new additional **25 key actors have been added** to the identified key actors considered as potentially relevant to support BioRural actions and widen project impacts. As observed in Figure 15, **at M36 the total key actors identified add 276 organisations in the 3 RBP countries.**

At M36, the profiles of identified key actors in the NE RBP remain similar to those at M24. Primary producers continue to represent the predominant group, followed by companies and research organisations. Research and Education, Government bodies and rural organisations also maintain a stable presence. Compared to M24, the profiles have not changed significantly, but their numbers have increased steadily, confirming the project's capacity to expand its outreach among relevant stakeholders.

Table 9. NE RBP: Bioeconomy themes coverage at M36 of project

Period: M1-M36 Bioeconomy theme	TOTAL		Nr. By profile								
	Nr	%	#PP or #PPOrg	#Comp or #Comp.Org	#Cons or #Cons.Org	#RU or #RU.Org	#Gov	#R/Ed	#Net	#Proj	#Oth
[Agr/F] Agri/F	77	25%	22	9	3	13	8	12	5	4	1
[For] Forest	27	9%	8	4	2	3	2	4	3	1	0
[Aq] Aquatic	60	19%	30	4	11	1	2	7	1	0	4
[BE] Bioenergy	44	14%	2	11	2	8	6	8	6	0	1
[BM] Biomaterials	36	12%	1	20	0	4	2	6	2	1	0
[Hor] Horizontal	44	14%	0	3	3	9	8	10	5	2	4
[Nspec] Non specific	22	7%	2	6	7	1	3	2	0	0	1
TOTAL (Nr)	310	100%	65	57	28	39	31	49	22	8	11
TOTAL (%)	100%	100%	21%	18%	9%	13%	10%	16%	7%	3%	4%

IMPORTANT NOTE: this table summarises the tags, to identify if all bioeconomy themes are being covered in the strategy to approach key actors. Since several key actors have been tagged with more than one tag, the total accounting of tags (310) is larger than the total number of key actors (276).

RBP NE: Status at M36 (August 2025)

Conducting meetings and communications was the first step in activating the relevant players. During this first stage, **by end of August 2023** (Month 12 of project) the **NE RBP partners considered more relevant initially 86 out of the 153 key actors identified**. By **M24 a total of 238 have been contacted or approached**, and the list of total key actors **considered relevant grew from 153 to 251**.

At M36, as observed in Table 10, a total of **270 actors have been object of communication** leading to a total of **354** meetings. These communications have triggered **the effect of 121 key actors having already either participated** (as audience by attending events, meetings, workshops) **or collaborated** (by supporting project, as by providing data, vision, connecting with other actors, or co-organising workshops or events), **or both of them, adding 246 participations and 127 collaborations**.

From the **276** key actors identified, **6** remained finally inactive, as being prioritised by partners the engagement towards other key actors.

Table 10. NE RBP: Actions performed to approach key actors by M36

ACTIONS	Nr. KEY ACTORS			TOTAL NR of actions			Interpretation (figures at M36)
	M12	M24	M36	M12	M24	M36	
Communi-cations	82	243	270	82	243	270	Informative or "ice-breaking" interactions are used to raise awareness of BioRural's existence and objectives. They are not engagement actions, though. <i>A total of 270 key actors have been contacted via phone, calls or emails.</i>
Meetings	44	113	140	49	196	354	<u>Meetings are direct actions of engagement</u> (visits, in-person talk, phone or e-meetings) where partners explain value and try to activate interest, so that key actors will take part into BioRural actions. <i>A total of 140 key actors were met, several of them with more than one meeting, totalling 354 meetings.</i>
Participa-tions	45	97	122	45	151	246	<u>Participation refers to</u> take part in a project action, meaning key actors are active, though not necessarily engaged and supporting project. Examples: participate as audience in a seminar or workshop, respond a survey, etc. <i>A total of 122 key actors have participated in BioRural actions by M36. Several of them participated in more than one action (adding a total of 246 participations). Among these 122 key actors 80 of them have also collaborated, thus considered status of "engaged", whereas the rest 42 simply participated, thus considered their status as "active" (see Figure 16).</i>
Collabora-tions	27	65	82	27	77	127	<u>Collaboration means</u> that engagement has been successful to trigger key actors to support BioRural actions: by collaborating in organising a workshop, by engaging other stakeholders to participate in project surveys, etc. <i>A total of 82 key actors have collaborated with BioRural. Several of them collaborated not just once, and therefore 127 collaborations took place.</i>

As observed in the period M12 to M36, the increase of meetings, participations and collaborations was substantial. The number of meetings grew steadily from 44 at M12 to 113 at M24, and reached 140 by M36, confirming the continued interaction with key actors. Similarly, participations rose from 45 to 97, and finally 122 by M36, showing that more actors became active in the project. Most importantly, the number of collaborations increased from 27 to 65, and then to 82, which highlights a solid level of engagement. This progress is related not only to the natural development of the project but also to the success of workshops and other BioRural activities. Key actors not only support project actions and the recruitment of new members, but also contribute to knowledge exchange and help expand the project's reach and visibility.

These figures are also displayed visually and disaggregated in Figure 16 by key actor profile.

Figure 16. NE RBP: status of activation of key actors at M36. LEFT: Identified VS Approached. RIGHT: distribution of achievements by type of key actor

As observed in Figure 16 (left) during the project the NE RBP partners faced to potentially contact and/or engage the whole set of identified key actors (totalling 276). Partners have finally approached 270 of them by M36 (aware, active or engaged). A number of key actors who were initially believed to be pertinent for the project have resulted to be not interested, reactive or simple not relevant for it. As result, BioRural partners have adjusted the strategy and focused efforts on other key actors, either previously or recently identified.

Several important actors have been drawn to join and/or work together as partners in their countries have executed pertinent project initiatives. Among the 10 key actors object of contact for awareness, a total of 124 have already participated and/or collaborated, meaning:

- 42 key actors have participated, but not collaborated; thus they reach the status of “active”
- 82 actors have collaborated, meaning they reached the status of “engaged” with BioRural. It must be noted that most of these actors, 79 in total, have done both, participate and collaborate. Notwithstanding in terms of degree of engagement they are classified with the superior stage, “engaged”.

RBP NE key actors’ analysis and next steps

By cross-checking in a graph the degree of activation (X-Axis) and the relevance (Y-Axis) that the key actors may have for project implementation and growth of ERBN in their countries, each country partner has conducted an analysis of the key actors in order to further determine the status of advancement in their engagement. The representation of these variables has been arranged by means of a “quadrant diagram” (methodology and explanation provided in D2.1, section 2.2.2).

Figure 17 shows by RBP country the evolution of the key actors from M12 (August 2023) until M36 (August 2025).

KEY ACTORS ENGAGEMENT STATUS AND EVOLUTION ALONG PROJECT LIFETIME

Status at M12

Status at M24

Status at M36

POLAND

LATVIA

LITHUANIA

Figure 17. NE RBP: Quadrant diagram and evolution for the period M12 – M36

As observed in all countries, the effect of partners by interacting with key actors has caused them, especially those considered relevant, to move to the right-side quadrants of the graph, in the transition from M12 till M36. Specific details and highlights by each SW RBP country is presented below in section 2.5.2 and Appendix to D2.3.

RBP NE: ERBN and adhesion of key actors and another stakeholders

As stated in the BioRural project proposal by the expected outcome KPI Nr #1.3 (eoKPI 1.3), each BioRural RBP had to achieve 100 Stakeholders to be registered on BioRural Toolkit (for a total of 400 when the four BioRural RBPs by M36 are added). These stakeholders may include either key actors (relevant at national level because of their influence, position or ability as multipliers), or any other actor being targeted by the project (final potential adopters, technology facilitators, etc.).

This enrolment and commitment has taken place by two paths:

- persons registering into the toolkit (key actors or stakeholders organisations)

- alternatively, for key actors, not willing to register in the IT platform, by reception of a formal statement (email or letter) of their intend to collaborate and interact with ERBN community, or become part of its structure.

The achievements by M36 are summarised into Figure 18. As observed on the left side at M36 the **NE RBP countries contribute to the ERBN community with a total of 119 members**. A total of 117 have subscribed to the ERBN by registering through the BioRural toolkit, whereas 2 have done it by formally agreeing to support BioRural and participate / sustain the ERBN. This total of 119 members of the ERBN complies with the minimum target set of 100 to be reached by M36. This shows a very good contribution from the NE to the growth of the ERBN community.

Among these 119 members, 95 are persons of key actors’ organisations (having an influencing or multiplying role in the country) **and 24 are persons considered part of BioRural target audience** (farmers, technicians, technology facilitators, consultants, cooperatives, etc.). Whereas key actors have been object of direct approach and interaction, the rest of stakeholders subscribing have not been object of direct communication. The fact that they have subscribed is an indicator of the project reach and ability to create value for final target audience. These stakeholders became aware of BioRural through communication (social media, posts, news, fairs, etc.) or after participating in any of the multiple BioRural actions (workshops, tutorials, events, etc.). This aggregation of key actors and stakeholders in connection through a platform, interested in innovation, bioeconomy and application of new small scale solutions, is a principal value which in return is expected to attract more organisations to enrol into the ERBN beyond project lifespan.

As observed below, Figure 18 (right) depicts the distribution of the 119 members from NE RBP at M36. The principal groups are private companies and self-employed stakeholders (67) and research and education institutions (27), which together represent the vast majority of ERBN members and show a relatively even distribution. Associations and clusters, including NGOs, account for 12 members. On the other hand, public administrations and government bodies contribute only 7 members, highlighting the persistent difficulty of involving public actors in this type of multi-stakeholder innovation networks. Additionally, 6 members fall under the classification of "other".

Figure 18. NE RBP: Achievements in the enrolment of key actors and stakeholders into the ERBN by M36. LEFT: achievements vs target; RIGHT: disaggregation by profile

2.5.2 Highlights by NE RBP country: Poland, Latvia and Lithuania

The general planning of the strategies for Poland, Latvia and Lithuania is available as an Annex to D2.1. The update at M24 as appendix to D2.2, and the details at M36 as an appendix to this deliverable D2.3. Highlights at M36 distilled from D2.3 appendix are presented next.

POLAND

By Month 36 (M36), a total of 170 key actors has been identified in Poland, with 7 new actors added between M24 and M36. These additions were mainly linked to new success stories (Task 2.4) and the organisation of national and European Bioeconomy Challenge (T3.3). The most common profiles among these actors include primary producer organisations, rural actors, companies, and research and education institutions.

By M36, 170 actors have been approached, leading to 207 participations in project activities. Among them, 38 actors actively collaborated with BioRural, e.g. by co-organising workshops or facilitating new partnerships.

Regarding the ERBN, the initial M36 target of 30 organisations was exceeded, reaching a total of 40 members from Poland subscribed through the toolkit. Most of them represent stakeholders directly involved in project actions.

Overall, the Polish engagement strategy achieved strong results: a growing database of relevant actors, solid cooperation with scientific institutions, and expanded stakeholder participation across all key project components.

LATVIA

At M36 the total key actors identified adds a total of 61. The biggest number of 34 key actors have been added in the period M12-M24, as they were new success cases (reported under T2.4) or necessary collaborators for the organisation of national and European Bioeconomy Challenge (T3.3). In the period M24-M36 1 key actor was added, as there were less project activities of engagement with new key actors. The distribution is as presented next in Figure 37 (left), with predominant profiles primary producers organisations, rural actors, companies and their organisations and research and education. At M36, as observed in Figure 37 (right) a total of 59 key actors has been approached, leading to 30 having already participated in at least one project action, and 9 of them having already collaborated, supporting BioRural implementation (e.g. as co-organiser of T3.2 workshops, or by bridging towards other organisations).

The good evolution of the involvement of key actors into project actions is well observed into Figure 17 with the quadrant graphs. It is evident how the rightmost quadrant (meaning actors already engaged and collaborating) is more densely populated than the graph at M12.

In respect of ERBN subscription, target by M36 was initially set to 33 organisations. This figure surpasses the M36 goal, with a total of 44 members adhered to ERBN community. At the current status, a total community of 44 users can be considered as part of ERBN.

LITHUANIA

By Month 36, Lithuania identified a total of 41 key actors relevant to the BioRural project. While no new stakeholders were added between M24 and M36, this period was marked by the strengthening of collaboration and engagement with the existing ones. Most actors represent companies and their organisations, research and education institutions, and primary producer organisations. In total, 26 actors were approached in this phase, leading to 41 representatives being actively involved. By M36, all 41 had participated in at least one project action, and 35 had already collaborated with the project - e.g. through co-organisation of T3.2 workshops or participation in national bioeconomy sessions.

The key stakeholders in Lithuania include sectorial and SME representatives, self-employed individuals, and actors from forestry, farming and fishery sectors. Efforts to engage them were supported by National BioRural workshops and roundtables, which enhanced visibility of the project and deepened stakeholder interest and trust. Academic stakeholders, particularly from VMU and related institutions, showed strong involvement, benefiting from efficient internal knowledge sharing and strategic alignment with BioRural objectives.

In terms of ERBN subscriptions, Lithuania exceeded its initial target of 20 members by M24. By M36, the national ERBN community had grown to 32 organisations. Most of these were guided into the network through tailored

invitations and proposals, supported by VMU and its partners. The ERBN continues to be seen as a valuable platform for information exchange, partnerships, and shared learning in the national bioeconomy landscape.

2.6 Aggregated indicators for all RBPs and ERBN

Every RBP has developed a community of interest prepared to support BioRural initiatives and participate in the ERBN as a result of BioRural's evolution. The results obtained are summarised next, using a similar methodology as used for each RBP in the preceding sections. The total figures have been created to provide insight into the size of the ERBN community and engagement initiatives.

Summary of all RBPs: Key actors profile

Figure 19 shows the total contribution of all BioRural countries to the identification of important actors who are pertinent to promoting BioRural actions. The distribution of numbers and percentages is also shown in Table 11.

As observed in Figure 19, at M36 **1,212 organisations from the 4 RBPs were considered** as key actors who were deemed relevant for circular bioeconomy in rural areas and who could be worth to be approached. **At M12 887 key actors** had been identified. **In the period M13 to M36, BioRural partners have newly identified other 225** key actors pertinent for the project. Since the initial draft of the national strategic plans was created by partners during the first year (by M12), when several pertinent project actions had not yet begun, this rise in the targeted important players to be engaged makes sense and is cohesive. As anticipated, partners have moved forward with the tasks and established connections with several important actors throughout the M12–M36 period. Some were included to the national strategies since they were not initially recognised.

The increase of the targeted key actors has been quite even among the different classes. The distribution, as represented in Figure 19, is quite paired to the distribution in M12. All the types of target group actors have grown, thus showing no specific derive as a whole in respect the profiles initially identified at M12. Partners have found relevant to involve companies (323) as the largest group, including both, technology facilitators, early adopters and start-ups and small rural enterprises interested or connected to circular bioeconomy. Second targeted group, in size, are research and education organisations (234), as being fundamental for the project actions and in the innovation for new circular bioeconomy solutions. As well primary producers and their organisations (159) are a key target, as they are the connection with primary sector, where the agricultural, livestock and forestry residues are produced, and require sustainable solutions to embrace circularity. Government (112) and rural organisations (83) are minor in number, but are crucial as a bridge and facilitators, as well as a backup to project actions. Therefore, their number do not imply less significance, as they are very influencing actors, and as a matter of fact have been participating and engaged with project, as shown in the quadrant diagrams by country in sections above. Consultants and their organisations are crucial for knowledge transfer towards primary sector, and have added 82 organisations as target. Networks (97) and projects (73) are also well represented, those in general having more direct links and readiness for cooperation.

Figure 19. BioRural RBPs: summary of identified key actors profiles by M36.

In respect the bioeconomy topics covered by these key actors already identified, they are presented in Table 11. As observed the prevailing class Theme is “Agriculture and food” (#Agr/F) with a share of 24% of tags. The rest of bioeconomy topics range 10 to 15%, showing a good balance. The fact that #Agr/F is prominent topic is coherent with the reality in each RBP and by individual country, as agri-food sector is the principal bioeconomy sector in most of the countries. A relevant tag group is #Hor (Horizontal) with a 19% representing for example research organisations or rural organisations working horizontally in all topics. This adds representation to all bioeconomy tags. As well other organisations or companies, not specific, not linked to any topic, which add 7% in the share of targeted actors, but which are facilitators or necessary actors to promote circular bioeconomy.

Table 11. BioRural RBPs: Bioeconomy themes coverage at M36 of project

Period: M1-M36 Bioeconomy theme	TOTAL		Nr. By Profile								
	Nr	%	#PP or #PPOrg	#Comp or #Comp.Org	#Cons or #Cons.Org	#RU or #RU.Org	#Gov	#R/Ed	#Net	#Proj	#Oth
[Agr/F] Agri/F	330	24%	79	81	12	25	26	56	27	20	4
[For] Forest	139	10%	25	20	10	9	16	31	16	8	4
[Aq] Aquatic	186	13%	52	43	15	3	14	39	7	6	7
[BE] Bioenergy	160	12%	3	67	12	12	14	24	10	10	8
[BM] Biomaterials	198	14%	2	110	10	5	5	38	14	9	5
[Hor] Horizontal	268	19%	2	26	19	39	51	57	22	29	17
[Nspec] Non specific	100	7%	3	15	18	4	9	30	9	2	10
TOTAL (Nr)	1,381	100 %	166	362	96	97	141	275	105	84	55
TOTAL (%)	100%	100 %	12%	26%	7%	7%	10%	20%	8%	6%	4%

IMPORTANT NOTE: this table summarises the tags, to identify if all bioeconomy themes are being covered in the strategy to approach key actors. Since several key actors have been tagged with more than one tag, the total accounting of tags (1,381) is larger than the total number of key actors (1,212).

Status of all RBPs at M36 (August 2025)

BioRural partners considered to prioritise the **engagement of key actors by M12, by concentrating in approaching 481 of the 887 initially detected.** However, BioRural actions expanded from M12 to M24, including among others impacting actions like more than 40 workshops, 5 EU online webinars, reporting of more than 20 success cases

and launch of the EU Challenge in four regions. In consequence **partners have widen the target towards most of the key actors**, and this has led to even **increase the actors identified from 887 to 1,131 by M24**.

During the last project period, M24-M36, BioRural has finished the finals for the regional calls of the EU Challenge (by M28) and has successfully organised the EU Challenge final in Brussels (May 2025, month M33). In addition, partners have participated in external events to present project results and materialise synergies. Furthermore, more success cases, factsheets, PAs, have been uploaded to toolkit, and final recommendations, bioeconomy blueprints and policy recommendations have been released. As such, the work in the last period **has been oriented to the consolidation of results, less connected to actions of communication and participation like workshops and events**. Accordingly, partners have continued mostly working with same targeted actors. Notwithstanding new key actors have been identified, approached and engaged, as being connected or relevant to BioRural actions taking place in this last period. As result **81 new key actors have been identified** and approached, adding at the end of project **1,212 key actors** in the list of the national strategies by BioRural partners **as a whole**.

The result of BioRural partners efforts in communication and engagement with key actors until M36 is presented in Table 12 and Figure 20. **Among the 1,212 key actors identified, 943 have been object of communication**, meaning circa 78% of the identified key actors are to some degree aware of BioRural purpose and strategy. The communication and engagement performed by partners has led **to meet or establish a personal communication with 659 actors**, adding at least 1,090 meetings (on-site, on-line, phone or casual dialogues as result of networking in events). This has been instrumental to **lead 441 of these 1,212 actors** (more than 36%) **to participate** in project actions. **And in total 305 of the targeted actors** (more than 25%) have **collaborated** by supporting or co-organising project actions (470 individual collaborations in total). Among the total 1,212 key actors identified, **269 remain at the end of project without evidence of awareness**. This is partly due to non-response, or to the fact that partners have decided to not contact or engage. The reason is in most cases that these organisations were initially thought to be ideal to play a role in circular bioeconomy for rural areas, and therefore prone to take part in BioRural actions. However, as projects progressed and initiatives were initiated, the initial assumptions about possible interest and synergies that could be achieved turned out to be either unfeasible or unworkable. These actors, however, may still play a role in future for ERBN, as they are in fact connected to relevant areas to promote more circular bioeconomy and innovation in rural areas.

Table 12. BioRural RBPs: Actions performed to approach key actors by M36

ACTIONS	Nr. KEY ACTORS			TOTAL NR of actions			Interpretation (figures at M36)
	M12	M24	M36	M12	M24	M36	
Communi-cations	402	824	943	402	824	943	Informative or "ice-breaking" interactions are used to raise awareness of BioRural's existence and objectives. They are not engagement actions, though. <i>A total of 943 key actors have been contacted via phone, calls or emails.</i>
Meetings	252	542	659	289	738	1090	<u>Meetings are direct actions of engagement</u> (visits, in-person talk, phone or e-meetings) where partners explain value and try to activate interest, so that key actors will take part into BioRural actions. <i>A total of 659 key actors approached, few of them with more than one meeting, totalling 1,090 meetings.</i>
Participa-tions	166	356	441	181	470	668	<u>Participation refers to</u> take part in a project action, meaning key actors are active, though not necessarily engaged and supporting project. Examples: participate as audience in a seminar or workshop, respond a survey, etc. <i>A total of 441 key actors have participated in BioRural actions by M36. Several of them participated in more than one action (adding a total of 668 participations). Among these 441 key actors, 236 of them have also collaborated, thus considered status of "engaged", whereas the rest 205 simply participated, thus considered their status as "active" (see Figure 4).</i>
Collabora-tions	80	229	305	87	303	470	<u>Collaboration means</u> that engagement has been successful to trigger key actors to support BioRural actions: by collaborating in organising a workshop, by engaging other stakeholders to participate in project surveys, etc.

A total of 305 key actors have collaborated with BioRural. Several of them collaborated not just once, and therefore 470 collaborations took place.

As Observed in in Table 12 (period M12 to M36) the increase of meetings, participations and collaborations have continued growing in the last project period. However, the rate of new meetings, participations and collaborations during this last period (M24-M36) is not as high as it was during the period M12-M24. This is coherent as most of the actions in events, workshops took place in the period M12-M24, whereas final actions during M24-M36 were intended to produce the final results, and promote its dissemination, more than the preparation of workshops ad events.

These figures are also displayed visually and disaggregated in Figure 20 by key actor profile.

Figure 20. BioRural RBPs: status of activation of key actors at M36. LEFT: Identified VS Approached. RIGHT: distribution of achievements by type of key actor

As observed in Figure 20 (left) during the project the BioRural partners faced to potentially contact and or engage the whole set of identified key actors (totaling 1,212). **Partners have finally approached 943 of them by M36** thus becoming: aware (450), active (205, having participated but not collaborated) and engaged (302, having collaborated, and many of them, also participated). A number of key actors who were initially believed to be pertinent for the project have resulted to be not interested, reactive or simple not relevant for it. As result, BioRural partners have adjusted the strategy and focused efforts on other key actors, either previously or recently identified.

Several important actors have been drawn to join and/or work together as partners in their countries have executed pertinent project initiatives. Among the 943 key actors object of contact for awareness, **a total of 507 (more than 53%) have already participated and/or collaborated**, meaning:

- 205 key actors have participated, but not collaborated; thus they reach the status of “active”
- 302 actors have collaborated, meaning they reached the status of “engaged” with BioRural. It must be noted that several of these actors, 236 in total, have done both, participate and collaborate. Notwithstanding in terms of degree of engagement they are classified with the superior stage, “engaged”.

Summary of all RBPs: ERBN and adhesion of key actors and another stakeholders

As stated in the BioRural project proposal by the expected outcome KPI Nr #1.3 (eoKPI 1.3), each BioRural RBP had to achieve 100 Stakeholders to be registered on BioRural Toolkit (for a total of 400 when the four BioRural RBPs by M36 are added). These stakeholders’ organisations may include either key actors (relevant at national level

because of their influence, position or ability as multipliers), or any other actor being targeted by the project (final potential adopters, technology facilitators, etc.).

This enrolment and commitment has taken place by two paths:

- persons registering into the toolkit (key actors or stakeholders organisations)
- alternatively, for key actors, not willing to register in the IT platform, by reception of a formal statement (email or letter) of their intend to collaborate and interact with ERBN community, or become part of its structure.

At month M12 a total of 233 users had either subscribed or declared intend to be part of ERBN. The ERBN community grew to reach **472 members by M24** (432 through the toolkit registration and 40 of them through a formal statement). **By M36, as observed in Figure 18, 586 persons are part of ERBN community in the 14 BioRural countries. However, 30 persons have registered from other countries:** Northern countries (like Finland or Sweden) adding 6 ERBN members; Eastern countries (Slovakia, Moldavia) adding 7 members; Central Europe (like Austria, Luxembourg, Belgium) adding 9 members, United Kingdom adding 4, or other countries from world adding 4 members).

In total ERBN membership adds 616 members from 26 countries, 574 registered through the toolkit, and 42 having declared formally their interest to be part but preferring to not register through the digital platform.

Among these 616 members, 376 are persons of key actors organisations (having an influencing or multiplying role in the country) **and 240 are persons considered part of BioRural target audience:** from the 14 project countries (farmers, technicians, technology facilitators, consultants, cooperatives, etc.), or from other countries (mainly Research and Education organisations, companies and clusters). Whereas key actors have been object of direct approach and interaction, the rest of stakeholders subscribing have not. The fact that they have subscribed is an indicator of the project reach and ability to create value for final target audience. These stakeholders became aware of BioRural through communication (social media, posts, news, fairs, etc.) or after participating in any of the multiple BioRural actions (workshops, tutorials, events, etc.). This aggregation of key actors and stakeholders in connection through a platform, interested in innovation, bioeconomy and application of new small-scale solutions, is a principal value which in return is expected to attract more organisations to enrol into the ERBN beyond project lifespan.

As observed below, **Table 13 and Figure 21** depict the **distribution of the 586 members from BioRural ERBN in the 14 project countries at M36.** It shows that the principal group are companies already in M12, though has been the group expanding more from M12. This is an indicator that M12 onwards BioRural actions have been able to raise the interest of private sector. Furthermore, at M12 the number of R&D members was similar in size as for companies. E&D members have keep growing during all periods, not as much as the category of companies, and showing the project was able to keep mobilising interest from R&D organisations. As well farmers organisations and clusters have expanded well through the project lifespan. Government and public servants are present to a lesser extent, and with smaller growing rate. This shows a good work of partners in initial engagement when project was launched, and the fact that most relevant or eager bodies were already incorporated in this first stage. Other actors are projects and networks also relevant for knowledge and results transfer. **All in all, this brings together key actors necessary to promote collaborations and further transfer and uptake of new bio-based circular solutions, which is a great value. This ERBN community is one of the key products of BioRural project.**

Table 13. Distribution of the ERBN community members in the 14 BioRural countries along the project periods

Profile	Nr. ERBN members		
	M12(*)	M24	M36
Associations, Clusters, NGOs	40	95	106

Government and public administrations	28	36	38
Private company / Self-employed	69	179	240
Research and education	68	124	156
Other	28	38	46
TOTAL	233	472	586

(*) Estimates for ERBN members at M12, based on distribution for 192 registrants through toolkit (profile of actors formally declaring interest but not registered was not included in M12 report)

Figure 21. BioRural ERBN: Achievements in the enrolment of key actors and stakeholders into the ERBN by M36 in the 14 BioRural countries. LEFT: achievements vs target; RIGHT: disaggregation by profile

Regarding the gender structure in the ERBN, the evolution has been quite paired, both in M24 and in M36. As observed Figure 22. By M24a total of 432 persons registered through the BioRural toolkit. Among them, 201 were identified as male, whereas 202 did it as female. Twentynine members (6.7%) did not disclose name or reveal gender, therefore gender is recorded as unknown.

In order to improve tracking, the registration process was modified after the reporting period M18, being effective shortly before M24. The objective was to ensure better tracking of the gender of ERBN members. BioRural partners received instructions to observe the evolution of gender, and try to detect deviations from parity. Figure 22 reveals how the gender balance is well paired by project end (M36), with 270 members being identified as male, and 271 as female. Four persons, 3% of the persons newly registered in the ERBN in this last period (M24-M36), did not disclose gender details. This shows an improvement in the tracking of the registration.

Figure 22. Gender distribution in the ERBN in M24 and M36 (registrants through toolkit)

The gender analysis has been disclosed by professional profiles after the first reporting period, and published in M24 in the deliverable report D2.2, and here with the update of figures in M36. The results are presented next in Figure 23.

Overall, the M24 balance shows a good balance. Taking into account for the purposes of this analysis simply the male-female balance (excluding members whose gender is unclear), it is observed that:

- As the gender distribution by stakeholder type is quite paired for government and the group of other types of stakeholders.
- For Research and education organisations and Private Companies prevails the male over the female gender, though not beyond 55% share.
- In contrast the Associations, clusters and NGOs registrants are more predominantly female, with shares reaching 66%.

Figure 23. Gender distribution according to ERBN members profile. Data in M24 and M36

The balance in M36 is quite similar to M24. Considering again for the analysis only the male – female balance (not counting the members for which gender is unknown), it is evidenced that:

- As the gender distribution remains quite paired for government and the group of other types of stakeholders.
- Research and education organisations balance disimproved partially, rising from 52% male share in M24 to 55% in M36
- Private Companies improved with 3 percentiles the balance reaching 51% in M36
- Associations, clusters and NGOs registrants keep the same rate of 66% share for females in M36

In summary, the gender balance has evolved in a very pairwise and even trend through the project. This reveals a good involvement and not relevant segmentation by biologic gender of the participation of persons in the ERBN. Furthermore, it reflects the work of engagement leaded by BioRural aiming to consider the gender balance in the creation of the ERBN community. It is evidenced a trend to female to be more linked to works in clusters and organisations, though. And a slightly more male profile in private companies and research and education organisations dealing with circular bioeconomy.

3 Area of action #2. Bioeconomy networks and projects

3.1 Introduction

Throughout the project's duration, BioRural has sought to embrace synergies with other national or EU institutions related to the rural circular bioeconomy, such as multi-actor projects and theme networks. In order to complement and strengthen other EU institutions and channels, the goal was to promote broad dissemination and exploitation, improve the cross-border transfer of regional bio-based solution applications, and create long-lasting partnerships in such action lines.

For that purpose, it is crucial to establish contact and synergies with other networks and projects. In case of networks, those that complement BioRural work and value, or other networks that partially overlap in purpose or functions. In both cases to generate more impact and more reach by combining actions or sharing materials.

BioRural has established two action lines for this purpose.

- Creation of a new permanent collaborative structure: the recently created (May 2023) RBA – Rural Bioeconomy Alliance, a cluster of European funded projects which come together to share knowledge on project outcomes and support dissemination and communication activities related to existing knowledge of the bioeconomy. BioRural performs the connection with the RBA projects through CERTH as project coordinator and by RFF as communication leader. Individual partners are establishing synergies at local level, when any of the RBA projects operates in their country as well.
- Individual interaction of BioRural with other EU and national bioeconomy research projects and networks:
 - Projects: either EU or national, they are temporal environments of collaboration of organizations, which are, at least some of them, key actors for BioRural. These projects, when aligned with BioRural vision and objectives, offer the possibility to establish punctual or temporary collaborations to achieve wider impacts, either at EU or at national level.
 - Networks: either EU or national, offer the possibility to reinforce BioRural's reach, by complementing actions, or by facilitating access to a wider public. These networks, refer principally to national and EU networks like CAP Networks, or Rural Development Networks. But beyond these formal networks, other networks specific on bioeconomy, sustainable farming, agri-food innovation and transfer, etc. are potential allies for BioRural either at EU or at national level.

Both forms of liaison have been explored by BioRural partners. The steps performed in respect the RBA activation, and the identified projects and networks are presented in next sub-sections 3.2 and 3.3 respectively.

3.2 The Rural Bioeconomy Alliance – RBA

3.2.1 About RBA

The Rural Bioeconomy Alliance (RBA) is a cluster of European funded projects that support the development of rural sustainable circular bioeconomy initiatives in the EU with action lines such as: analyse framework, rural circular bioeconomy success stories, best practices, pilots as well as ways to increase the adoption of circular bioeconomy concepts mainly in rural areas (e.g. training and education).

By creating such a cluster, it is enhanced the impact on supporting the transition towards a circular bioeconomy beyond the effects achievable by individual projects. These projects come together to share knowledge on project outcomes and support dissemination and communication activities related to existing knowledge of the bioeconomy. The RBA project members have agreed to collaborate to promote joint actions, knowledge sharing and synergies as follows: (i) events organisation and dissemination / promotion; (ii) exchange of success stories contents and lessons learned; (iii) exchange insights on small-scale biobased innovative technologies; (iv)

workshops co-organisation and promotion; (v) knowledge exchange among projects and to a wider audience; (vi) reinforced dissemination of projects' results

3.2.2 RBA members and coordination

On a six-month cycle, several project representatives (usually coordinator or communication leaders) take up the RBA coordination. Through CERTH, BioRural started the RBA and oversaw its first six months from May 15 to November 15, 2023. Numerous organisations have now adopted the coordinator function. The RBA coordinator is in charge of organising and hosting regular virtual meetings of all project representatives and leading any other tasks that are required to keep the RBA relevant and active. The RBA is currently going through an expansion whereby a number of additional projects. In addition to the 11 originally participating, a total of 8 have joined.

- | | |
|--------------------|----------------|
| 1. ROBIN | 12. Argonatut |
| 2. CEE2ACT | 13. thERBN |
| 3. ShapingBio | 14. Futural |
| 4. BioModel4Region | 15. Agriloop |
| 5. COOPID | 16. BIO2REG |
| 6. Scale-UP | 17. BioINSouth |
| 7. RuralBioUp | 18. BRILLIAN |
| 8. RELIEF | 19. BBionets |
| 9. P2Green | |
| 10. MainstreamBIO | |
| 11. BioRural | |

The total number of projects reaches in August 2025 (Month 36 of BioRural) a total of 19 projects, which logos are presented below in Figure 24.

Figure 24. Rural Bioeconomy Alliance – RBA: logo and participating projects at date August 2025

3.2.3 Results – Status at M36

At M9 the RBA launched in the frame of the COOPID Bioeconomy Conference, which was held in Brussels (on the 31st of May 2023). Since then, regular internal meetings between Alliance members have allowed partners to share relevant knowledge, events and explore synergies. Over the period M12-M24, the Alliance has been

represented at various high-level events including the Regional Innovation Valleys for Bioeconomy and Food Systems (RIV4BFS), the EC Bioeconomy Changemakers Festival and the World Circular Economy Forum. In addition, the RBA has been represented and presented at a range of national workshops held by RBA members.

Between months M25 and M36, the leadership and facilitation of the Rural Bioeconomy Alliance (RBA) transitioned twice. From December 2024 to May 2025, the Alliance was coordinated by CLuBE, representing the BioModels4Regions project. Leadership then shifted to Moverim, representing the P2GreenN project, for the period from June to November 2025.

Each coordinating organization was responsible for organizing regular RBA meetings involving all participating projects, managing the Alliance's social media presence across all platforms, and responding to member inquiries. They also undertook tasks essential to maintaining the relevance and visibility of the RBA.

A key activity during this period was the RBA's participation in the EU Green Week in June 2025, where the Alliance was presented alongside several newly joined EU projects. Additionally, several participating projects successfully concluded their activities during this time, including COOPID, RELIEF, and BioModels4Regions.

3.3 Liaison with national and EU projects

One of BioRural's strategies for achieving more significant outcomes and expanding the project's reach to a wider range of stakeholders has been liaising with projects. Projects are short-term endeavours that rely on action plans and allocated funds to be carried out. Therefore, working on projects at the national or EU level has proven to be a way to increase the influence of the BioRural action plans.

The liaison with projects is presented below, arranged as follows:

1. **The RBA – Rural bioeconomy alliance:** as a collaborative framework for EU funded projects on rural bioeconomy
2. **Long term EU initiatives:** projects that may facilitate not only individual synergies, but the integration of BioRural results, ERBN and BioRural toolkit with/into other referential EU scale structures and initiatives
3. **EU funded projects,** contemporary and similar to BioRural, with 2 to 4 years duration, and having similar scopes and targets, thus allowing collaborations at EU Level (in webinars, EU events, etc.) and at national level (local or regional workshops, surveys, etc.) when the projects have programmed actions in the same country
4. **National projects,** which may allow synergies at local or national level in a specific country by the interaction of a specific partner with projects like Operational groups, national R&D projects, operating only at national or local scale

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY – NATIONAL and EU projects

BioRural partners have contributed through task T2.1 and T2.2 to establish contact and collaborations with other EU and also national projects. Multiple synergies have taken place. **At month M36 a total of 50 individual collaborations took effect between partners of BioRural and 19 RBA projects.**

Additionally, a total of three long term EU initiatives has been identified: **EU-Farmbook, modernAKIS and Tools4CAP.** In total **9 synergies were identified, and 5 have been leveraged.** The **agreement to link the BioRural toolbox with EU-Farmbook** has resulted in the **primary synergy.** Toolkit began with BioRural and will continue with a new project entitled thERBN once BioRural is completed.

Partners have **identified a total of 35 EU project and 8 national projects** to establish synergies with. **About EU projects,** a total of **63 synergies were discussed, leveraging 52 collaborations** by end of BioRural project. In respect the **national 8 funded projects, 17 potential synergies were identified, and gave rise to 15 effective individual collaborations.**

3.3.1 Liaison with RBA projects

The RBA projects cluster (as presented in section 3.2) has already started the collaboration among project coordinators and dissemination leaders. At country level BioRural partners have identified, discussed and triggered synergies with other national partners from RBA projects

Among the 19 RBA projects, synergies have been established with all the 11 projects who founded the RBA, and as well with few of the projects who joined recently. By end of BioRural project (month M36) partners have established links at national level, to discuss synergies. In total **59 potential synergies were identified**, and **50 have taken place with 13 RBA projects**, as reported by partners.

Table 14. Series of tables to track synergies with the RBA projects

Type of project	Short name / Timing	Focus area	Link	Leader	Keywords / Focus area
Horizon Project	COOPID (Jan 2021-June 2023)	#Ag, #For, #Aq, #BM, #BE	WEB	Spanish Agrifood Cooperatives	Bioeconomy cluster, innovative business model, primary production, knowledge transfer, peer-to-peer dissemination

Project description:

The reduction of CO2 emissions and an overall lower waste production chain hinge on the successful uptake of sustainable bio-based business models in the primary production sector. The EU-funded COOPID project is proposing a new strategy. A network of COOPID Bioeconomy Clusters from 10 European countries has been created ad hoc, involving a range of stakeholders: primary producers, in cooperatives or associations, within agriculture, forestry and aquaculture; industry; public sector; research and academia. Based on the proposed model, COOPID ambassadors will showcase success stories, organise workshops and conduct interactive dissemination and communication campaigns. One of the main target groups will be women and young producers who have great potential to innovate but are underrepresented in the primary production sector

Partner / country / status: CERTH / Greece / Finished

Synergy planned: (i) dissemination of BioRural and RBA during COOPID final project conference

Achieved: (i) CERTH presented newly created RBA platform and BioRural during the Final COOPID Conference (31st may 2023, #EUGreenWeek 2023 Partner Event, at Les Ateliers des Tanneurs, Brussels).

Type of project	Short name / Timing	Focus area	Link	Leader	Keywords / Focus area
Horizon Project	MainstreamBIO (Oct 2022-Sept2025)	#Ag, #For, #Aq, #BM	WEB	QPlan	Small scale, biobased, solutions, rural

Project description:

The objective of MainstreamBIO is to foster small-scale bio-based projects in rural areas, in order to promote the participation of more actors in the development of the bioeconomy. The project will offer tailor-made technical and business support tools and services, designed in collaboration with Multi-Stakeholder Innovation Platforms (MIPs), to rural actors in the participating regions leading small-scale bioeconomy initiatives.

Partner / country / status: AVEBIOM / SPAIN / identified and partially implemented

Synergy planned: (i) co-organisation of events/workshops. (ii) Support project visualisation. (iii) Collaboration in the European Challenge in Spain

Achieved: : (i) co-organised B2B in frame of Expobiomasa 8th May 2025; (iii) INNOVARUM (Spanish partner of MainstreamBio) shared T3.3 EU challenge with bioeconomy community of interest in Ebro Valley region (June 2024). As well Innovarum was part of the jury

Partner / country / status: CERTH / Greece / Ongoing

Synergy planned: (i) connecting MainstreamBio and BioRural candidates for mutual calls; (ii) Potential joined policy workshop in May/June 2025

Achieved: (i) mutual support in finding candidates for MainstreamBIO's open call for Central Macedonia and BioRural Eu challenge SE regional call (T3.3); (ii) Joined policy workshop in Brussels on 14th may 2025; (iii) joint policy briefs as input to new EU Bioeconomy strategy

Partner / country / status: IUNG / Poland / participating

Synergy planned: (i) mutual support in dissemination; (ii) co-organisation of events and workshops, (iii) common final event (e.g), (iv) round table,

Achieved: (i) IUNG partner shared T3.3 EU challenge with bioeconomy community of interest in (June 2024), distribution of brochures at their workshops. Including information about BioRural at presentations during their meetings. (ii) Partners from MainstreamBIO have presented their work at workshop organised within T3.1

Partner / country / status: Delphy / The Netherlands / linked

Synergy planned: (i) mutual support in and presenting their project work at workshops and events; (ii) support to project visualization (iii) Collaboration towards the European Challenge in the Netherlands

Achieved: (iii) participating in ERBN, participating in organized events and workshops. (ii) Shared communication on workshops and results.

Type of project	Short name / Timing	Focus area	Link	Leader	Keywords / Focus area
Horizon Project	CEE2ACT	#Ag, #For, #Aq, #BM	WEB	Geonardo Ltd	Small scale, biobased, solutions, rural

Project description:

CEE2ACT is empowering countries in Central Eastern Europe and beyond (Bulgaria, Croatia, Czech Republic, Greece, Hungary, Poland, Romania, Serbia, Slovakia and Slovenia) to develop circular bioeconomy strategies and action plans through innovative governance models. The objective is to achieve better informed decision-making processes, societal engagement and innovation, building on the practice of partners from contributing countries (Austria, Germany, The Netherlands, Belgium, Spain, Finland, Sweden), and addressing relevant economic, social and environmental aspects. The project will also create bioeconomy hubs to facilitate the transfer of knowledge and to develop a participatory, non-political, bottom-up approach.

Partner / country / status: IUNG / Poland / participating

Synergy planned: (i) co-organisation of events and workshops, (ii) common final event (e.g)

Achieved: (i) Partners from CEE2ACT have presented their work at workshop organised within T3.1

Partner / country / status: GEA /ASIMCOV / ROMANIA / discussed, close cooperation.

Synergy planned: (i) co-organisation of events and workshops. (II) Support to project visualisation. (III) Joint event in Q4 of 2023 with the support of the Sustainable Development Department of the Government of Romania.

Achieved: (i) co-organised a workshop on capacity building and knowledge transfer in May 2024 and March 2025. (iii) organized joint event in Q4 of 2023 with the support of the Sustainable Development Department of the Government of Romania, jointly participated in the bioeconomy session in the Clusters meet Regions in Iasi, in November 2023, in the Bioeast Conference in Bucharest on the 9th April 2025 together with other RBA projects.

Partner / country / status: UL, Algen / Slovenia/ close cooperation with the Anteja (Partner in CEE2ACT, contact for Bioeconomy hub in Slovenia <https://www.cee2act.eu/hub/slovenia/>).

Synergy planned: (i) co-organisation of events and workshops. (ii) Supporting dissemination; (iii) further collaborations

Achieved: (i) Participation in two national multi-actor innovation workshops. (iii) UL has been invited to CEE2Act Bioeconomy HUB Slovenia. (iv) UL has participated in the project meeting in Wageningen UR (invited by Antea). (v) UL has participated in all of the Slovenia Bioeconomy HUB activities.

Type of project	Short name / Timing	Focus area	Link	Leader	Keywords / Focus area
Horizon Project	RuralBioUp (October 2022 - September 2025)	#Ag, #For, #BM	WEB	APRE	Bioeconomy, biobased, circular economy

Project description:

The aim of the RuralBioUp project is to bring together the players in an area in order to develop the use of bio-based resources on a local scale. RuralBioUp also seeks to develop and structure the bioeconomy sectors in the territories.

It will strengthen the cooperation among regional key actors and knowledge holders in order to support bio-based business models in rural areas. In particular, RuralBioUp will establish nine regional hubs across six EU countries that will co-design and implement nine action plans on 18 value chains. Those areas will be empowered by RuralBioUp's partners with mentoring, coaching and training activities in the implementation of their action plans. A digital tool, the RuralBioUp One-Stop-Shop, will support regional actors in making science-based decisions. By mapping the players and their needs beforehand, the project will develop a platform for pooling solutions and cooperation between local players (e.g. producers of by-products and innovators of bio-based solutions).

Partner / country / status: Valorial / FRANCE / agreed.

Achieved: (i) Agreement to disseminate BioRural events and actions (ii) communication to the RuralBio Up and Scale Up network of ERBN and registrations.

Partner / country / status: CERTH/ Greece /ongoing

Synergy planned: (i) Involvement of BioRural members in validation of RuralBioUp platform; (ii) joint policy briefs

Achieved: (i) Members of BioRural were invited and participated in RuralBioUp's platform validation focus group in Iasi, Romania on November 21st 2023. (ii) joint policy briefs as input to new EU Bioeconomy Strategy

Partner / country / status: GEA / ROMANIA / discussed, close cooperation

Synergy planned: (i) visualisation of mutual actions (ii) Potential joint workshops on inland raw materials topic (agriculture, forestry) (iii) Joint event in Q4 of 2023 with the support of the Sustainable Development Department of the Government of Romania.

Achieved: (iii) jointly participated in the bioeconomy session in the Clusters meet Regions in Iasi, in November 2023, and in the Bioeast Conference in Bucharest on the 9th April 2025, together with other RBA projects. (ii) organised joint consultation workshops with stakeholders from Centru region, Romania on agriculture and forestry

Partner / country / status: CBE/ Portugal/ First contact performed
Institute for Economic Forecasting – Romanian Academy/

Achieved: No further synergy achieved

Partner / country / status: LBTU / Latvia/ collaboration achieved

Synergy planned: (i) knowledge and insights generated in this project used in the BioRural project

Achieved: (i) knowledge and insights generated in this project used in the BioRural project

Type of project	Short name / Timing	Focus area	Link	Leader	Keywords / Focus area
Horizon Project	SCALE-UP (September 2022- August 2025)	#Ag, #For, #BM	WEB	ECO	Bioeconomy, biobased, circular economy

Project description:

The overall objective of SCALE-UP is to support regional multi-stakeholder partnerships, comprising private companies, public authorities, civil society organisations and researchers, to identify and develop innovative and sustainable value chains based on regional biomass resources. Through its approach, SCALE-UP will adapt, implement and evaluate tools to help regional actors overcome apparent bottlenecks to fully exploit the potential of the bioeconomy in their region. SCALE-UP will support regional multi-actor partnerships, consisting of private businesses, governments and policymakers, civil society organizations, and researchers in identifying and scaling-up innovative and sustainable bio-based value chains that build on regional resources.

Partner / country / status: Valorial / FRANCE / agreed

Achieved: (i) Agreement to disseminate BioRural events and actions (ii) communication to the RuralBioUp and Scale Up network of ERBN and registrations.

Partner / country / status: CERTH / Greece/ongoing

Synergy planned: (i) mutual dissemination of project actions; (ii) Joint policy briefs

Achieved: (i) Disseminated SCALE-UP request to look for relevant local biobased value chains that would be relevant for mentoring support. (ii) preparing join policy briefs and comments to EU Bioeconomy strategy

Partner / country / status: Green Growth Platform / North Macedonia/ Synergy agreed upon

Synergy planned: (i) Participation in events/workshops. (ii) Collaboration in stakeholders mapping and engagement in the south-eastern parts of The Republic of North Macedonia.

Achieved: (i) Participation in online knowledge exchange workshops by an invitation of SDEWES center – North Macedonia (SCALE UP project partner). (ii) Collaborative meeting and activities for the purposes of key stakeholders mapping in the rural bio-economy.

Partner / country / status: AVEBIOM/ Spain / First contact performed

Synergy planned: (i) potential connection of BioRural success case with SCALE-UP workshops; (ii) Potential participation in workshops; (iii) Mutual dissemination.

Achieved: (iii) communication in social networks and distribution of SW EU challenge opportunity

Type of project	Short name / Timing	Focus area	Link	Leader	Keywords / Focus area
Horizon Project	Biomodel4regions (July 2022-June 2025)	#Ag, #For, #Aq, #BM	WEB	Ciaotech	Bioeconomy, biobased, network

Project description:

The BIOMODEL4REGIONS project aims to support the establishment of the innovative governance models at local/regional level to achieve better-informed decision-making processes, social engagement and innovation to support and strengthen EU and international science-policy interfaces to achieve the Sustainable Development Goals.

Partner / country / status: NaturePlast / FRANCE /participating

Synergy planned: (i) Share network and pool the effects.

Achieved: (i) Discussions have been initiated with a view to presenting the two projects at French workshops, as well as monitoring and promoting both projects on social networks.

Type of project	Short name / Timing	Focus area	Link	Leader	Keywords / Focus area
Horizon Project	P2Green (Dec 2022-Nov 2026)	#Ag, #BE #BM	WEB	Agrathaer GMBH	-Air and water pollution control - Fertilization - Wastewater management

Project description:

P2Green will foster a paradigm shift, from a linearly organized resource and nutrient system within the agri-food supply chain, towards a circular material flow system between urban and rural areas thereby restoring the coupling of the water-agri-food system using a holistic symbiotic resource management approach following the 3R principle "Reduce, Reuse, Recover". P2Green will therefore develop new

circular governance solutions for the transition from fork to farm to halt and eliminate N & P pollution by connecting blue urban with green rural infrastructure, focusing on circular nutrient flows of nitrogen (N) and phosphorus (P).

Partner / country / status: CERTH / Greece / ongoing

Synergy planned: (i) mutual collaboration in events and workshops. (ii) Support to project visualisation. (iii) Collaboration towards the European Challenge in Greece

Achieved: (i) Presented the BioRural toolkit to coordinators as an example of best practice.

Type of project	Short name / Timing	Focus area	Link	Leader	Keywords / Focus area
ERASMUS-LS	RELIEF (June 2022-May 2025)	#BE, #Agr	WEB	UoP	bio economy, sustainable development, circular economy, digitalization, agriculture, green skills, entrepreneurial skills, transversal skills, digital skills

Project description:

RELIEF aims to develop and deliver an innovative approach for teaching bio-economy in farming, by developing specific learning resources addressing HEIs students and farming practitioners. HEIs, VETs, farmer consultants, research institutes, and social partners from Italy, Greece, Sweden, Cyprus and Portugal will deliver a high-quality network within the EU to advance bio-economy in the farming agenda. RELIEF will deliver a training needs analysis and develop two curricula in bio-economy, for HE students, farming practitioners and farmers exploring the key areas that are critical for the implementation of business models and strategies towards bio-economy in farming. Based on this knowledge, RELIEF will design and pilot learning units which will incorporate a mix of training methodologies.

Partner / country / status: CERTH/ Greece / ongoing

Synergy planned: (i) visualisation of mutual actions. (ii) Potential workshop on inland resources. (iii) Synergies on European Challenge.

Achieved: (i) Relief project was presented in the Greek National Aquatics Workshop

Type of project	Short name / Timing	Focus area	Link	Leader	Keywords / Focus area
Horizon 2020	ShapingBio (Sep 2022-Aug 2025)	#BE, #Agr	WEB	FRAUNHOFER Institut	Food system bioeconomy governance

Project description:

ShapingBio: aims to support and accelerate such an ecosystem. To that end, it will map and analyse initiatives, structures, policy instruments, gaps in policy and governance, applied R&D and technology transfer, as well as collaboration and financing across the EU macro-regions and fields. It will work with stakeholders from various sectors and receive input from key actors. The results will lead to evidence-based and concrete information and recommendations for better policy-making and stakeholder activity. Moreover, it will support the EU Green Deal policy priorities and the EU's climate ambition for 2030 and beyond.

Partner / country / status: AVEBIOM/Spain / ongoing

Synergy planned: (i) participation in ShapingBio cross sectorial workshops. (ii) Dissemination of T3.3 EU Challenge.

Achieved: (i) AVEBIOM invited by AseBio (Spanish partner) and participated in cross-sectorial workshops online #1 (nov. 2023) and #3 (June 2024). (ii) T3.3 EU Challenge call SW shared by AseBio to local community of interest for ShapingBio.

Partner / country / status: IUNG/Poland/ongoing

Synergy planned: participation in ShapingBio cross sectorial workshops.

Achieved: IUNG invited by APRE (Italian partner) and participated in cross-sectorial workshops online #1 (nov. 2023) # onside (18th of April).

Type of project	Short name / Timing	Focus area	Link	Leader	Keywords / Focus area
Horizon Project	Robin (Sep 2022-Aug 2025)	#Agr, #BE	WEB	QPLAN	-government systems, bioeconomy

Project description:

ROBIN aims to empower Europe's regions to adapt their governance models and structures in ways that accelerate the achievement of their circular bioeconomy targets while promoting social innovation and accounting for different territorial contexts.

Partner / country / status: CERTH / Greece/ongoing

Synergy planned: (i) dissemination of project activities; (ii) Future synergies under discussion.; (iii) Organising policy workshop in Brussels; (iii) Joint policy brief

Achieved: (i) Robin partners disseminated BioRural's open calls during their workshop on July 18th 2024. (ii) co-organising policy workshop in Brussels on 13th and 14th May 2025; (iii) collaboration to prepare joint policy brief and comments to the EU Bioeconomy strategy (June 2025)

Type of project	Short name / Timing	Focus area	Link	Leader	Keywords / Focus area
Horizon Project	BBioNets (Nov 2023 – Oct 2026)	#Ag, #For	WEB	MTU	Small scale, biobased, solutions, rural

Project description:

BBioNets will rely on, promote, and further advance the work carried out by EIP-AGRI Operational Groups (OGs) with respect to management and/or processing of agricultural and forest biomass with [Bio-Based Technologies \(BBTs\)](#). FANs will identify local needs and, through co-creation and joint actions, prioritise specific BBTs, benefit from and validate knowledge material developed by the consortium building on previous OG and EU-funded project results. Applying the quintuple helix model and a multi-actor approach both within the consortium itself and on the ground activities, BBioNets will set up 6 regional Forest and Agriculture Networks - FANs (IE, EL, ES, IT, PL, CZ) that will ensure balanced representation of all AKIS stakeholders.

Partner / country / status: IUNG / Poland / participating

Synergy planned: (i) mutual dissemination; (ii) participation in events and workshops,

Achieved: (i) share of newsletter, invitation to workshops ; (ii) Presentation of BioRural toolkit at kickoff meeting of BBioNets

Partner / country / status: AVEBIOM/ Spain / participating

Synergy planned: (i) mutual dissemination; (ii) participation in BBionets Spanish FAN (Forest and Agriculture Network)

Achieved: (i) sort intro of BioRural to BBionets Spanish partner; (ii) Participation in 3rd meeting of Spanish FAN on 8th July 2025

Type of project	Short name / Timing	Focus area	Link	Leader	Keywords / Focus area
RIA	ARGONAUT (01.2025 – 06.2028)	#Hor	WEB	CERTH	Bio-based value chains - AI

Project description: The EU-funded ARGONAUT project will develop an efficient and user-friendly AI digital tool to calculate the climate and environmental impacts of bio-based products throughout their value chain. Additionally, the project will deliver a decision-support tool to recommend alternative, more sustainable actions and decisions. Through these efforts, it will support small and medium-sized producers while significantly assisting in the implementation of the EU's Ecodesign for Sustainable Products Regulation.

Partner / country / status: UL / Slovenia / Partner

Synergy planned: (i) Activities related to ERBN and RBA

Achieved: (i) KoM participation

Type of project	Short name / Timing	Focus area	Link	Leader	Keywords / Focus area ^[IP1]
Horizon Europe	tHERBN (01.2025 – 12.2027)	#Hor	WEB	University Ghent	Circular bioeconomy, urgent needs, primary sector, by-products, residues, solutions, thematic network

Project description: tHERBN aims to establish a multi-actor thematic network that bridges the gap between existing innovative circular bioeconomy solutions and the real-world challenges faced by small-holder farmers and foresters at a local scale in rural areas. By identifying practical and sustainable approaches to managing biological by-products and residues, tHERBN strives to empower practitioners with actionable solutions. As part of its mission, tHERBN will ensure open access to long-term digital depositories, like the EU-Farmbook platform. The project will also develop tools in multiple languages to facilitate this knowledge-sharing and to enhance cross-border collaboration. Additionally, tHERBN will offer policy recommendations to support the adoption of small-scale circular bioeconomy solutions on farms. The tHERBN consortium is led by Ghent University (UGent) in cocreation with 20 partners from 11 countries.

Partner / country / status: AVEBIOM, CERTH, GEA, Valorial, VMU, IUNG / EU / Planned and Achieved

Synergy planned: (i) organisation of workshop urgent needs from primary sector in Greece; (ii) mutual dissemination; (iii) merge BioRural toolkit with tHERBN platform; (iv) taking care of ERBN community and create a thematic network on ERBN

Achieved: (i) workshop organised tHERBN Kick-off meeting Athens in collaboration (22nd January 2025); (ii) project leaders connected; (iii) undergoing the visualisation of toolkit as BioRural and tHERBN platform; (iv) agreement to manage and grow the ERBN community and create thematic network around it

3.3.2 Liaison with long term EU initiatives

Three principal long-term initiatives have been identified and approached by M36 by BioRural partners: **EU-FarmBook, modernAKIS and Tools4CAP**. EU-Farmbook and ModernAKIS started 2022 and will be ongoing till 2029. They are both long term initiatives with potential continuation after 2029. In the case of Tools4CAP, the framework is Dezember 2026, still covering whole lifetime of BioRural. Specifically, about them:

- EU-Farmbook covers 18 EU countries, to compile and facilitate practical knowledge for farmers and foresters in multilanguage environment. There is a high synergy for mutual benefits, as for example, BioRural can provide specific insights into small scale biobased solutions, and reversely, BioRural toolkit may be connected with EU-Farmbook (thus allowing to be better known and acknowledged).
- modernAKIS is empowering and structuring the AKIS system in 26 EU countries. Therefore, collaboration is a path to visualise ERBN and BioRural toolkit to potential users or participants like AKIS bodies or agricultural advisors.
- Tools4CAP works in 17 EU countries to support the design and monitoring of national CAP strategic plans. The creation of a networking platform and the connection with CAP key actors per country is a potential synergy to connect BioRural and the newly created ERBN

Nine synergies were found once these three projects were approached. Five synergies have been reported by BioRural partners at M36. Despite their small number, some of the synergies are particularly crucial, such as those with EU-Farmbook, because they have resulted in an agreement to connect the BioRural toolkit and EU-Farmbook, which is essential for the visualisation and recognition of the BioRural toolkit.

Table 15. Series of tables to track synergies with Long term EU Initiatives

Type of project	Short name / Timing	Focus area	Link	Leader	Keywords / Focus area
HORIZON EUROPE	EU-FarmBook (August 2022-July 2029)	#Ag, #For, #Aq, #BM, #BE	WEB	UNIVERSITEIT GENT	bioeconomy, digitalization, resources, platform, knowledge transfer

Project description:

EU-FarmBook, is a Horizon Europe project that is working at regional, national, and European level, to build a Digital Platform, gathering and sharing agriculture and forestry knowledge, based on a co-creation approach and built on EURAKNOS and EUREKA outputs. EU-FarmBook is the answer to real needs of farmers, foresters and advisors. The Horizon Europe project offers an interactive, multi-lingual meeting place for agriculture and forestry communities, giving access to trustworthy knowledge objects according to findable, accessible, interoperable, and reusable (FAIR) data principles. EU-FarmBook users can interact and explore innovative ways to solve their daily challenges.

Partner / status: AVEBIOM & CERTH / ongoing

Synergy planned: (i) Promotion of EU-Farmbook launch among RBA members and BioRural partners. (ii) Connect EU-Farmbook and BioRural toolkit; (iii) connect EU-Farmbook and

Achieved: (i) EU-Farmbook launch shared with RBA and BioRural partners; (ii) EU-Farmbook and ERBN being connected. Discussed distribution of materials in each platform and complementarity. Collaboration to merge contents through thERBN project

Type of project	Short name / Timing	Focus area	Link	Leader	Keywords / Focus area
HORIZON EUROPE	modernAKIS (Sept 2022-Aug 2029)	#Hor	WEB	LFI OSTERREICH	AKIS, support service, knowledge transfer

Project description:

modernAKIS, modernisation of Agriculture through more efficient and effective Agricultural Knowledge and Innovation Systems (AKIS), aims to improve AKIS actors' capacities to leverage individual, organizational and systemic resources needed for the transformation towards more coherent, effective, and efficient AKIS systems and the transition to a more sustainable management and use of natural resources in farming and forestry.

To this end it will build and foster a European network of at least 1.000 key AKIS actors, including AKIS coordination bodies, from all EU MS, who will act as linchpins in the transformation of the AKIS systems towards a more effective governance and the modernization of the European agri-food sector.

Partner / country / status: AVEBIOM / Spain / ongoing

Synergy planned: discussed about synergies between ERBN and modernAKIS. (i) Agreed to transfer to modernAKIS partners and community to join ERBN once set-up and in operation. (ii) Potential key actors for ERBN management; (iii) collaborate in national actions of each project

Achieved: (i) AVEBIOM registered in AKIS Connect platform; agreed further visualization of ERBN in Spain once structure consolidated and linked to each national AKIS; (iii) AVEBIOM participated in workshop 28th Oct 2024 Modern AKIS in Spain.

Partner / country / status: CERTH /AVEBIOM / EU / ongoing

Synergy planned: discussed about synergies between ERBN and modernAKIS. (i) Agreed to transfer to modernAKIS partners and community to join ERBN once set-up and in operation. (ii) Potential key actors for ERBN management; (iii) collaborate in national actions of each project

Achieved: (i) AVEBIOM and other BioRural partners registered in AKIS Connect platform; agreed further visualization of ERBN to all Member states once structure consolidated and linked to each national AKIS;

Type of project	Short name / Timing	Focus area	Link	Leader	Keywords / Focus area
HORIZON EUROPE	Tools4CAP (Jan 2023-Dez 2026)	#Hor	WEB	ECORYS BRUSSELS NV	CAP Strategic Plan, policy modelling, participatory approach

Project description:

Tools4CAP, which stands for Innovative Toolbox empowering effective CAP governance towards EU ambitions, is a Coordination and Support Action in Horizon Europe (2023-2026) coordinated by Ecorys, gathering 21 partner organisations. The project aims to support the design and monitoring of the national Common Agricultural Policy (CAP) Strategic Plans (SPs) 2023-2027 and lay the foundations for sound preparation of Post-2027 Strategic Plans through a bottom-up adaptation of innovative methods and tools. Tools4CAP ambition is to provide end users with suitable tools for a more evidence-based policy design, ultimately improving capabilities to design next-generation Strategic Plans and to perform monitoring tasks.

Partner / country / status: UL / Slovenia / established contact

Synergy planned: no synergy achieved as being BioRural quite vertical topic on circularity, not in line with main aim of Tools4CAP

Achieved: no synergy achieved so far

3.3.3 Liaison with EU funded projects

EU funded projects have been identified by BioRural partners to establish individual bilateral collaborations, mainly at country level. The evolution through the project is as follows:

- **At M12** partners reported a total of **16 EU projects**, for which a total of 11 agreed upon collaboration, and 6 had started the discussions to collaborate.
- **At M24** **24 projects** had been approached, 48 potential synergies discussed and 29 collaborations becoming effective.
- **At M36 partners have identified 35 EU projects** to establish synergies with. This adds 11 EU projects more than those identified at month M24. By end of project, BioRural partners have identified and **discussed** at least **63 individual lines of collaboration**, leading to 52 effective collaborations.

As seen, the leverage of synergies with EU-Funded initiatives has increased in the last period of the project. Table 16 lists the initiatives in detail, along with the synergies that were found and realised.

Table 16. Series of tables to track synergies with EU funded projects

Type of project	Short name / Timing	Focus area	Link	Leader	Keywords / Focus area
Interreg-CE	BIOECO-UP at a glance (04.2023-03.2026)	#Ag, #For, #Aq, #BM	WEB	Ministry of Agriculture Hungary	Small scale, biobased, solutions, rural

The bioeconomy concept seeks to replace fossil resources with renewable raw materials in as many areas and applications as possible. The BIOECO-UP project widely establishes this concept across central Europe. The partners will design new circular value chains for the bioeconomy and change consumer behaviour. They will also support the policy level to push ahead with the transformation.

Partner / country / status: UL / Slovenia / participating as Partner

Synergy planned: (i) co-organisation of events and workshops, (ii) common final event, (iii) mutual support in dissemination

Achieved: (i) participation in three national multi-actor innovation workshops, (iii) dissemination of project results and actions

Type of project	Short name / Timing	Focus area	Link	Leader	Keywords / Focus area
HORIZON 2020	BRANCHES (January 2020-Dec 2023)	#Ag, #For, #Aq, #BM, #BE	WEB	LUKE Natural Resources Institute Finland	bioeconomy, knowledge transfer, thematic networks

Project description:

BRANCHES aims to promote the implementation of new cost-effective technologies; mobilize more biomass and create innovative business opportunities in rural areas by improving and strengthening the links between bioeconomy practice and science. The project will ensure communication through the two-way flow of information for the transfer of ideas and technologies between scientists and professionals from agriculture and forestry in rural areas. The valuable knowledge produced by research and development should always be shared far beyond the scientific community.

BRANCHES will integrate selected knowledge on forest and agricultural biomass supply chains with available innovative technologies and best practice cases for bioeconomy solutions with bioenergy conversion systems in a wider bioeconomy context. Five national thematic networks launched by BRANCHES in Germany, Poland, Finland, Italy and Spain will engage science and practitioners.

Partner / country / status: AVEBIOM / Spain / agreed, started

Synergy planned: (i) presentation in mutual events. (ii) Potential invitation to INTERCAMBIOM national network to join ERBN. (iii) Participation in BRANCHES final event.

Achieved: (i) BioRural presentation 26th April 2023 at BRANCHES local workshop and visit to success case Alcarrás Bioproductors; (ii) two communication to the 400 members of INTERCAMBIOM (a. to announce BioRural Toolkit and ERBN; b. on SW EU Challenge); (iii) poster at BRANCHES final event Spain; (iii) presenting BioRural recommendations at BRANCHES final conference (Nov 2023, Rome)

Partner / country / status: CERTH / Greece&EU / discussed and finished

Synergy planned: (i) potential participation in RBA. (ii) Potential connection of the 5 NTNs created by BRANCHES with the ERBN and toolkit.

Achieved: Connections were offered. At the moment no further synergy achieved (BRANCHES project already finished Dez 2023).

Type of project	Short name / Timing	Focus area	Link	Leader	Keywords / Focus area
ERASMUS-KA2	COM (June 2022-May 2025)	#BE, #Agr		UPV	bio economy, organic waste, sustainable development, circular economy, digitalization, green skills

Project description:

COM (Circular Organic Management) aims to develop and deliver a series of materials and tools for secondary school teachers to incorporate the circular economy into their classrooms, and more specifically on issues around organic waste management. Its goal is to support the behavioral change in schools around the food and organic waste, by engaging a set of actors, including teachers, students, schools, universities and social partners from Spain, Italy, Greece, Romania, Slovenia and Turkey.

Partner / country / status: ICO / Greece / established synergy

Synergy planned: Material developed in COM will be uploaded in BioRural Toolkit.

Achieved: performed

Type of project	Short name / Timing	Focus area	Link	Leader	Keywords / Focus area
Interreg VI B	ReNu2Cycle (March 2023-March 2027)	#Agr, #BM		IZES gGmbH	Bio-based, recycled fertiliser

Project description:

The aim of ReNu2Cycle is to implement recycling derived fertilizer (short RDFs) to the market and thereby reduce the dependency on conventional fertiliser, which are optimized for the fast release of nutrients, making them an attractive choice for farmers but also a threat to soil and ecosystem. To address the implementation of RDFs to the market, ReNu2Cycle develops policy recommendations at regional and European level and is also testing various RDFs on pot and field trials in several North-West European Countries. The integral part of ReNu2Cycle is to develop RDF business solutions and technologies for a market uptake.

Partner / country / status: IZES gGmbH / Germany / agreed

Synergy planned: Introduction of technologies and project results into toolkit.

Achieved: project into toolkit

Type of project	Short name / Timing	Focus area	Link	Leader	Keywords / Focus area
-----------------	---------------------	------------	------	--------	-----------------------

Interreg A	W.A.V.E. (proposal 2 step)	#BM	WEB	IZES gGmbH (Scientific)	Biomaterials, Forest Wood
-------------------	-------------------------------	-----	---------------------	----------------------------	---------------------------

Project description:

WaVE focuses on the improvement of regional and local policies to open up their possibilities for supporting the development of integrated adaptive reuses of water-linked cultural heritage sites in human settlements.

WaVE goal is to improve the overall support by the addressed policy instruments for integrated valorisation approaches of cultural heritage, to sparkle ideas for the creation of new projects aiming at integrated valorisation of water-linked cultural heritage, and to raise awareness for the subject at other cities and regions in Europe.

Partner / country / status: IZES gGmbH / Germany / proposal 2 step

Synergy planned: Introduction of technologies and project results into toolkit.

Achieved: no synergies achieved so far

Type of project	Short name / Timing	Focus area	Link	Leader	Keywords / Focus area
Horizon 2020	Go-Grass (2022-2025)	#Ag, #BE	WEB	ATB	Small scale, biobased, solutions, rural

Project description:

The GO-GRASS project is developing small-scale bio-based solutions to unlock the overlooked potential of grassland across Europe and create new business opportunities for rural areas. To develop cost-effective and circular business models exploiting the underused potential of grass resources, GO-GRASS partners will test a wide range of solutions in four promising regional demonstration sites located in The Netherlands, Sweden, Germany and Denmark.

Partner / country / status: AU/ Denmark / identified - ongoing

Synergy planned: (i) co-organisation of events and workshops. (ii) Support to project visualisation. (iii) Collaboration towards the Green Transition in Europe

Achieved: (i) Participation in national workshop on biomass. (iii) Results from Go-Grass provided input on exercises on innovation idea regarding protein extraction from biomass.

Type of project	Short name / Timing	Focus area	Link	Leader	Keywords / Focus area
Horizon Project	B-Resilient (September 2022 - September 2025)	#Ag, #BM	WEB	Wagralim	Bioeconomy, co-product, circular economy,

Project description:

The B-Resilient project aims to increase the use of available raw materials and the recovery of secondary flows into biobased ingredients. In particular, it will enable SMEs involved in the production and processing of food products to become more resilient by making optimum use of biomass.

Partner / country / status: Valorial / FRANCE / discussed.

Synergy planned: (i) Looking for bioeconomy promotion, engagement, identification of actors and dissemination

Achieved: first discussions took place, no synergy achieved so far

Type of project	Short name / Timing	Focus area	Link	Leader	Keywords / Focus area
Horizon Project	Blue Bio Cluster (September 2022 - September 2025)	#Aq	WEB	Submariner Network	Blue economy, blue bioeconomy, circular economy,

Partner / country / status: Valorial / FRANCE / discussed.

Synergy planned: (i) Looking for bioeconomy promotion, engagement, identification of actors and dissemination (ii) Co-organisation of events and workshops.

Achieved: first discussions took place, no synergy achieved so far

Type of project	Short name / Timing	Focus area	Link	Leader	Keywords / Focus area
Horizon Project	Hub4Food (January 2024- January 2027)	#Aq, #Ag	WEB	CLUSAGA (Cluster Alimentario de Galicia)	Marine resources, food products, SMEs, Innovation, RTO's

Project description:

The B-Resilient project aims to increase the use of available raw materials and the recovery of secondary flows into biobased ingredients. In particular, it will enable SMEs involved in the production and processing of food products to become more resilient by making optimum use of biomass.

Partner / country / status: Valorial / FRANCE / discussed.

Synergy planned: Co-organisation of workshop

Achieved: co-organization of a morning presentation of success stories and collaborative workshops on adding value to marine co-products.

Type of project	Short name / Timing	Focus area	Link	Leader	Keywords / Focus area
Intereg project	INdiGo (Sept 2022-Dec 2025)	#Aq, #BM	WEB	UBS University	Biodegradable plastics, marine environment, fishing gear

Project description:

The INdiGO project aims to develop the first fishing gear with a controlled lifespan that is biodegradable in the marine environment. It also aims to define a strategy for improving the recycling of end-of-life fishing gear and promoting the circular economy.

Partner / country / status: NaturePlast/ FRANCE / discussed

Synergy planned: (i) Share network and pool the effects. (ii) Some partners of this project will be asked to join the network.

Achieved: Discussions with the project's French partners to enable them to join the toolkit.

Type of project	Short name / Timing	Focus area	Link	Leader	Keywords / Focus area
ERASMUS +	SAGRE (June 2021-Nov 2023)	#Agr	WEB	Republic of Turkey - Ministry of Agriculture and Forestry -General Directorate of Agrarian Reform	*Precision agriculture *Circular economy *Sustainable agriculture

Project description:

SAGRE purposes two issues on farming and specifically on the crop and horticulture cultivation

- to enhance the precise and sustainable usage of chemical fertilizers
- to promote a shift to Circular Economy and increased usage of bio-fertilizers

SAGRE trains the trainers. SAGRE builds on the excellence of European agri-technology and directs its efforts on transferring knowledge and demonstrating feasible IT solutions to build capacity for the new profession of Smart Agri Expert. Smart Agri Experts will form a practice-oriented knowledge node between agri-tech forerunners, science community and agriculture stakeholders and farmers.

Partner / country / status: Green Growth Platform / North Macedonia/ finished

Synergy planned: (i) Participation in events and workshops; (ii) collaboration in field of precise agriculture.

Achieved: (i) Representatives of AgFutura Technologies (SAGRE project partner) took active participation in all of the national capacity building workshops (T3.2) and gave a presentation on their Remote Agriculture Monitoring and Advisory System (RAMAS) at the online knowledge exchange workshop on food and agriculture (T3.1).

Type of project	Short name / Timing	Focus area	Link	Leader	Keywords / Focus area
Horizon Europe	Locality (June 2023 – May 2026)	#Ag, #Aq, #BM	not yet established	NIVA	Algae, food, agriculture, aquaculture

Project description:

LOCALITY will implement local, innovative, and sustainable value chains, supporting the interaction of the algae value chain actors with relevant waste stream producing industries. Three regional ecosystems will be strategically developed in key regions considering strong and active business on which circularity and sustainability will be improved by the reutilization of wasted nutrients for algae cultivation. An integrative methodology involving R&D partners, industry, and SMEs will work in each market sector to develop innovative and sustainable algae-based products.

Partner / country / status: ALGEN / Slovenia / identified and agreed to participate in Webinar on Aquatic systems

Synergy planned: (i) co-operation at events and workshops. (ii) Collaboration in algae valorisation & possible business models establishment.

Achieved: (i) participation in BioRural webinar (Aquaculture) and presenting at national multi-actor innovation workshops ; (ii) policy issues in aquaculture researched in Locality and implemented in BioRural Policy briefs

Partner / country / status: Algen / SLOVENIA / ongoing

Synergy planned: Joining ERBN

Achieved: Locality coordinator joined ERBN

Type of project	Short name / Timing	Focus area	Link	Leader	Keywords / Focus area
Horizon Europe	CRONUS (Dec 2022 - Aug 2026)	#Aq, #Aq, #BM, #BE	WEB	NTUA	Bio-genic gases, CO2 valorisation, biofuels, sustainable

Project description:

Overall objective is to develop, assess and test 5 new integrated and sustainable technological solutions for highly efficient biogenic effluent gases capture, utilisation, and storage within the biofuels value chain. Functional prototype with algal ponds will capture CO2 from three processes, including anaerobic digestion, with the help of carbonic anhydrase, extracted from algae, cultivated on digestate.

Partner / country / status: Algen / SLOVENIA / ongoing

Synergy planned: (i) Cooperation on workshops, (ii) collaborating on potential solutions for rural areas; (iii) Joining ERBN

Achieved: (i) participation in two national multi-actor innovation workshops; (iii) Cronus coordinator joined ERBN

Type of project	Short name / Timing	Focus area	Link	Leader	Keywords / Focus area
Horizon Project	BIOEAST Initiative BOOST4BIOEAST (Jan 2024 - Dec 2026)	#For, #BM, #BE	WEB	OMKI	Bioeconomy strategy, research and innovation, rural development

Project description: The Central-Eastern European Initiative for Knowledge-based Agriculture, Aquaculture and Forestry in the Bioeconomy. It provides a common and shared strategic research and innovation framework for working towards sustainable bioeconomies of the Central and Eastern European countries. It is an open initiative started by the Visegrad Group Countries: Czech Republic, Hungary, Poland, Slovakia, and joined by Bulgaria, Romania, Slovenia, Croatia and Estonia.

The Boost4Bioeast consortium is composed of 30 partners from 17 EU countries (11 BIOEAST countries and Belgium, Finland, Germany, Ireland, Italy and Spain).

Partner / country / status: GEA / ROMANIA / ongoing

Synergy planned: (i) visualisation of mutual actions. (ii) Policy recommendations, advocacy. (iii) take part into ERBN

Achieved: (i) Boost4Bioeast Romanian partner and GEA jointly participated in May 2024 in a workshop organised by CEE2ACT on developing the bioeconomy roadmap for Romania, discussed project cooperation areas, (iii) Boost4Bioeast Romanian partners invited to join the ERBN. (i) participation on the Bioeast conference in Budapest (4-6 December 2024) and Bucharest (9-10 April 2025), including poster presentation.

Partner / country / status: LBTU / Latvia/ collaboration achieved

Synergy planned: (i) knowledge and insights generated in this project used in the BioRural project

Achieved: (i) knowledge and insights generated in this project used in the BioRural project

Type of project	Short name / Timing	Focus area	Link	Leader	Keywords / Focus area
Horizon Project	ROSEWOOD 4.0 (Gen 2020-Dec 2022)	#For	WEB	Steinbeis-Europa-Zentrum	Network for innovation in forestry

Project description:

Searching, listing and spreading best practices in the wood mobilization sector along with digitalization and innovation all over Europe. The second edition started 01.01.2020-01.01.2021. Created by the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation program.

Budget 2.047.901,25E under grant agreement No. 862681.

Partner / country / status: AIEL/ ITALY / finished

Synergy planned: (i) Connect with the existing network in order to get organizations to participate to the BioRural network.

Achieved: The coordinator of the network has been connected

Type of project	Short name / Timing	Focus area	Link	Leader	Keywords / Focus area
Alpine Space	Alps4GreenC (Sept 2022-Feb 2024)	#Agr/F; #For; #BE; #BM	WEB	Kemijski inštitut	Biochar production and wooden residues mapping and

Project description:

The Alps4GreenC project is focused on setting-the-scene for transnational utilization of biomass residues through investigation of biomass conversion opportunities in project partner countries and proposal of transnational biochar-based value chains. The framework includes mapping of stakeholders&resources, implementation of crowdsourcing campaign to collect biomass residues and raise awareness, testing and piloting of biochar and context&gap analysis of biomass conversion opportunities for green carbon supply.

Partner / country / status: AIEL / ITALY / Finished

Synergy planned: co-organisation of events and workshops.

Achieved: no synergies achieved so far

Partner / country / status: UL / Slovenia / Finished

Synergy planned: (i) co-organisation of events and workshops; (ii) take part into ERBN; (iii) mutual dissemination.

Achieved: (i) Participation in Alps4GreenC Final Event, (ii) Subscription to ERBN (NIC, National Institute of Chemistry) and (iii) promotion of BioRural events in Slovenia

Type of project	Short name / Timing	Focus area	Link	Leader	Keywords / Focus area
European Joint programme	EJP SOIL - EOM4SOIL (Nov 2021-Oct 2024)	#Ag, #For, #Aq, #BM	WEB	INRAE	Organic matter and soil management

Project description:

EOM4SOIL aims at proposing best management practices of external organic matter (EOM) pre-processing and application on soil to contribute to climate change mitigation and improve soil health. Representative farming systems in Europe (arable crops and vineyards) are selected, taking into account the diversity of pedoclimatic conditions. The net budget of soil C storage and greenhouse gas emission including the pre-process step and field application, is assessed as well as the multiple effects of EOM application on soils including contaminants are quantified. Innovative pre-processing are recommended to improve C budget and soil health. The best management practices are defined from scenarios of use assessed with a multicriteria simulation tool, parameterized from long-term experiments.

Partner / country / status: AIEL / ITALY / ongoing

Synergy planned: (i) co-organisation of events and workshops.

Synergy achieved: (i) co-organisation of three workshops (T3.2) were co-organized with CREA (EJP Soil Italian partner); additionally a 4th workshop by CREA with the methodology designed by BioRural, supported by AIEL (not included in the workshop activities as it was held after the deadline for BioRural).

Partner / country / status: IUNG /Poland / Ongoing

Synergy planned: (i) participation in a workshop organised in Task 3.1.

Synergy achieved: (i) Partners from EJP soil have presented their work at workshop organised within T3.1

Type of project	Short name / Timing	Focus area	Link	Leader	Keywords / Focus area
PRIMA Project	MEDACORNET (Jun 2023 - Jun 2026)	#Ag, #BM	WEB	LANDRATEC H	Innovative food products; Product valorisation; rural development

Project description:

The "MEDACORNET" project aims to boost adherence to the Mediterranean diet, through the development of new products based on acorns, as a historic Mediterranean superfood, while promoting the actors involved in its production and processing. The data generated will be used to define dietary guidelines/recommendations and strategies to promote the adoption of acorns as an ingredient in healthy and sustainable Mediterranean diets. In short, MEDACORNET aims to unlock the value chain of the acorn, an ancient traditional ingredient of Mediterranean cuisine produced by several native oak species, currently wasted. Based on the established trans-Mediterranean consortium, the project will produce results in complementary but diversified fields of action, aimed at valuing the acorns of our native forests.

Partner / country / status: CBE / Portugal / finished

Synergy planned: (i) Potential success story. (ii) Dissemination of results.

Achieved: (ii) Dissemination of the project through the Toolkit's Bioeconomy Inventory

Type of project	Short name / Timing	Focus area	Link	Leader	Keywords / Focus area
HE	genB (Nov 2022 - Apr 2025)	#Hor	WEB	APRE	Young people, teachers, education, awareness, bioeconomy, bio-based, co-creation

Project description:

genB "Preparing tomorrow's adults to assume their role in a circular and sustainable bioeconomy" aims to prepare children today to assume their role in the future circular and sustainable bioeconomy. In this context, the EU-funded GenB project will involve several other EU projects and initiatives. The project's overall objective is to inspire and encourage youth and future generations to be aware, sensitive and interested on environmental issues, sustainability and circularity. In cooperation with young people, parents and teachers, GenB will co-create resources like toolkits on bioeconomy and bio-based sectors. To maximise its impacts, GenB will widely engage society, create synergies with other initiatives and consolidate its education model.

Partner / country / status: AVEBIOM / EU / Finished

Synergy planned: (i) distribution of EU Challenge call; (ii) other potential synergies to be discussed

Achieved: (i) Distribution of EU Challenge (T3.3) in the SM channels followed by youths community (@biovoices).

Type of project	Short name / Timing	Focus area	Link	Leader	Keywords / Focus area
HE	BIOLOC (Oct 2022 – Sept 2025)	#Ag, #For, #Aq, #BM, #BE	https://bioloc.eu/	CEI	biobased, social innovation

Project description: developing resilient innovative biobased activities open to the contribution of socially disadvantaged or marginalized groups. It will deliver innovative and inclusive business models and drive the establishment of permanent public-private multistakeholder hubs to pioneer a social dialogue on innovative and inclusive circular bioeconomy as a leveraging factor for sustainable and resilient local communities.

Partner / country / status: GEA / Romania/ ongoing

Synergy planned: (i) Cooperation on workshops, (ii) collaborating on potential solutions for rural areas.

Achieved: (i) participation and promotion of each other's dissemination actions: Bioloc Romanian partner participated in a conference organized by GEA in October 2023

Type of project	Short name / Timing	Focus area	Link	Leader	Keywords / Focus area
I3	GREET-CE (Nov 2023 – Nov 2025)	#Ag,#BM, #BE	www.greetc.eu	KSENA	regenerative agriculture, eco-construction

Project description: The project focuses on the green transition in Central Europe, aiming to increase the capacity of regional innovation ecosystems, especially SMEs, in less developed Central European regions. The project focuses primarily on green transition within the bioeconomy sector. Key objectives include fostering bioeconomy investments, facilitating interoperation in EU value chains, and enhancing interactive training and education opportunities.

Partner / country / status: GEA / Romania/ agreed and ongoing

Synergy planned: (i) Cooperation on workshops, (ii) promoting innovative biobased start-ups

Achieved: (i) co-organized events (ii) promoted BioRural regional challenge workshops announcements in July 2024

Type of project	Short name / Timing	Focus area	Link	Leader	Keywords / Focus area
Interreg Europe	ORIGINN (Mar 2023 – May 2027)	#Ag	www.interregeurope.eu/originn	Government of Catalonia	agr-food, industrial innovation, rural areas

Project description: Economic and social transformation in rural areas through industrial innovation, emphasis in agri-food sector. The main goal is to enlarge and improve policy instruments in the involved territories (in EE, ES, IE, IT, RO, SE, SK) seeking to foster innovation-based industrial transition in rural areas, with an emphasis in the agri-food sector. Under this topic, ORIGINN puts special attention to digitalisation, industrial sustainability, social innovation, and soft innovation measures

Partner / country / status: GEA / Romania/ ongoing

Synergy planned: (i) Cooperation on workshops, (ii) joint dissemination

Achieved: (i) GEA participated on a workshop organized by OriginN Romanian partner in June 2024.

Type of project	Short name / Timing	Focus area	Link	Leader	Keywords / Focus area
LIFE	ConnectHeat (Oct 2022 – Sept 2025)	#BE	WEB	Ambiente Italia S.R.L. (Italy)	district heating, renewable, renewable heat communities

Project description:

ConnectHeat is the first European initiative to develop heating and cooling communities in Europe, implementing seven real pilot cases in different EU countries and putting public authorities and citizens at the heart of energy transitions.

Partner / country / status: AIEL / Italy / participating

Synergy achieved: The partner participated to focus group for the development of renewable heating and cooling communities and the Biorural toolkit was disseminated between the partners.

Type of project	Short name / Timing	Focus area	Link	Leader	Keywords / Focus area
-----------------	---------------------	------------	------	--------	-----------------------

Interreg	Clim4Cast (03.2023 – 02.2026)	#Ag,	WEB	CZECHGlobe	drought, weather,
<p>Project description: The aim is to increase resilience of the CE region to impacts of drought, heatwaves, fire weather (DHF), and their combined effects, by upgrading existing national tools that mostly ONLY monitor DHF status. The tools will be upgraded by jointly developed DHF forecasts connected to specific action plans on the forecast use and strategy for building DHF-climate change awareness. The project will improve regions' best practices across 7 involved countries but can be scaled up to the entire CE.</p> <p>Partner / country / status: IUNG / Poland/ collaboration agreed</p> <p>Synergy planned: (i) participation in workshops and events</p> <p>Achieved: (i) Partners from Clim4Cast have presented their work at workshop organised within T3.1</p>					

Type of project	Short name / Timing	Focus area	Link	Leader	Keywords / Focus area
Interreg Baltic Sea Region	BioBoosters (01.2023 – 12.2025)	#Agr,#Hor	WEB	JAMK University of Applied Sciences (Finland)	Circular economy, climate-neutral society
<p>Project description: The project BioBoosters brings together bio-based businesses in rural areas to share the know-how in circular production, and trigger green business opportunities. BioBoosters Hackathon is connecting the bioeconomy innovation ecosystems of 9 regions across the Baltic Sea Region. By implementing the open innovation process in inter-regional co-operation, we can facilitate cross-sectoral knowledge transfer as well as connect SMEs, start-ups, and research groups with companies in an international context.</p> <p>Partner / country / status: IUNG / Poland/ collaboration agreed</p> <p>Synergy planned: (i) registration to BioRural toolkit</p> <p>Achieved: (i) registration to BioRural toolkit, upload of material</p>					

Type of project	Short name / Timing	Focus area	Link	Leader	Keywords / Focus area
LIFE project	OrgBalt (08.2019 – 08.2023)	#For	WEB	LVMI "Silava"	climate change, organic soils
<p>Project description: The aim of the project is to demonstrate climate change mitigation measures through the management of fertile organic soils in agricultural and forest lands in the temperate climate zone to reduce greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions and contribute to the achievement of the EU's common and national climate targets in the post-2020 commitment period.</p> <p>Partner / country / status: LBTU / Latvia/ collaboration achieved</p> <p>Synergy planned: (i) knowledge and insights generated in this project used in the BioRural project</p> <p>Achieved: (i) knowledge and insights generated in this project used in the BioRural project</p>					

Type of project	Short name / Timing	Focus area	Link	Leader	Keywords / Focus area
Horizon Europe	BioMonitoring (06.2018 – 05.2022)	#Ag	WEB	Wageningen University and Research	bioeconomy, monitoring
<p>Project description: BioMonitor addresses the information gap in bioeconomy research by re-structuring its existing data and modelling framework. The ultimate goal of the project is to get a clearer picture of how bioeconomy affects our lives.</p> <p>Partner / country / status: LBTU / Latvia/ collaboration achieved</p> <p>Synergy planned: (i) knowledge and insights generated in this project used in the BioRural project</p> <p>Achieved: (i) knowledge and insights generated in this project used in the BioRural project</p>					

Type of project	Short name / Timing	Focus area	Link	Leader	Keywords / Focus area
Horizon Europe	BIOEASTsUP (10.2019 – 09.2022)	#Ag	WEB	INSTYTUT UPRAWY NAWOZENIA I GLEBOZNAWSTWA, PANSTWOWY INSTYTUT BADAWCZY	circular bioeconomy, macro-regional cooperation
<p>Project description: The overall objective of the BIOEASTsUP project is to support the BIOEAST initiative in implementing its Vision 2030 and Action Plan 11 for the transition to a bioeconomy in Central and Eastern Europe (CEE).</p>					

The BIOEAST initiative will be supported by engaging relevant stakeholders, placing a sustainable circular bioeconomy on the agenda of Central and Eastern European governments, improving macro-regional cooperation formats with downstream and upstream agri-food sectors, and supporting the development of national bioeconomy strategies.

Partner / country / status: LBTU / Latvia/ collaboration achieved

Synergy planned: (i) knowledge and insights generated in this project used in the BioRural project

Achieved: (i) knowledge and insights generated in this project used in the BioRural project

Type of project	Short name / Timing	Focus area	Link	Leader	Keywords / Focus area
Horizon Europe	NENUPHAR (11.2023 – 04.2027)	#BM	WEB	Fundacion Circe Centro de Investigacion de Recursos y Consumos Energeticos	waste streams, innovations

Project description: The project focuses on three waste streams in the EU: manure, sewage sludge and dairy wastewater. It introduces four key innovations, including a methodology for estimating N/P emissions, new governance models, economic and financial incentives, and enabling technologies.

Partner / country / status: LBTU / Latvia/ collaboration achieved

Synergy planned: (i) knowledge and insights generated in this project used in the BioRural project

Achieved: (i) knowledge and insights generated in this project used in the BioRural project

Type of project	Short name / Timing	Focus area	Link	Leader	Keywords / Focus area
Horizon Europe	NATALIE (09.2023 – 08.2028)	#Ag, #For	-	Office International De L'eau	nature-based solutions, climate change

Project description: The NATALIE project aims to address the risks posed by climate change and advance the concepts of "ecosystem-based adaptation" in Europe through impact-driven Nature-Based Solutions (NBS). The project aligns with the recent IPCC AR6 WGII Report, emphasizing the importance of NBS for resilience to climate change.

Partner / country / status: LBTU / Latvia/ collaboration achieved

Synergy planned: (i) knowledge and insights generated in this project used in the BioRural project

Achieved: (i) knowledge and insights generated in this project used in the BioRural project

Type of project	Short name / Timing	Focus area	Link	Leader	Keywords / Focus area
	FuelPhoria (03.2023 – 02.2026)	#Aq, #Aq, #BM, #BE	WEB	CERTH	Biofuels

Project description: FUELPHORIA is an EU-funded Innovation Action project that aims to establish sustainable, competitive and secure value chains for advanced biofuels and renewable fuels of non-biological origin. It will set up and test a portfolio of nine complete value chains at four locations in Belgium, Greece and Spain

Partner / country / status: Algen / Slovenia/ ongoing

Synergy planned: (i) participation in workshops and events (ii) Partners of ERBN

Achieved: (i) Algen has presented project at BioRural webinar and national workshops (ii) FuelPhoria coordinator and one of the partners have joint ERBN

Type of project	Short name / Timing	Focus area	Link	Leader	Keywords / Focus area[IP1]
Horizon Europe	LegumES (01.2024 – 12.2027)	#Agr/F	WEB	Universidade Católica Portuguesa	legume cultivation, soil health, greenhouse gas reduction, rural development, circular bioeconomy

Project description: The LegumES project addresses key challenges in modern agriculture by promoting legumes as a sustainable solution to reduce synthetic fertilizer use, cut greenhouse gas emissions, and improve soil health. It enhances biodiversity, supports resilient food systems, and strengthens rural economies by fostering legume-based agriculture. Operating across diverse European regions, the project combines scientific research, field trials, and stakeholder engagement to assess and scale legume cultivation. Through collaboration with farmers, industry, and policymakers, LegumES ensures that environmental and socioeconomic data drive practical, regionally adaptable strategies. The project supports the circular bioeconomy by linking innovation with resource efficiency, soil regeneration, and low-input farming practices.

Partner / country / status: Green Growth Platform / North Macedonia/ Achieved

Synergy planned: (i) participation in workshops and events

Achieved: (i) Representatives from Green Growth Platform took active participation in a national workshop organized under the Legumes project.

Type of project	Short name / Timing	Focus area	Link	Leader	Keywords / Focus area
Horizon Europe	Rural BioReFarmeries 1 December 2024 - 30 November 2028	#BM, #Ag, #BE	LINK	MTU Ireland	Biorefined Grass Bio-based value chains Protein Extraction Supply Chain Optimisation

Project description:

From grasslands to green bio-based products — forging a robust farm-centred bioeconomy in Europe.

- Demonstrate an improved green biorefinery model that empowers farmers and enhances economic returns across Europe's rural regions.
- Develop small-scale, decentralized green biorefineries to convert locally sourced biomass into valuable products such as human-grade protein, bio-based packaging and clean energy.
- Support farmers on their journey towards a sustainable and resilient rural bioeconomy, where innovation meets tradition.

Partner / country / status: AU / Denmark / Partner

Synergy planned: (i) Knowledge sharing; (ii) activities related to ERBN

Achieved: (ii) Participation in events and workshops

Type of project	Short name / Timing	Focus area	Link	Leader	Keywords / Focus area
HE	RIBES (Mar 2024 – Feb 2027)	#Ag, #For, #Aq, #BM, #BE	LINK	INCE	biobased, entrepreneurship, business models

Project description: Regional Inclusive Biobased Entrepreneurship Solutions project will address the need to enhance the uptake of biobased innovations through pioneering governance and business models developed on the convergence of the circular bioeconomy, social innovation and rural development, thus contributing to the shift from a linear to a circular economy in 9 European regions lagging in innovation.

Partner / country / status: GEA / Romania/ ongoing

Synergy planned: (i) Cooperation on workshops, (ii) collaborating on potential solutions for rural areas.

Achieved: (i) participation and promotion of each other's dissemination actions, (i) GEA participated on a stakeholders' workshop in July 2025.

Type of project	Short name / Timing	Focus area	Link	Leader	Keywords / Focus area
HE	GreenMeUp (Aug 2022 – Jul 2025)	#BM, #BE	LINK	CRES	biomethane biogas upgrading policy measures

Project description: GREEN bioMEthane market Uptake project seeks to facilitate the wider market uptake of biomethane in the European energy and transport sectors by strengthening the market in countries with slow development rates.

Partner / country / status: GEA / Romania/ ongoing

Synergy planned: (i) Cooperation on workshops

Achieved: (i) participation and promotion of each other's dissemination actions, (i) GEA participated in 2 workshops regarding the establishment of a Danube Biomethane Hub (in June and December 2024).

3.3.4 Liaison with National funded projects

Partners have pointed out several national projects which, even not providing directly an EU dimension, also allow connections at country scale and the implementation of relevant synergies. The evolution is as follows:

- **At M12** partners identified a total of 6 national projects.
- **At M24** a total of 8 national projects had been identified, 17 potential lines of collaboration discussed, and a total of 9 synergies realised
- **At M36** the number of national projects remain in 8, still **17 potential synergies identified** and proceeding to leverage a total of **15 collaborations**

As can be observed, the synergies have increased during the project; some projects have realised several synergies (e.g., not simply co-organizing a workshop, but several workshops), while others have remained without collaboration. Table 17 below provides the description.

Table 17. Series of tables to track synergies with National funded projects

Type of project	Short name / Timing	Focus area	Link	Leader	Keywords / Focus area
Krajowa Sieć Obszarów Wiejskich +	KSOW+ 2023	#For, #BM, #BE	WEB	Centrum Doradztwa Rolniczego w Brwinowie, Oddział w Warszawie	Rural areas, agriculture

Project description:

The National Rural Network+ (NRN+) is a partnership network for information exchange and cooperation at the regional, national and international level between organizations and administration, representatives of the agricultural sector, advisors, scientists, entities involved in the implementation of innovations and other entities working for the development of agriculture, including increasing its competitiveness and improving the quality of life of inhabitants of rural areas and small towns.

Partner / country / status: IUNG / Poland / finished

Synergy planned: (i) mutual support in communication; (ii) participation in events, and workshops

Achieved: (i) communication about project achievement, share newsletter, (i) invitation to the NE open call t.3.3

Type of project	Short name / Timing	Focus area	Link	Leader	Keywords / Focus area
German Investing Funding	Bioenergy Initiative Niederbexbach (10/2023 – 10/2028)	#BE		IZES gGmbH (Scientific); Heating grid initiative Niederbexbach (Implementation)	Bioenergy, renewable energy

Project description:

The project was initiated through the citizen of the village Niederbexbach to generate an independence on fossil energy carriers and to develop bio-based solutions for energy supply.

Partner / country / status: IZES gGmbH / Germany / agreed

Synergy planned: Introduction of technologies and project results into toolkit.

Achieved: no synergies achieved so far

Type of project	Short name / Timing	Focus area	Link	Leader	Keywords / Focus area
National Project	GrassProtein (2022-2025)	#Ag, #BE	WEB	QPlan	Small scale, biobased, solutions, rural

Project description:

Increasing perennial forage crop protein yield and increasing biorefining efficiency in order to produce bio economically sustainable livestock feed

Partner / country / status: CERTH / GREECE / identified

Synergy planned: common final event (e.g)

Achieved: no synergies achieved so far

Type of project	Short name / Timing	Focus area	Link	Leader	Keywords / Focus area
EIP Operational Group project	EIP BlueGreen (May 2023 - April 2025)	#BM, #Ag, #Aq	Not yet established	Algen	Food, spirulina, Slovenian farms

Project description:

The project will evolve business model for growing spirulina in Slovenian farms, including logistics, processing and product development in rural areas.

Partner / country / status: Algen / SLOVENIA / finished

Synergy planned: (i) mutual actions and events. (ii) Joint development of business models for farmers growing algae (iii) participation in ERBN

Achieved: (i) participation in T3.2 national workshops ; (i) ; BioRural poster at the final EIP BlueGreen conference; (iii) Project coordinator joined ERBN

Type of project	Short name / Timing	Focus area	Link	Leader	Keywords / Focus area
EIP Operational Group project	InoBerry (2021-2023)	#Agr/F	WEB	VDU	High added value, bio-products, bio-business

Project description:

The main objective of the project is to combine the technological and commercialization processes in order to create products high added value products from the beneficial berry product with the help of an innovative management model.

Partner / country / status: VDU/ LITHUANIA/Finished

Synergy planned: (i) involvement into project activities, (ii) introduction of technologies and project results into toolkit.

Achieved: (i) participation in T3.2 national workshop and T1.2. surveys for end-users.

Type of project	Short name / Timing	Focus area	Link	Leader	Keywords / Focus area
FEDER funds (FITE – Teruel)	Agrifood-Te (Jan 2023-Dec 2024)	#Ag/F #For, #BM, #BE	WEB	CITA-Te (Centre for innovation in rural bioeconomy of Aragón)	Agriculture, forestry, food, bioenergy, biochemicals

Project description:

AgriFood-Te - Agrifood Knowledge and Innovation Network is financed by the Government of Aragon through the Teruel Investment Fund (FITE). It aims to create a network in the Teruel province, involving more than 100 agents to accelerate exchange scientific knowledge and transfer the results of research and innovation projects to them, and implementing "living-labs" or demonstrative and participatory pilot trials.

Partner / country / status: AVEBIOM / SPAIN / Finished

Synergy planned: (i) collaboration in workshops in T3.2; (ii) promotion of participations in EU Challenge

Achieved: (i) co-organising 3 workshops under T3.2 (inland and biobased) in Oct and Nov 2023; (ii) innovative solutions proposed in T3.2 workshops discussed to offer participants to present idea to EU challenge T3.3

Type of project	Short name / Timing	Focus area	Link	Leader	Keywords / Focus area
ARIS (CRP)	CircAgro (Oct 2022-Sept 2025)	#Ag/F, #For, #BM, #BE, #Aq	WEB	UL	Agriculture, circular technological concepts business models

Project description:

The general goal of the project is to demonstrate circular system solutions for the use of side streams of biomass from the primary agricultural production to set up convenient and accessible circular business models in tight cooperation and coordination with farms and industry associations involved in project activities. The project focus is on the development of system solutions that will connect agricultural holdings with other actors in supply chains into an innovative circular model for the valorization of biomass side streams on agricultural properties. The model will address the main challenges of the circular use of biomass streams and will have continuous dialogue with policy makers and decision-makers developed proposals for systemic cross-sectoral solution, with a high potential for reproducibility and scalability.

Partner / country / status: UL / Slovenia / Ongoing

Synergy planned: (i) collaboration in national workshops; (ii) promotion of participations in EU Challenge, (iii) success cases; (iv) mutual dissemination

Achieved: (i) co-organising 3 workshops under T3.2; (ii) innovative solutions presented in T3.3 Challenge, (iv) several dissemination of BioRural activities and events

Type of project	Short name / Timing	Focus area	Link	Leader	Keywords / Focus area
EIP Operational Group project	PreConAgri (2023-2025)	#Ag/F, #For, #BM, #BE, #Aq	WEB	CERTH	Agriculture, circular economy

Project description:

The PreConAgri research project is about the application of Conservation and Precision Agriculture techniques to reduce the impact of conventional agricultural practices on climate change through soil carbon sequestration with an increase in soil quality and production. Pilot applications are carried out in model fields of durum wheat, in two Greek regions with severe erosion problems, Krokos Kozanis and Nikaia Larissas. Pilot applications include the implementation of conservation agriculture methodologies, differential fertilization as well as controlled movement of machinery. The results will enhance field sustainability, maximizing benefits for the farmer and the environment

Partner / country / status: CERTH / Greece / Finished

Synergy planned: (i) joint dissemination activities (ii) promotion of participations in EU Challenge, (iii) success cases;

Achieved: no synergies achieved so far

3.4 Liaison with national and EU networks

A crucial component of BioRural's approach for achieving more significant outcomes and expanding the project's reach to a wider range of stakeholders has been liaising with networks and initiatives. When it comes to networks, the existing formal or informal collaboration arrangements may have a multiplicative influence on project actions. They might be focussing on topics like forestry, bioeconomy, biomaterials, etc., or they might be associated with industries and then related to pertinent target audiences like sectorial businesses, practitioners, advisers, or scientists.

The liaison is presented below, arranged as follows:

1. **CAP Networks:** both EU and National CAP networks are key networks for dissemination and transmission of novel biobased solutions. BioRural targets the national eco-systems for knowledge transfer, EIP-Agri operating groups, advising, etc., which are typically closely connected to CAP networks.
2. **EU Networks:** several identified by M12, though in general scoped to other areas of action with a limited synergy. Only those relevant are being described in this update D2.3
3. **National networks,** which may be actor- or theme-specific, could enable the expansion of a project's reach in terms of communication and distribution.

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY – NATIONAL and EU Networks

Liaison with **other EU and national networks** has proceeded in different level of involvement. In respect EU networks, several **referential sectorial or non-specific networks** linked to bioeconomy were identified. **Several synergies (totalling 5)** were leveraged, as with: Bioenergy Europe as speaker in BioRural online tutorials; the ICA - Association for European Life Science Universities to promote the EU Challenge; or ERIAFF - European Regions for Innovation in Agriculture, Food and Forestry to disseminate BioRural.

Eight bioeconomy networks in the EU have been identified. Before the initiative was completed, BioRural partners had completed **6 separate collaborations**. Some examples are the Community of Practice for Bioeconomy Education in Europe (ICA-CoP Bio-Edu), Biorefine Cluster Europe, ERDN - European Rural Development Network and the CIGR Bioeconomy Network. Notwithstanding these collaborations were in general weaker than with EU and National projects or national Networks, where the mutual interests were found to be stronger and easier to realise.

National networks, either related to bioeconomy, or on specific bioeconomy topics, have revealed to be quite effective and synergistic to trigger collaborations. BioRural partners have identified in the 14 BioRural countries a total of **24 relevant national networks throughout the project lifetime**. The approach has led to **identify up to 40 potential synergies**. A total of **34 individual collaborations** have been leveraged.

3.4.1 EU CAP Network and National CAP Networks

The connection of BioRural with CAP Networks at national level is relevant and strategic. During the project's duration, partners have contacted both national and EU CAP networks. At M24 the EU CAP network has already

contacted and object of short collaboration with purpose of T1.2. Project news have been released through EU CAP Network webpage.

In regard the **National CAP Networks**, 9 of them were contacted by M12. By end of project, **11 out of the 14 BioRural countries have been contacted**. Several synergies took place to disseminate BioRural actions like workshops, through their channels. As well several partners maintain a regular contact, thus allowing mutual transfer of info, more than specific synergies. In terms of individual **collaborations**, **8 have been reported by partners in total**. The detail can be consulted in Table 18.

Table 18. Series of tables to track synergies with EU and national CAP Networks

Country level	Name	Managed by	LINK	Contact performed / Synergy established
EU	EU CAP Network	European Commission DG AGRI	WEB	BioRural partners: Several contacts. Published BioRural news in EU CAP Network webpage. VDU: participated in experts surveys T1.2
ES	Spanish CAP Network keeps the National Rural Network name and website	Ministry of Agric. Fisheries and Food (Spain)	WEB	AVEBIOM: contact to present briefly BioRural. Contact to find synergies in workshops and with new agrarian advisors network. Achieved: dissemination of T3.2 workshops to CAP Network in the agenda of events (Oct & Nov 2024). New encounter Oct 2024 to explain BioRural.
IT	MASAF – National rural network name and website	Ministry of Agric. Food and Forests	WEB	AIEL: contacted MASAF with purpose of finding synergies.
PT	Portuguese CAP Network keeps the National Rural Network name and website	General Directorate of Agriculture and Rural Development (DGADR)	WEB	CBE: contact to present briefly BioRural.
PL	National Network for Rural Development (Krajowej Sieci Obszarów Wiejskich +)	Krajowa Sieć Obszarów Wiejskich	WEB	IUNG: contacted ERDN with purpose of finding Synergies. Invitation to participate in the workshops and open call
LV	National Rural Network	Latvijas Lauku konsultāciju un izglītības centrs	WEB	LBTU: constant cooperation on many topics Achieved: participation in all T3.1. and T3.2. workshops.
LT	National Rural Network	Ministry of the Agriculture of the Republic of Lithuania	WEB	VMU: contacted national NRN with purpose of finding synergies
DK	The Danish Agricultural Agency	Ministry of Food, Agriculture and Fisheries of Denmark	WEB 1 WEB 2	AU: continuously contact as part of public consultancy assignments for the ministry related to the new CAP
DE	DVS Netzwerk Ländliche Räume	Federal Office of Agriculture and Food	WEB	IZES No contact with purpose of synergy
NL	Netwerk Platteland	Ministry of Agric. Fisheries and Food (Netherlands)	WEB	DELPHY No contact with purpose of synergy
FR	French rural network	ANCT, RDF, French Ministry of Agriculture and Food Sovereignty	WEB	VALORIAL already contacted: Achieved: Valorial: contact to present BioRural and strengthen synergies
GR	Greek National CAP	Ministry of Rural Development and Food	WEB	CERTH / FSH No contact with purpose of synergy
SL	CAP Network Slovenia	Slovenian Ministry of Agriculture, Forestry & Food	WEB	UL Contacted
RO	National Rural Development Network Romania	Ministry of Agriculture and Rural Development	WEB	GEA: contact to present briefly BioRural and to find synergies in workshops.

				Achieved: participation in one of the T3.2 workshops in #Ag/F
NMK	Ministry of Agriculture, Forestry and Water Economy of the Republic of North Macedonia	Government of the Republic of North Macedonia	WEB	GGP , contact performed Achieved: The Ministry of Agriculture, Forestry and Water Economy is part of the ENRB as one of the country's key stakeholders in the rural bio-economy. Local representatives of this institution took active participation in all of the national capacity building workshops.

3.4.2 Liaison with EU relevant networks

Sectoral clusters and EU-level organisations are important players that may help BioRural and communicate its goals, initiatives, and outcomes to numerous national organisations as well as to individual stakeholders across several countries. They may be centred in the private sector, industry-driven, or public or private networks for knowledge transfer and collaboration. They are also pertinent to the possible multiplicative effects of project actions. At M36 a total of **5 collaborations have been achieved**; the status of connection with such networks is as presented in Table 19.

Table 19. Series of tables to track synergies with EU sectorial clusters and organisations

ACRONYM	Name / Description	LINK	Contact performed / Synergy established
COPA-COGECA	Farmers and cooperatives EU organisation	WEB	Partner: --- Achieved: ---
Bioenergy Europe (BE)	European association to promote sustainable bioenergy market	WEB	UL & UC contacted and agreed. Achieved: participation into online tutorial T3.1 on bioenergy March 2024. Dissemination of BioRural tutorial to BE members, BE newsletter and social media
ICA	Association for European Life Science Universities	WEB	VDU & AVEBIOM: contacted and agreed Achieved: dissemination of BioRural webinars (T3.1) and EU Challenge Call (T3.3) the EU Challenge through ICA members
ERIAFF	European Regions for Innovation in Agriculture, Food and Forestry	WEB	Valorial: contacted Achieved: participation into 10 th annual conference in June 2024. Dissemination of BioRural project with participants
CBE-JU	Circular Bio-Based Europe	WEB	AVEBIOM: contacted Spanish members of CBE-JU working group on primary sector Achieved: discussion to participate and to transfer invitation to key actors identified by BioRural

Additionally to sectorial organisations or theme specific networks, **other relevant networks dealing with bioeconomy** were identified by BioRural partners through the project lifetime. Several of them have been contacted, as exposed below in Table 20. The effectiveness of achieving synergies has been lower than that of EU projects. A number of factors include the various network scopes, governance, and the time allotted by coordinating bodies. It total **6 distinct synergies were established**.

Table 20. Series of tables to track synergies with EU bioeconomy networks

Name / WEB	Description	Contact performed / Synergy established
EPRI European Platform for Rural Innovation / WEB	Open and independent virtual innovation hub to boost bottom up rural development and community-led innovation in rural areas from across the EU.	AVEBIOM: contacted but not active response Achieved: no collaborations achieved so far

European Bioeconomy Network / WEB	Proactive alliance of 109 EU funded projects and initiatives dealing with Bioeconomy promotion	Partner: --- Achieved: no collaborations achieved so far. To be achieved through RBA and follow-up projects structuring ERBN community
European Bioeconomy University / WEB	Alliance of the six leading European universities in this field AgroParisTech, Uni Bologna, Eastern Finland, Hohenheim, BOKU, Wageningen	Partner: --- Achieved: no collaborations achieved so far
Community of Practice for Bioeconomy Education in Europe (ICA-CoP Bio-Edu) / WEB	Committee of the Board of the Association for European Life Science Universities (ICA), to enhance the quality, offer and diversity of education for the sustainable circular bioeconomy in Europe.	AVEBIOM: contacted and discussed. Achieved: invited to distribute info on T3.1 online tutorials (Nov 2023); invited to participate in T3.3 EU Challenge AVEBIOM/VDU: contacted and discussed. Achieved: widespread T3.3 EU Challenge call to ICA members to reach lecturers and students.
European Bioeconomy Alliance / WEB	Informal alliance of leading European organisations active in the bioeconomy. BIC, CEFS, CEPF, CEPI, COPA-COGECA, ePURE, EuropaBio, EUBP, FEDIOL, FTP, PFP, Starch Europe	AVEBIOM: first contact Achieved: first contact through ePURE. No collaborations achieved so far
Biorefine Cluster Europe / WEB	The Biorefine Cluster Europe interconnects projects and people within the domain of biobased resource recovery, striving to contribute to a more sustainable resource management.	AVEBIOM: contacted and discussed. Achieved: motivated meeting with CERTH to find synergies RBA and BioRural with Biorefine. Potential learning of their value proposition to preserve BioRural toolkit
ERDN - European Rural Development Network / WEB	It integrates efforts and competences of various EU research institutions for transformation of rural areas, in particular farming. It aims to build a EU Research Area for agriculture and rural development.	AVEBIOM: contacted and discussed. Achieved: widespread T3.3 EU Challenge call to ERDN members, principally scientists and lecturers who could trigger new applications with students. IUNG: constant contact and sharing information about project Achieved: ERDN presentation at workshop organised in T3.1, acceptance to participate in their conference sept 2024
CIGR Bioeconomy Network WEB	Create a network for Agricultural Biosystems Engineering professionals and related disciplines to collaborate to develop and disseminate useful knowledge and technology related to circular bioeconomy that leads to improved quality of life of all in a sustainable and socially responsible manner.	AU: Member of network Achieved: Participation in regular meetings.

3.4.3 Liaison with National networks

National networks have been identified already by partners by M12 in their national strategies (see in D2.1 annex of national plans). The evolution through the project is as follows:

- **At M12** partners reported a total of **16 national networks as being relevant** for project implementation at country level. The initial discussion of **synergies with 8 of them lead to 3 agreements** for collaboration.
- **At M24**, as described in D2.2, partners have identified 5 more, totalling **21 national networks**. A total of **23 synergies** identified, achieving **20 individual collaborations**.
- **At M36**, partners have identified 3 more, totalling **24 national networks**. A total of **40 synergies** have been identified, reaching a realization of **34 of them**.

Table 21. Series of tables to track synergies with National networks

Country level	Short name	Managed by	Link	Keywords / Focus area
Spain (National)	INtercamBIOM	AVEBIOM, CIRCE	WEB	Biomass resources, bioenergy, bioproducts
Network description: INtercamBIOM network is a National Thematic Network through which participants can easily and directly keep up to date with INNOVATIVE PRACTICES that are already being applied in the field of biomass supply, bioenergy and value-added				

uses. [INTERCAMBIOM](#) has been implemented in the framework of the [BRANCHES](#) Horizon 2020 project (Grant Agreement no. 101000375).

Partner / country / status: AVEBIOM / SPAIN / agreed

Synergy planned: (i) mutual transfer of case studies and success cases. (ii) Invitation to form part of BioRural

Achieved: (i) two success cases of INTERCAMBIOM adapted and uploaded into BioRural; (i) agreed to disseminate T2.3 & T2.4 success cases into INTERCAMBIOM; (ii) communication to INTERCAMBIOM network about ERBN and subscription

Country level	Short name	Managed by	Link	Keywords / Focus area
Lithuania (Sub-national)	AKIS Cluster	VDU	WEB	Knowledge transfer, partnerships, agriculture

Network description:

It is an ecosystem of advanced organizations gathered on a voluntary initiative, the operation of which is based on coordinated, partnership and networked knowledge flows between individuals, organizations and institutions that create and implement knowledge and innovations for agriculture and related sectors in order to achieve progress, sustainability and competitiveness in the sector.

Partner / country / status: VDU/ Lithuania/ agreed

Synergy planned: (i) continuous communication. (ii) potential collaboration in workshops and events; (iii) collaboration in T1.2 surveys

Achieved: (ii) participation in T3.2 national workshop and (iii) T1.2. surveys for end-users.

Country level	Short name	Managed by	Link	Keywords / Focus area
Poland (National)	Agroekoton Association	Agroekoton	WEB	Agriculture, Horticulture,

Network description:

Organisation focuses on the intersections between different agriculture-related communities, connecting scientists, growers, consumers, local governments, industry organisations, and many others. We aim to facilitate the exchange of ideas and to create real value, both for those communities and for the environment. AGROEKOTON is a place for creating new ideas and adapting them for use in agriculture, according to European Union strategies.. Our core values are commitment, cooperation, and innovation.

Partner / country / status: IUNG / Poland

Synergy planned: participation in events, and workshops

Achieved: ongoing communication, participation in Conference co-organised by AGROECOTON [IBO SUMMIT 2023](#)

Poland (Sub-national)	LODR	LODR	WEB	Agriculture, food, bioenergy,
-----------------------	------	------	---------------------	-------------------------------

Network description:

Deals with consulting in the field of agriculture, rural development, agricultural markets and rural households, aimed at improving the level of income from agriculture and improving the market competitiveness of farms, supporting sustainable development of rural areas and raising the level of professional qualifications of farmers and other rural residents.

Partner / country / status: IUNG / Poland

Synergy planned: (i) collaboration in workshops; (ii) collaboration in T1.2 surveys; (iii) mutual dissemination; (iv) become part of ERBN

Achieved: (i) continued communication, (iii) promotion of workshops organised by BioRural between farmer and advisors; (iv) Registered in ERBN.

Country level	Short name	Managed by	Link	Keywords / Focus area
Germany (Sub-national)	Biosphärenzweckverband	Administration for organisation of biosphere reserve	WEB	Agriculture, forestry, food, bioenergy, biomaterials, local producer, sustainability

Network description:

Network of rural bioeconomic actors, local producer of bio-based (nutrition) products and biomaterials. Principle: Think global, act local. Regional awareness for global environmental protection.

Partner / country / status: IZES / Germany / ongoing

Synergy planned: collaboration in workshops

Achieved: no synergies achieved so far

Country level	Short name	Managed by	Link	Keywords / Focus area
Danish	Food & Bio Cluster	Governing Body	WEB	Agriculture, forestry, food, bioenergy, biochemicals

Network description:

Denmark's national cluster organisation for the Danish food and bioresource industry. It is a unifying platform for innovation and growth – for Danish and international companies and knowledge institutions. Food & Bio Cluster Denmark exists to strengthen knowledge-based innovation and collaboration between companies and knowledge institutions across the food and bioresources value chain. We are the gateway to networking, the development of new business ideas and funding opportunities. Food & Bio Cluster Denmark has over 300 Danish and international members, including startups, established companies, knowledge institutions, municipals, regional authorities and other public institutions.

Partner / country / status: AU / Denmark / identified

Synergy planned: (i) collaboration in workshops

Achieved: (i) Co-organizer of two out of three national workshops (T3.3) in Denmark. (i) Provided input for innovation ideas discussed at the workshops.

Danish	CBIO (Aarhus University Centre for Circular Bioeconomy)	Governing Body	WEB	Agriculture, forestry, food, bioenergy, biochemicals
--------	---	----------------	---------------------	--

Network description:

CBIO activities include research within the entire production chain ranging from cultivating and procuring biomasses, logistics, management, refining, product development and tests, recirculation, impact on nature and environment as well as research in relation to society and economy. In addition, more basic research activities are carried out, e.g. in relation to the understanding of biomass conversion at molecular level, supported by advanced chemical analyses.

Partner / country / status: AU / Denmark / identified

Synergy planned: (i) collaboration in workshops and other dissemination activities, building networks, etc.

Achieved: (i) Participated in national workshop in Denmark. (i) Provided input for the innovation idea on protein extraction discussed in the workshop.

Country level	Short name	Managed by	Link	Keywords / Focus area
The Netherlands (National)	Building Balance	Network governing body	WEB	Biobased solution, construction industry

Network description:

Building Balance aims to boost the bioeconomy through the development of new value chains around sustainable construction materials.

Partner / country / status: Delphy / The Netherlands / agreed

Synergy planned: (i) mutual transfer of case studies and success cases. (ii) Visualisation of mutual actions. (iii) Potential workshop on inland resources.

Achieved: (iii) Participated in national workshop in the Netherlands. (ii) Delphy participates in various consultation groups within Building Balance to provide expert advice

Country level	Short name	Managed by	Link	Keywords / Focus area
France (regional)	CIVAM network	CIVAM	WEB	Agriculture, food, Biomass resources

Network description:

Driven by strong values of humanism and cooperation, the CIVAM network brings together farmers, association leaders and citizens in Normandy who want to support the development of sustainable farming and food systems and an environmental approach to behaviour.

Partner / country / status: NaturePlast/ FRANCE/ identified

Synergy planned: Share network and pool the effects.

Achieved: Initial discussions were held with members of this network to promote BioRural and present the toolkit.

France (regional)	Pays de la Loire Hub for Bioeconomy	Pays de la Loire region	WEB	Biomass resources and circular economy
-------------------	-------------------------------------	-------------------------	---------------------	--

Network description:

The aim of the Bioeconomy Hub is to create a collective dynamic in Pays de la Loire that will enable the emergence of European projects. Its aim is to take greater account of the interests of the region's players in the circular bioeconomy value chain.

Partner / country / status: Valorial / FRANCE/ agreed
Synergy planned: co-organisation of events and workshops.
Achieved: Agreement to disseminate BioRural events and actions

France (regional)	NFA Normandie Filière Algues	Normandie	Web	Seaweed, algoculture and creation of
--------------------------	------------------------------	-----------	---------------------	--------------------------------------

Network description:

Bringing together seaweed stakeholders in Normandy to structure and develop the development of seaweed resources

Partner / country / status: Valorial / FRANCE/ contacted

Synergy planned: Participation in a workshop

Achieved: NFA's participation in a workshop organized by BioRural and the European Hub4Food project in June 2025

France (regional)	Réseau NOE Bretagne	Brittany	WEB	Research and innovation
--------------------------	---------------------	----------	---------------------	-------------------------

Network description:

Since 2008, the Noé Bretagne network has brought together the main academic and socio-economic players in Brittany involved in research and innovation.

Partner / country / status: Valorial / FRANCE/ agreed

Synergy planned: mutual dissemination

Achieved: assistance for implementation of action and dissemination at regional level.

Country level	Short name	Managed by	Link	Keywords / Focus area
---------------	------------	------------	------	-----------------------

Romania (National)	Local Action Groups for Fisheries – FLAGS	FLAG	WEB	Fishery
---------------------------	---	------	-----	---------

Network description: Romanian National Fisheries Network, to support Local Action Groups in fishing areas (FLAGS) in their efforts to contribute to the sustainable development of fishing areas included in the Local Development Strategies. The National Fisheries Network plays an important role in the connection and cooperation of FLAGS, all actors and authorities involved in the development of the fisheries sector. The National Fishing Network also participates in geographical and thematic groups for the development of activities, the promotion of more extensive cooperation, the promotion of technical exchange and dialogue between networks.

Partner / country / status: GEA / ROMANIA / identified

Synergy planned: collaboration in workshops

Achieved: collaborated with FLAG Galati branch in organising a workshop on aquaculture in March 2024.

Romania (Sub-National I)	ECORURALIS Association	ECORURALIS	WEB	Agriculture, food, short value chain, farm-to-fork
---------------------------------	------------------------	------------	-----	--

Network description: Association of farmers and peasants, which operates at the national level, with almost 20,000 members in all counties of the country. The association was founded in 2009 and represents the interests and rights of peasants, small producers and people working in the countryside in Romania.

Partner / country / status: GEA / ROMANIA / in discussion

Synergy planned: collaboration in workshops

Achieved: no synergies achieved so far

Romania (Sub-National I)	Romanian Forestry Association	ASFOR	WEB	forestry
---------------------------------	-------------------------------	-------	-----	----------

Network description: ASFOR is a professional organization, autonomous, non-governmental and apolitical, of economic agents in the primary wood exploitation and processing industry, representing, supporting and defending their economic, technical, commercial and social interests in relations with public authorities, trade unions and other legal and natural persons, nationally and internationally.

Partner / country / status: GEA / ROMANIA / in discussion

Synergy planned: collaboration in workshops

Achieved: (i) collaborated in promoting and organising workshop on forestry in November 2023, (ii) jointly participated in a workshop organised by CEE2ACT project, coordinator of the National Bioeconomy Hub, in May 2024, with the topic: consultation with stakeholders to develop a roadmap for the bioeconomy in Romania.

Country level	Short name	Managed by	Link	Keywords / Focus area
---------------	------------	------------	------	-----------------------

Slovenia (National)	SRIP circular economy	Algen, UL	WEB	Biomass resources, bioenergy, bioproducts, circular economy
----------------------------	-----------------------	-----------	---------------------	---

Network description:

The Strategic Research and Innovation Partnership – Networks for the transition into circular economy (SRIP – Circular economy) is a connection of Slovenian business subjects, educational and research institutions (RRI), non-governmental organisations and other interested parties, in collaboration with the state, into new value chains according to the economic principles of closed material flows.

Partner / country / status: Algen / Slovenia / Interested

Synergy planned: (i) Mutual transfer of case studies and success cases; (ii) Invitation to be a part of BioRural ERBN; (iii) promotion of national workshops

Achieved: (ii) part of ERBN; (iii) Collaborated in promoting online Knowledge Exchange Workshops

Country level	Short name	Managed by	Link	Keywords / Focus area
---------------	------------	------------	------	-----------------------

ITALY	ICHAR - Italian Association of Biochar producers	CNR	WEB	Biochar, biomaterials
-------	--	-----	---------------------	-----------------------

Network description:

Ichar is the Italian Biochar Association that promote demonstration activities in support of Biochar (vegetable carbon) and its diffusion, through educational tools and projects related to its production and use.

Partner / country / status: AIEL / ITALY / finished

Synergy planned: (i) co-organisation of events and workshops. (ii) Identification of success cases biochar.

Achieved: (ii) Success case biochar identified and reported.

ITALY	Italia Solare	Italia Solare	WEB	Renewable energy
-------	---------------	---------------	---------------------	------------------

Network description:

ITALIA SOLARE is a third sector association that supports the defense of the environment and human health by supporting intelligent and sustainable methods of production, storage, management, and distribution of energy through distributed generation from renewable sources, in particular photovoltaics.

Partner / country / status: AIEL / ITALY / identified

Synergy planned: co-organisation of events and workshops.

Achieved: no synergies achieved so far

ITALY	PescAgri	CIA	WEB	Aquaculture
-------	----------	-----	---------------------	-------------

Network description:

PescAgri is the Italian Fishermen's Association promoted by CIA for the protection, development and enhancement of fishing and aquaculture in all its professional and territorial meanings.

Partner / country / status: AIEL / ITALY / identified

Synergy planned: co-organisation of events and workshops.

Achieved: no synergies achieved so far

Country level	Short name	Managed by	Link	Keywords / Focus area
---------------	------------	------------	------	-----------------------

PT	SPM	SPM	WEB	Biomaterials
----	-----	-----	---------------------	--------------

Network description:

Portuguese Society of Materials (SPM) aims to bring together individuals and legal entities interested in promoting, at a national level, the improvement, development and progress of Materials Science and Technology. It seeks to be the voice of Materials in Portugal and take the lead in discussion and interconnection with political and economic decision-makers, academia, business and civil society.

Partner / country / status: CBE/UC / Portugal / Agreed

Synergy planned: co-organization of events and workshops.

Achieved: Joint organisation of Bio-based industries and services workshop in Portugal.

PT	ASWP	ASWP	WEB	Residues Valorisation, Circular economy
----	------	------	---------------------	---

Network description:

SmartWaste Portugal (ASWP) is a non-profit association whose mission is to enhance the Circular Economy in the various value chains, through education, innovation, collaboration and the creation of new businesses. It intends to establish itself as a hub that brings together and aggregates interests, with a focused perspective for the business.

Partner / country / status: CBE/UC / Portugal / Agreed

Synergy planned: (i) Participation in common events and projects. (ii) Dissemination of actions.

Achieved: (i) Dissemination and (ii) participation by ASWP in the Bio-based industries and services workshop in Portugal.

Country level	Short name	Managed by	Link	Keywords / Focus area
North Macedonia (national)	National Federation of Farmers (NFF)	NFF	WEB	Smallholder farmers, rural development, agricultural advocacy, social inclusion, sustainable farming.[IP1]
<p>Network description: The National Federation of Farmers (NFF) of the Republic of North Macedonia is the country's largest network of agricultural organizations, representing over 10,000 farmers through 43 local unions and cooperatives. As a non-governmental and non-political entity, the NFF advocates for the economic and social rights of smallholder and family-run farms, with a strong focus on rural development, gender equality, youth engagement, and environmental sustainability. Its work includes policy advocacy, capacity-building initiatives, digital sales platforms, and inclusive projects in partnership with international organizations such as We Effect and the EU. Guided by the vision of "Profitable agriculture – stable village," the NFF plays a key role in shaping rural policy and empowering marginalized farming communities across North Macedonia.</p> <p>Partner / country / status: Green Growth Platform / North Macedonia / Agreed and Achieved</p> <p>Synergy planned: (i) Participation in T1.2 survey; (ii) participation in workshops; (iii) collaboration in Online Workshops; (iv) involved in ERBN</p> <p>Achieved: (i) its representatives participated into the BioRural Survey (WP1); (Participated in (ii) National Workshops and (iii) Online Workshops (WP3); (iv) NFF is a member of the ERBN.</p>				

4 Area of action #3: establishing a durable ERBN structure

4.1 Introduction

The third Area of action for the ERBN strategy is the **creation of a structure of organisations to take over the management of the network after BioRural finishes**. For this purpose, it is necessary to set a strategy for the network that generates sufficient value and interest for the network members, but as well to the network managers.

The principal values that the ERBN inherently include were described in D2.1, section 1.3. In summary the main value is the aggregation in a network and platform of key actors and stakeholders interested in small-scale biobased solutions for the bioeconomy progress in rural areas. The values identified are summarised next:

- The value increases as far as the network is well populated, as it talks about the dimension and reach achieved
- The degree the network is active in knowledge transfer, allowing the participants to stay updated on new circular bioeconomy solutions or materials
- An alive community, with a traffic of contacts, demands for services, and growing trend in the volume of materials (bio-based solutions, success cases, etc.) available in the toolkit, which are being facilitated by these ERBN members, not only by the managerial structure of by BioRural partners.
- A functional hosting place for CB communities, where they can host their community, materials, be visible, but at same time, stay connected to other communities (from Operational Groups, thematic networks, EU projects, etc.)
- Potential acknowledgement by national AKIS managers or connected to the knowledge sharing programs to primary sector and rural areas, specialised in practical information on CB solutions for farmers and foresters
- Connected to official well-known platforms like EIP-Agri webpage or the EU-Farmbook, which provide practical information to farmers and foresters on innovative practices, though not specifically on residues and by-products management (circular bioeconomy).

All these values would lead to individuals, OG and project communities, key actors in the knowledge transfer from AKIS, to participate in the ERBN community and its growth. The underlying IT platforms, such as BioRural toolkit, would be a major asset enabling the aforementioned values, and this would together create enough added value for some important organisations in several EU countries to participate and invest resources to collaborate and maintain this community.

4.2 Actions and status at M24

During the evolution of the BioRural project till Month M36, **partners achieved to engage actors to cooperate with project actions**. As explained in detail in section 2, 441 key actors participated in project actions, and 305 supported project and collaborated. Furthermore, **BioRural has attracted actors of multiple profiles adding a community of 616 persons**, 574 visible through the toolkit.

Creating a structure requires however, compromise and resources, which goes beyond of the participation in a community. During the period M12-M24 BioRural partners efforts were scoped to:

1. Approach potential key organisations to become part of ERBN managerial structure and create first core board
2. Define ERBN scope and basic action lines (ERBN definition, mission, potential tasks, working groups)
3. Draft planning of actions and identification of resources to maintain operative the toolkit

By end of the second year of the project (month M24) partners agreed to re-define the scope of the ERBN, to be structured as a thematic network, where the actions and contents start from the needs of the primary sector and rural enterprises. The following factors led to this rescoping:

- The difficulty to engage organisations to compromise with the management of the ERBN community after BioRural finished
- The need to make the ERBN more attractive and complementary with national AKIS purposes
- The opportunity to gather the interest from primary sector and advisors (organisations devoted to the knowledge sharing with farmers and foresters) in a genuine network and environment providing solutions tailored to their urgent needs to find solutions of circularity for residues and by-products

As consequence, the consideration of ERBN as thematic driven network, diverges from the initial envisioning proposed in D2.1 by M12 (ERBN definition, purpose, profile of actors, coordination, communications to be carried, etc.). **From M16 onwards** AVEBIOM worked with CERTH, VDU and other partners in the preparation of a **new definition for ERBN**. A SWOT analysis led to the identification of multiple action lines, as summarised in Table 22 in Deliverable D2.2, here enclosed for more clarity, in Table 22 (SWOT) and Table 23 (strategic actions).

Table 22. SWOT analysis performed by M24 on the re-scoping of ERBN towards thematic division and post-project continuity

Strengths	Weakness
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Several partners are theme specific (agrifood, or bioenergy, or biomaterials, etc.) and are more prone to take leadership if ERBN is thematic • Multiple partners have experience in EU network and project participation • BioRural is part of RBA and is able to engage RBA project coordinators to grow-up the ERBN • ERBN and RBA have both a brand are become being known 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The themes, technologies and success cases in toolkit are selected by partners and not under demand (e.g. from primary sector needs) • ERBN and BioRural toolkit are currently standalone, not linked to any official platform or EU instrument • Ability to engage national AKIS bodies for most of partners (potential involvement is not easy) • Project partners are not representative of primary producers • After project ends viability is not possible without funding or strong role from ERBN board • The current behaviour of most ERBN members is passive (no action after subscription)
Opportunities	Threats
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Lack of knowledge in primary sector on bio-based solutions (they demand knowledge to comply with Green Deal) • Funding opportunities for new bioeconomy networks • EU-Farmbook in initial stage, potential connection with ERBN and BioRural toolkit • modernAKIS initiatives as a path to reinforce connections of ERBN with national AKIS 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • New structure may require more funding or may involve actions not planned under BioRural • To not achieve engagement of sufficient actors on-time • To diverge too much from original scope and cause distrust into current ERBN members • To not achieve integration with existing referential platforms (EU-Farmbook and others) • More networks and projects proceed, possibility to become buffered

Table 23. Strategic actions for ERBN as derived from SWOT analysis performed in M24 by BioRural partners

Strategy lines	Actions to be included in a thematic ERBN network
#1 Re-define the ERBN	The ERBN could be re-defined as: multi-actor (MA) thematic network (TN) for knowledge sharing on innovative solutions for sustainable circular bioeconomy (CB) applicable by farmers and foresters (practitioners) at a local scale in rural areas to cover their most urgent needs on the management of biological by-products and residues
#2 Respond to primary producers urgent needs	Actions to consult most urgent needs on the management of biological by-products and residues, as a first step (demand), followed by the search and identification existing solutions (either from EU projects, Operational Groups or grassroots from primary sector). Urgent needs identification could require surveying, participative workshops, or direct contacts (interviews) and should be enabling to identify areas or regions of more urgency (more prone to adopt solutions).

#3 Offer information more suitable to primary sector	The current toolkit already facilitates simple information, and available in 14 languages. Short summaries on success cases and technologies are available. They could be complemented with testimonials, videos (not necessarily highly edited), materials more practical and incorporating the voice of user or adopter (knowledge sharing format more close to peer-to-peer approach).
#4 Involve RBA projects strongly into ERBN	The collaboration under RBA is being fruitful in terms of supporting the RBA projects communication and dissemination. However, to fully take advantage from the materials, community and tools developed by these projects, it is necessary an agreement for further cooperation with ERBN and toolkit
#5 Connect to EU-Farmbook	EU-Farmbook is the EU-wide interactive knowledge reservoir called to be a dissemination channel most consulted by farmers and foresters with automatic translation services. BioRural toolkit is not currently connected to EU-Farmbook. This requires a negotiation with EU-Farmbook coordinator and dissemination leaders, followed with agreement and resources to build the IT infrastructures to permeate information among both platforms.
#6 Connect to AKIS	ERBN representatives at national level should have a good contact and interaction with national AKIS bodies. The interaction with modernAKIS is a good path. But also it would be advisable to participate into SCAR strategic working groups on bioeconomy and on AKIS. But also would be required to count on with lessons learned and policy recommendations, to be conveyed to these groups. This requires ERBN representatives to take this role, thus becoming one of the potential activities in the ERBN agenda.
#7 Widen the ERBN reach	At the moment the members into ERBN have been engaged by direct communications, though also multiple enrolled freely after participating in events, or learning about the ERBN's goals. ERBN would benefit by growing on base of the communities of practice already created through projects and OGs. These communities could as well get benefited by the services and visualisation offered by the ERBN platform. And by the active knowledge transfer promoted by the ERBN. This would require to revise the method to host and offer value to such existing communities, and to resolve the procedures for easing the affiliation to ERBN through the BioRural toolkit.
#8 ERBN branding should prevail above BioRural	During BioRural lifetime BioRural toolkit and BioRural actions have reached a good branding in the participating countries but as well at EU level. However, after project the remaining brand will be the ERBN, and therefore the actions will be rebranded. A transition is necessary already during BioRural lifetime.
#9 Connection with other EU institutions and programs	Connection with EU CAP Network is fundamental. Participation in working groups or workshops could be part of ERBN board and working group members. It may facilitate the transfer of knowledge as well as of recommendations or urgent needs. Interactions with DG Agri would be also a key action line to make ERBN instrumental for Europe.
#10 Activate and keep offering value to ERBN members	First 24 months for BioRural have evidenced a limited interaction between ERBN members (at least to the extent the toolkit platform allows to track). Potential actions have been proposed in M18 project report. They would contribute to the knowledge transfer and also to connect offer-and-demand (providers of solutions with practitioners). The ERBN should include actions to promote interaction, as well as to become a channel to communicate news of interest beyond the BioRural newsletter.

Following the strategic lines as presented above, the actions performed from M16 till M24 concentrated in the connection with EU-Farmbook by CERTH and AVEBIOM. IUNG as responsible of toolkit has collaborated to identify potential actions to connect with EU-Farmbook. VDU contributed to the EU scope and connections with SCAR or EIP Agri. Valorial and GEA suggested forms of connection with other innovation clusters, with primary producers and the integration of local communities.

All partners have discussed about the potential activation of the ERBN members. Internal workshop in M22 gathered ideas as follows: publish an agenda, facilitate the publication of demands for service or support, deployment of webinars or workshop to capture urgent needs, utilise the ERBN to support the ideas selected under the EU Challenge from M25 onwards.

Furthermore, sources for funding have been detected, as for example Thematic Networks or CircBio calls under HE Cluster 6. Programs like HE CBE JU 2024 calls have been revised as well. At national level partners have been

encouraged to identify sources which could complement ERBN maintenance and upgrade, as could be Operational Groups or programs for knowledge transfer to primary sector.

4.3 ERBN evolution and status by end of BioRural project

From September 2024, the framework has changed as result of the effort of part of the BioRural partners, working together in parallel to BioRural project. The initial connections with EU-Farmbook and the CIRC-Bio sister projects (RuralBioUp, Scale-Up, MainstreamBio) triggered the interest to participate in the launch of ERBN as a thematic network, aligned with the new orientations for the ERBN to become thematic network. A core of organisations started working aside BioRural project, to present a proposal for ERBN as thematic network, which succeeded.

The new project thERBN was conceived and led in a collaboration of University Ghent (leader of EU-Farmbook) with some key partners from BioRural, RuralBioUp, Scale-Up and MainstreamBio. The project obtained funding from Horizon Europe under Grant Agreement 101182955 and the topic [HORIZON-CL6-2024-GOVERNANCE-01-9 - Thematic networks to compile and share knowledge ready for practice.](#)

More info about the new project thERBN is available in:

- CORDIS <https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101182955>
- thERBN webpage www.therbn.eu, which is a landing page with friendly access, leading to the project webpage, embedded into EU-Farmbook: <https://eufarmbook.eu/en/projects/therbn/contributions>

thERBN and BioRural have shared hands-on work on ERBN during 2025. The actions have been coordinated to be additive and complementary. BioRural concentrated in ERBN community growth and toolkit contents. thERBN started with the identification of urgent needs from the primary sector and the analysis of AKIS system in the participating countries. During M25-M36, object of this report, two periods can be distinguished:

- Before thERBN starting date (till 31st December 2024), where BioRural has continued working in the expansion of the ERBN community and BioRural toolkit functionalities
- After thERBN starting date (1st January 2025 onwards), where BioRural has kept working on ERBN community growth, and tuning of BioRural toolkit with some few functionalities. At same time thERBN has started, connecting with projects and actors, identifying farmers and foresters urgent needs, identification of AKIS actors, evaluating soundness of knowledge transfer interfaces for knowledge transfer on CB solutions, effective connections with EU-Farmbook and design of new toolkit functionalities, among others.

A summary of the evolution and BioRural actions related to ERBN is presented next in Table 24.

Table 24. Strategic actions performed by BioRural before and after the starting date of thERBN project

Strategy lines	Actions from M25-M28, before 1 st January 2025 (start date of thERBN)	Actions from M29-M36, 1 st January 2025 onwards (start date of thERBN)
#1 Re-define the ERBN	No further re-scoping (already defined in D2.2)	Starting of thERBN project is itself the realisation of this line.
#2 Respond to primary producers urgent needs	No specific action	Action to consult urgent needs launched under thERBN in January 2025. BioRural transferred thERBN vision gained through the consults to primary sector in WP1, which identify barriers and drivers on adoption of innovations by primary sector and rural smallholders).
#3 Offer information more suitable to primary sector	Partners continued reporting success cases under T2.4. IUNG started changes to allow more languages in BioRural toolkit. RBA members were offered to visit ERBN and upload materials.	New languages were implemented through BioRural. More materials of success cases, technologies and technologies being uploaded to BioRural toolkit.
#4 Involve RBA projects strongly into ERBN	BioRural shared about new project with RBA members.	The new project thERBN (which will lead ERBN transition towards a thematic network), applied to be part of RBA, and became member in March 2025.

		Together with a united voice BioRural and thERBN invited RBA projects to follow ERBN, subscribe community and upload solutions (RBA meeting April 2025). Several project coordinators from RBA have subscribed in thERBN.
#5 Connect to EU-Farmbook	Initial informal dialogues started between IUNG as responsible from BioRural and thERBN, and project coordinators CERTH and University Ghent (UGhent)	Definition of new features was discussed under thERBN. As well the connections and information share between both platforms. BioRural partners discussed about during last General Assembly on 13 th May 2025, held in Brussels. New features and EU-Farmbook connections will be finalised during thERBN project.
#6 Connect to AKIS	Several BioRural partners have kept connecting with national CAP Networks and AKIS actors. Some have entered in contact with AKIS national coordination body.	Continued action, same as before 1 st January. In such occasions shared the continuation and re-scoping of ERBN as a thematic network. thERBN will continue to create national thematic working groups, connected to AKIS, and conforming the base for ERBN structure after BioRural finishes.
#7 Widen the ERBN reach	BioRural partners continued actions to grow the value of ERBN by growing the community (tasks T2.1 & T2.2).	Continued action, same as before 1 st January. No new communities invited to be part of ERBN community. The complexity to create tailored environment and appealing functionalities discussed. thERBN will continue with implementation.
#8 ERBN branding should prevail above BioRural	Contacts of BioRural PC with BioRural PO, to present the issue of toolkit rebranding, to reflect both thERBN and BioRural in the new branded platform.	Discussion BioRural – thERBN about the name, rebranding image in toolkit. Maintaining the name ERBN, to separate conceptually the main asset created (ERBN), which should be long lasting, from the project thERBN, which would be temporal action till end 2027.
#9 Connection with other EU institutions and programs	No specific actions.	Participation in European Rural Circular Bioeconomy Conference 13-14 th May in Brussels, including policy roundtable with distinguished experts and policy representatives from the European Commission. Combined efforts of thERBN and BioRural to connect with European Research Executive Agency (REA).
#10 Activate and keep offering value to ERBN members	A new feature enabled to allow share of ideas and ask for cooperation (following principles of open innovation processes)	Participants in the EU Challenge published their ideas and published an announce of collaboration. Partners and BioRural dissemination leader shared in social media to incentivise their visualisation. New feature for unified search of information. New feature to connect materials (e.g. success case) with owner. New feature to make visible project related to each material uploaded.

Next steps in ERBN after BioRural ends

The project thERBN is the instrument facilitating resources and a plan to continue with ERBN evolution after BioRural finishes. The ERBN counts with an agenda linked to the thERBN project and aiming to embed the network in existing structures or setting up new structures to make the network functional and coordinated as a new EU-wide thematic network.

The foreseen plan is summarised next in a timeline into Table 25.

Table 25. Timeline of ERBN progress after BioRural finishes

Date (by quarters)	Actions related to toolkit	Actions related to community and structure	Knowledge transfer on CB solutions
2025 – Q4	New features for easy upload of materials and integration of CB communities	Creation of national WGs connected to AKIS.	Agricultural residues Step #1. Identification of CB solutions for (>48), training materials for 16 most promising.
2026 – Q1	Reshape and rebranding of toolkit. Uploading sister projects materials.	Host of sister projects communities into ERBN toolkit community	Step #2. Training in 16 zones with pressure / need to solve circularity of agricultural residues
2026 – Q2	Upload of first CB solutions training materials on agricultural residues .	First proposal of thematic network governance.	Step#3. Policy recommendations transferred in Brussels and at national level.

	Premiere, presentation of thERBN in an open impacting EU webinar		Open EU webinar for cross-border knowledge transfer.
2026 – Q3	Keep uploading materials in toolkit (CB solutions for livestock and forestry residues) Tuning of functionalities.	Keep integrating CB communities into thERBN	Livestock residues
2026 – Q4			Step #1, same as above.
2026 – Q1		Consolidate the national links with existing structures.	Step #2, same as above.
2026 – Q2			Step #3, same as above.
2026 – Q3		Agreeing governance, post-project roadmap and coordination.	Forestry and other env. residues
2026 – Q4			Step #1, same as above.
			Step #2, same as above.
			Step #3, same as above.

Following the next plan for 2025 – 2027 period, managed under thERBN project, it is expected to establish a thematic network on Circular Bioeconomy solutions for farmers and foresters, thus expanding the reach initially foreseen by BioRural project.

5 Conclusions

The present document has reported the evolution of key actors engagement and evolution of ERBN community, with a special focus in the last project period, M25-M36. It is the third report, following the initial D2.1 deliverable report on ERBN creation and key actors engagement at M12, and its update at month M24. through the public deliverable D2.2.

The mobilisation of interest from important players and stakeholders in 14 EU countries, as well as at the EU and Brussels scale, is the evidence for of BioRural's accomplishments. More than 900 important players have been contacted by BioRural partners; of these, 441 have taken part in project actions, and 305 have worked with the project. More than 600 people have joined the ERBN community throughout the years, with 574 of them having already registered using the BioRural toolbox. The members gender distribution shows no segmentation, with a paired share of 50 to 50% of male and female genders. More specific details on the figures can be found in sections 2.2 to 2.5 by RBP (SW, SE, NW, NE). The aggregated EU vision is facilitated in section 2.6.

Furthermore, BioRural partners have communicated with other networks and projects at the national and EU levels. A total of 50 synergies with RBA EU projects, five with long-term EU programs like EU-Farmbook or modernAKIS, 35 with EU-funded projects, and 15 with national-funded projects have been leveraged by BioRural. Eleven countries have reached out to the EU CAP and national CAP networks. Thirty-four synergies with national networks and six with EU Bioeconomy networks have been realised. Sections 3.2 for RBA projects, 3.3 for other national and EU initiatives, and 3.4 for EU and national networks contain specific information.

The Circular Bioeconomy (CB) has drawn the attention of several parties who are willing to work with ERBN. The challenge of keeping the ERBN going after BioRural was overcome because of the cooperation of several actors who met during BioRural and agreed to collaborate outside of their projects and initiatives in order to raise resources to turn the ERBN community into a thematic network on the circular bioeconomy. As a result, the ERBN network will continue to exist, and the new ERBN initiative will aim to connect ERBN to national AKIS structures and advisory systems in order to ensure that it continues to be an important resource after 2027.

Through the project partners have established links with multiple actors to participate in project actions, collaborate, register in toolkit to be part of ERBN community and get engaged to keep ERBN active. Some of the lessons learned are as follows:

- Circular bioeconomy and solution for residues and by-product is an appealing topic for most of actors
- BioRural actions were differential from usual events, given the specificity, and therefore participations and collaborations have grown through the project
- Going a step beyond in terms of engagement is, however, complex. Many actors of diverse profiles became allies through the project collaborated punctually. When a more sustained compromise has been proposed, as for maintaining ERBN structure, or to keep uploading materials, the key actors have been in general be more cautious, since it requires efforts and resources.
- It has been stated that national public bodies, government or AKIS coordination bodies are keen to discuss and get informed about CB solutions, bioeconomy landscapes, etc. However, CB is quite specific topic, not a horizontal issue, and therefore is difficult to engage those actors to keep coordinating or maintaining ERBN.
- Through the project it has been stated that small companies with CB solutions for primary sector are quite eager to collaborate. They find toolkit and project actions as an opportunity for visualisation. In other words, the side of the “offer” is eager to participate and contribute.
- On the side of the “demand”, the potential adopters, primary sector, small and medium sized rural companies, cooperatives, or individual farmers and foresters, appear to be more passive. Only more pro-active farmers, visionaries, or innovators, are willing to participate and to get involved into new cooperations. Here a few possible explanations:
 - primary sector is concentrated in their main products (milk, grain, fruits, wood, etc.).

- o For the primary sector, daily life is complicated due to ongoing policy and market changes, consumable costs, the consequences of climate change, and other factors. As a result, they view leftovers and byproducts as non-valuable fractions and are more interested in finding the simplest way to manage or dispose of them than in finding other solutions that might have some potential value.
- o Taking advantage of the by-products through CB solutions is in general not easy in small and medium scales, due to lack of solutions, scales of costs, absence of local markets, or difficulties to enter in new bioeconomy markets.
- o New processes or techniques are not always well known, perceived as non-proven, or simply complex or difficult to get adopted (requiring specialised operators).
- The primary sector's lack of a leading position may also be restricting the ability of decision-makers and policymakers to carry out plans, since the primary sector is requesting other forms of assistance.
- In this context the role of advisors may be crucial, as they are close to primary sector, are able to understand and prescribe solutions, and are usually trusted by farmers and foresters. Still, a higher interest and demand of CB solutions from primary sector could contribute to change the current paradigm

The project thERBN, taking lead in maintenance and transformation of ERBN community into an active thematic network after BioRural finishes, is taking into account these considerations. As a matter of fact, the starting point are the more urgent needs declared by the primary sector, and actions are intended to be connected to areas with more troubles in the management of residues and by-products. Consequently, knowledge transfer and CB solutions are intended to meet the actual needs of the primary sector, hence seeking to stimulate the "demand" for relevant CB solutions.

Overall, BioRural's involvement efforts have been excellent. and has produced pertinent outcomes or products, such as the ERBN community and toolkit, and has encouraged beneficial information sharing, trainings, contacts, and conversations. Consequently, BioRural has produced significant additional value for the EU, which is being utilised by project partners and the new ERBN initiative.

Appendix

ANNEX 1 - Country updates at M36

This annex to D2.3 deliverable report contains the individual updates for the 14 countries taking part in BioRural at the date of M36 (August 2025).

Link to country reports: D2.3 [Annex Country Updates](#)